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D10.2 Final Report on Transnational Access 3

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
TA	Transnational Access
RIL	Research Infrastructure Leader
CA	Contract Agreement
BA	Bilateral Agreement
PI	Principal Investigator

Executive summary

This executive summary presents the global overview of the transnational access (TA) activities conducted in Work Package 10 (WP10) **TA3 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for Everyday Living**, as part of the VITALISE project. As the final comprehensive report, it offers an in-depth review of the transnational access activities conducted across four participating research infrastructures. The final reports completed by the visiting research teams could be provided upon request to the following e-mail: vitalise-helpdesk@googlegroups.com.

The document highlights the significance of transnational access in facilitating collaborative research efforts across different research infrastructures. By granting researchers access to state-of-the-art Living Lab infrastructures, the project aims to foster innovation and advance knowledge in the field of everyday living.

The report reflects on the entire span of the project providing an analysis of all TA activities and the overall evaluation results, highlighting the several research projects conducted, outcomes achieved, and notable advancements or discoveries. This comprehensive overview underlines the TA program's vital role in fulfilling the VITALISE project's primary objectives and demonstrates the tangible impact of these collaborative efforts, underscore the project's enduring commitment to exploring new research avenues and maximizing the potential of Living Lab infrastructures.

As the final comprehensive report, this document is a culmination of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP10's TA3. It showcases the project's success in fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of everyday living. Serving as an essential resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, this report provides critical insights into the project's overall outcomes and its lasting impact in the field.

1. Introduction

1.1. Description of WP10

Work Package 10 (WP10) in the VITALISE project focuses on the centralized and coordinated design and implementation of Transnational Access for Living Lab infrastructures related to the everyday living domain. The term “Transnational Access” (TA) refers to the utilization of VITALISE infrastructures by researchers located in countries other than where the accessed infrastructure is located.

WP10 encompasses several research infrastructures: 1) AUTH's simulated living environment, 2) GAIA's smart spaces, 3) INTRAS' MIND lab, 4) LICALAB's older adults' homes, 5) TREBAG's wellbeing living lab, 6) LAUREA's Activity Living Lab, and 7) AIT's Technology Experience Laboratory.

The support offered during TA visits includes, but is not limited to, logistics management, provision of working space, scientific support by Living Lab researchers for stakeholder management, assistance in preparing and submitting ethical applications, conducting experiments, and technical support for maintenance or resolving technology issues, if necessary.

The TA procedure and manual is handled in WP11 NA4 - Calls for ideas and proposals, experiment selection. Efforts for outreach to new users are described in WP13, utilizing the project website and existing communication channels of ENoLL, EIT Health LL, and Forum LLSA. Capacity-building activities in WP4 and the calls in WP11 facilitate outreach and selection of approved proposals.

1.2. Purpose of the document

The purpose of the D10.2 "Final Report on Transnational Access 3" is to summarize the activities conducted under the VITALISE project's Work Package 10 TA3 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for everyday living. The report describes the completed transnational access activities across seven research infrastructures. It details the research conducted, the outcomes, and significant findings from the completed activities.

As a definitive summary of WP10's TA3 efforts, this report is a testament to the progress achieved in interdisciplinary research and as a valuable tool for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, offering deep insights into the Transnational Access Program impact and the potential directions for future research in the field of everyday living.

The report is linked to the activities and information collected in the Transactional Accesses of WP8 and WP9, having the same structure as D8.2 "Final Report on Transnational Access 1" and D9.2 "Final Report on Transnational Access 2". The final reports completed by the visiting research teams could be provided upon request to the following e-mail: vitalise-helpdesk@googlegroups.com.

1.3. Document Structure

The deliverable is structure as such:

- **Section 1 (Introduction)** provides a description of Work Package 10 (WP10), outlines the purpose of the document, and presents the structure of the report.
- **Section 2 (Transnational Access Projects)** includes the overall evaluation results, as analysed from the responses of visiting researchers to the “After TA evaluation questionnaires”. It also provides details for each Transnational Access (TA) project, presenting in the PROJECT SUMMARY the background, set objectives, adopted research methodologies and the principal results achieved. The CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK of this section not only reflects on the conclusions drawn from each TA project, but also reflects on the immediate aftermath of the TAs and ventures into potential future collaborations and researcher evaluations. Then the TA EVALUATION offers insights of the researchers' evaluation and feedback and present the Living Lab personnel dedicated efforts including hours spent.

- **Section 3 (Discussion)** offers an overview of the WP10 TA results, as well as a reflective analysis including overall LL experience of the Living Labs in relation to the TAs, distilling lessons learnt and experience gained throughout the process, as well as insightful information about the services utilized during the TA research studies.
- **Section 4 (Conclusion)** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2. Transnational Access projects

This section initially presents the overall evaluation results as analysed from the responses of visiting researchers to the “After TA evaluation questionnaire” answers of the Transnational Access to the Transitional Care Infrastructures.

In addition, this section offers an insightful description of all the TA projects that have been performed in each of the WP10 Living Lab infrastructures. It also contains the information in case of cancellation or amendment of the TA.

2.1. Overall evaluation results

The evaluation of the visiting researchers' experience from the TA to the Everyday living environment Infrastructures presented below, is based on their feedback provided through the “After-TA evaluation questionnaire” (see ANNEX), which they were required to complete individually, upon concluding their research studies. These questionnaires, developed by VITALISE partners on the EUSurvey platform prior to the TA Open Calls, were distributed to participating researchers via a provided link for completion. We received a total of 30 responses in the “After-TA evaluation questionnaire” from the 26 TAs to the Everyday living environment Infrastructures.

The analysis of the responses shows an overall positive experience. All 30 responders answered 7 or above to the first question (“How likely are you to recommend Transnational Access to your colleagues or other researchers (0 not at all – 10 very likely)”). We also calculated the Net Promoter Score (NPS), asking respondents to rate the likelihood of recommending the TA experience to colleagues. The NPS is calculated by subtracting the Detractors from the Promoters. Promoters are considered those who answered above or equal to 9, Passives are those that answered from 7 to 8 and Detractors are those who answered below or equal to 6. Twenty-five (25) out of thirty (30) responders, approximately 83.3% were promoters and there were zero (0) detractors. This results in an NPS equal to 83 (Figure 1).

The participants were also asked to rate how well their expectations were met, on a 5-point Likert scale (much higher, higher, as expected, lower, much lower). The total percentage of expectations met is 100% (30 out of 30) that reflects the responders who answered, "much higher", "higher" or "as expected". More precisely, twelve (12) participants stated that the output was "as expected", seven (7) participants responded that they experienced a higher output and eleven (11) participants responded that they experienced a much higher output.

In terms of quality, the analysis of the services provided, shows that the rating is mostly high, with few neutral and low or very low responses in each category. The questions that were analyzed were those of section 6: “Please rate the following services provided by the hosting Living Lab in terms of quality”. The services were rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from very low to very high, also providing the NA option. The services rated were the following:

1. Methodological support and guidance,
2. Physical infrastructure,
3. Expertise/support with end users,
4. Understanding of end-user needs and problems
5. Selection/recruitment of research participants

Each question of section 6 represented one service. The percentage of “very high” and “high” answers was the most common, with few “neutral”, “low” and “very low” answers. The Overall Satisfaction percentage was based on the answers to all the questions that were related to the quality of services. More specifically, we counted all the instances of High and Very High answers to all 5 questions related to the quality of services (143 answers in total, 7 NA values). One hundred twenty-one (121) out of one hundred forty-three (143) responses (84.61%) declared a positive attitude (high or very high satisfaction) for the services provided.

The following dashboard (Figure 1) contains the data visualizations of the analysis conducted on the questionnaires in terms of quality and satisfaction of the TA visiting researchers.

Figure 1. Quality of services provided by the TA LL infrastructures

Further analysis of the answers to the fourth (“What did you appreciate most about the Transnational Access?”) and seventh (“7.B What do you think are key strengths in terms of expertise/coaching/etc. of the visited research infrastructure from the perspective of your research or study?”) open questions, led to the discovery of the TA key strengths, as reported by the researchers. The responses were analyzed using qualitative content analysis. Coding the main points of each answer and grouping them based on common elements, we eventually concluded in the following four (4) categories that represent the TA key strengths.

1. Collaboration and exchange of innovative ideas
2. Expertise and Infrastructure
3. Support and Hospitality
4. Engagement and Co-Creation

Accordingly, following the same method described above, we analyzed the answers to the fifth (“Do you have any suggestions for improvement concerning the Transnational Access?”) and seventh (“7C. What weaknesses in the visited research infrastructure do you believe need to be addressed? These could include any aspect of the institution that hinders your research productivity”) open questions, resulting to the following four (4) TA suggestions for improvement:

1. Enhance Participant Diversity
2. Extend Program Duration and Preparation Time
3. Reduce Bureaucracy and Streamline Processes
4. Improve Technical and Spatial Resources

Additionally, the answers to open questions thirteen (“Is there any other service or product you anticipate needing in your future research?”) and fourteen (“Any additional comments you would like to share with us?”) complemented the strengths or the suggestions of the categories mentioned above.

2.2. Presentation of the TA research projects

This section offers an insightful description of all the TA projects that have been performed in each of the WP10 Living Lab infrastructures. For each TA research project, we have included a dedicated session for the following aspects:

- **PROJECT SUMMARY**

(background, set objectives, adopted research methodologies and the principal results achieved)

- **CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK**

(reflects on the conclusions drawn from each TA project, and on the immediate aftermath of the TAs and ventures into potential future collaborations and researcher evaluations)

- **TA EVALUATION**

(researchers' evaluation and feedback and present the Living Lab personnel dedicated efforts including hours spent, as illustrated in an accompanying excel spreadsheet)

2.2.1. AUTH living environment simulation

AUTH Living Environment Simulation has completed a total of three (3) Transnational Access projects in the period from June 2023 to November 2023. A total of six (6) researchers visited AUTH Living Environment Simulation, three belonging to TA ID34, one belonging to TA ID28 and two to TA ID31. From the TA studies performed in this specific AUTH LL infrastructure, three abstracts were submitted to the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February, 2024.

Table 1. Current status of each TA project in AUTH living environment simulation

Project	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	N° of researchers	In-person visit
Assure (ID34)	March-July 2023	<i>Living lab project planning and management, Legal, regulation, and safety standard support, Capacity building, Expert opinion and advisory services, Co-creation session, Intake and matching, Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping, Panel management, Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation, Simulation test, Equipment and facility rental.</i>	30 (PI)	30 (researcher 1) 21 (researcher 2)	3	03.06.2023-01.07.2023
IoT-MH (ID28)	March-July 2023	<i>Living lab project planning and management, Capacity building, Expert opinion and advisory services, Co-creation session, Legal, regulation, and safety standard support.</i>	-	21	1	10.07.2023-28.07.2023
MADW (ID31)	March-November 2023	<i>Living lab project planning and management, Legal, regulation, and safety standard support, Capacity building, Expert opinion and advisory services, Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping, Panel management,</i>	-	21 (both researchers)	2	16.10.2023-03.11.2023

		Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation, Equipment and facility rental.				
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“ASSURE” project - ID34

Participant Researchers: Carlo Pedrolli (lead applicant), Camilla Nocchi - University of Verona & S. Chiara Hospital, Trento. Added researcher with addendum: Simone Segala -University of Padua.

Project summary

The main focus of the “ASSURE” project (Automatic dySphagia Screening throUgh aRtificial intelligence) was the assessment of a novel technology based on AI (Artificial Intelligence) that can be used to detect the risk of dysphagia among the elderly population. Dysphagia can be defined as the “medical term for swallowing difficulties”. The automatic tool, which is supported by WITA device as software-hardware solution, uses computer vision and artificial intelligence. More specifically, a 3D camera and a digital laryngophone, streamline, through an automatic unsupervised approach, the “Test of Masticating and Swallowing Solids” (TOMASS) which represents a best clinical practice to screen oral phase dysphagia among older subjects. The same is proposed for the timed Swallow Test (TWST), a dysphagia screening test to screen dysphagia for liquids using the swallowing of 150 ml of tapered water measuring the speed to consume 150 mL of tap water in (mL/s) and comparing it with normative data for age. For all the participants, both TOMASS and TWST were performed, recorded and analysed within ASSURE project.

The setup simply required the subject to carry on the activities, as defined by TOMASS and TWST, in front of a camera connected to a computer, while wearing a digital laryngophone strapped to the neck, without the need for the intervention of specialized clinical staff. The study participants were people with no difficulties in swallowing (no-difficulties label) and with difficulties in swallowing or with mild symptoms of dysphagia (difficulties label).

Figure 2. Captures from the clinical trials in AUTH Living Environment simulation and “Hippokraton” General Hospital of Thessaloniki

Prior to the beginning of the test, a complete clinical oral examination was performed, aiming to understand whether the presence of gingival inflammation or the type of the patient's dental formula may interfere and be confounding factors in the diagnosis of dysphagia and thus may lead to a misdiagnosis. Along with the oral examination, the EAT-10 questionnaire was administered to each participant to obtain a complete view of possible swallowing difficulties.

In addition, prior to the test, the operator started the ASSURE software on a PC and filled in the information regarding the gender and age of the participants. Moreover, a clinical history was collected, asking some important clinical data (presence of hypertension, cancer, etc.) and some questions about swallowing liquids and solids, chewing, dentures etc.

For the purposes of this TA, two researchers, Camilla Nocchi from the University of Verona and Simone Segala from the University of Padua visited AUTH Living Environment Simulation in Thessaloniki, Greece, under the supervision of Prof. Carlo Pedrolli. The visiting days were June 3 – July 1, 2023 for Camilla Nocchi and June 6-23, 2023 for Simone Segala. During this period, the two researchers had the opportunity to recruit and perform the test on around 30 participants in total, with the continuous support of the Living Lab's research staff. In particular, the researchers were able to test around 15 people who were at risk of dysphagia (had difficulties in swallowing) and 15 people in the control group (had no difficulty), who had no dysphagic symptoms. In addition, during their visit, the two researchers trained two members of the Living Lab staff, a doctor and a dentist, in order to continue ad hoc the data collection.

Regarding the analysis of the results, a machine-learning algorithm will be implemented to auto-score both TOMASS and TWST from the captured videos. To achieve this, the WITA research team is analysing the videos (this procedure is still undergoing as it is very time consuming). Data (video with soundtrack) are manually reviewed by a member of the research team who manually annotates all the indicators of relevance for the THOMASS test, which refers to the number of bites (with timestamp), number of swallows (both from video and button presses-with timestamp), number of chews (with timestamp) and the total time for completing the tests. Similarly, for the TWST, the number of sips and swallows, and the total time for finishing the 150 mL of water will be manually annotated. This extracted information will be used as a ground truth to assess the efficacy and accuracy of the ASSURE algorithm. The algorithm, which will later be embedded into commercial software, will analyse, blindly, the video and audio channels and will automatically assess the mouth movements (extensions) and position of key points in space, the spatial movement of the larynx, the total time to swallow the cracker, the number of masticatory cycles and masticatory frequency/speed, as well as the average and total time between swallows. From these features the very same indicators, as mentioned above, will be extracted. Automatically extracted data will be then compared to the manually annotated data, and Root-Mean-Square Error (RMSE) will be calculated for model fit. A model with RMSE above 0.75 will be considered to have acceptable accuracy.

Figure 3. Snapshot with the visiting researchers at “Hippokratia” General Hospital of Thessaloniki

Conclusions and Future Outlook

In a nutshell, the ASSURE project demonstrates innovation by integrating AI, computer vision, and a hardware solution (WITA device) to screen for dysphagia. This amalgamation offers a non-invasive and automated approach, allowing for widespread application without the need for specialized clinical staff. In this context, the utilization of TOMASS and TWST, established clinical tests, enhances the credibility of the project's outcomes, along with the inclusion of participants with and without mild symptoms of dysphagia, which ensures a comprehensive assessment of the technology's efficacy across diverse populations. In addition, the complete clinical oral examination and the administration of the EAT 10 questionnaire prior to the tests indicates a thorough approach to identifying potential confounding factors. This pre-test evaluation adds depth to the data analysis and helps in ensuring accurate results.

The ongoing analysis of video data for TOMASS/TWST, though time-consuming, is considered essential for obtaining reliable results and the manual review of videos and subsequent comparison with automatically extracted data using the RMSE metric is crucial for ensuring the accuracy and validity of the technology. Accordingly, pivotal in establishing the technology's reliability and effectiveness is the ongoing algorithm development for auto-scoring TOMASS and TWST.

In parallel, the training of local staff members during the researchers' visit ensures the continuity of data collection, laying the ground for an extended dataset. This not only facilitates the project's scalability and enhances the reliability of the technology, but also contributes to building local research capacity.

The collaboration between researchers from the University of Verona, the University of Padua, and the AUTH Living Environment Simulation showcases a collaborative effort in research that fosters ongoing knowledge exchange and opens avenues for future collaborative projects, potentially expanding the scope of research and the application of AI in healthcare beyond dysphagia screening.

The results of the ASSURE project trials, once finalized, are planned to be disseminated through scientific publications and presentations, after communications between the visiting researchers and the AUTH team to identify the best dissemination opportunities together.

TA Evaluation

For supporting the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. In particular, apart from the LL manager, who was also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), two Ethics & Security Managers, two Administrative & Financial Managers, one technical expert, one doctor, one dentist and some other supportive LL staff (4 more people) were involved. In total, approximately 172 hours were spent by all the mentioned professionals for supporting the realization of ASSURE project in AUTH Living environment simulation, both in person and remotely, which is translated to more or less 32 person days.

Overall, the feedback from the researchers on their experience in the AUTH Living Environment Simulation was very positive. Both researchers reported that the outcome of the TA was as expected or even much higher than expected and that they are very likely to recommend the Transnational Access to their colleagues or other researchers. The researchers also felt that the inclusion of the Fast Track Training during the Transnational Access was very useful, and they rated highly the quality of the services provided by the hosted Living Lab, especially in terms of understanding the needs and problems of end-users and providing methodological support and guidance. They only emphasized the idea of delivering the Fast Track Training before the arrival of the researcher to fully benefit from the in-person visit to conduct the planned tests and experiments. The key strengths of this experience that the researchers reported to have valued most were the AUTH research team who supported them with professionalism throughout the realization of their project, as well as the access to the LL infrastructures and research facilities.

"IoT-MH" project - ID28

Participant researcher: Richard Rak (Lead applicant) - University of Bologna, Italy.

Project summary

The present project, named "IoT-MH" (Privacy and Data Protection Challenges Affecting Internet of Things for Mental Health: Comparative Perspectives and Pathways for Soft Regulation in Europe and Canada) aimed to analyse whether soft law instruments could address privacy and data protection challenges that are specific to the deployment of IoT devices for mental health.

In particular, the study focus was to construct inter-jurisdictional perspectives through collaboration with two Living Labs. One of the researchers, Richard Rak from the University of Bologna, explored and analysed the "EU perspective" of the problem at the AUTH Living Environment Simulation, while another researcher, Elisabeth Steindl from the University of Vienna, studied the "Canadian perspective" at the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab.

For the purposes of this TA project, the researcher Richard Rak from the University of Bologna visited AUTH Living Environment Simulation in Thessaloniki, Greece, between 10-28 of July 2023. During this period, the researcher initially received introduction from the Living Lab (LL) staff on past and ongoing projects that are relevant to the current research topic (i.e. IoT devices/applications intended to be used for mental health purposes). Moreover, the researcher had the opportunity to conduct semi-structured interviews with selected researchers of the AUTH Living Environment Simulation / Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Lab, who have experience in developing and using IoT-enabled mental health applications. The interviews took place at AUTH Living Environment Simulation, subject to the Research Protocol approved by the Ethics Committee of AUTH.

The objective of those interviews was to collect information about the empirical experiences of experts on the state-of-the art advancements in the context of Internet of Health Things and on user (patient) experiences in remote health monitoring. Also, the interviews aimed to shed light on the privacy and data protection challenges relating to the design and deployment of IoT-enabled telehealth devices / applications covering a broad range of challenges such as trust, consent, data minimisation, purpose limitation, sensor fusion, inferences, research and commercial interests, de lege ferenda suggestions. Furthermore, another topic that was explored through the interviews was

the systems architecture considerations and security challenges relating to the design and deployment IoT-enabled telehealth devices /applications, and on how these issues affect privacy and personal data protection. Finally, the interviews focused on obtaining trust, as well as expectations for future (soft) regulation for IoT-enabled telehealth (or smart home) devices /applications that may be used to process personal data for mental health purposes, as well as on what issues a new common data governance protocol for LLs could include.

Afterwards, the analysis of the data collected through the interviews took place in 2 stages: a) content analysis of individual interviews; b) comparison, integration and synthesis of content analysis results. For the first step, the researcher classified the individual answers according to the questions (areas of discussions), evaluating the relevance of the answers to the study. For the second step, the researcher proceeded to a mapping of the recurring answer patterns and identified any deviating answers.

The interviews covered a broad range of privacy and data protection-related challenges relating to the deployment and use of IoT-enabled mental health services. In general, the analysis revealed that the degree of trust in IoT-enabled solutions is influenced by the end users' age, family members, education, technological and digital health literacy, as well as communication (advice) by health professionals (arguably the most important), researchers and technical experts. To obtain trust, it is important to ensure that the process for obtaining consent is transparent, the documents provide comprehensive information, and are supplemented with verbal explanations by health professionals and researchers. Dynamic consent can be useful in the context of research. However, it seemed to be debatable that the patient gives consent freely where a health professional prescribes a digital health application for use.

Another important aspect that was revealed through the interviews was that for ensuring privacy and data protection by default and by design for IoT-enabled solutions in mental health, developers should conduct a data protection impact assessment; apply different pseudonymisation measures in various interactions with the same patient; and implement technical and organisational measures, including security measures on all layers (cloud infrastructure; data transmission between cloud and edge device; version control of the software in the services of the edge device; edge device). From the end users' perspective, experience shows that the deployment of IoT devices do not intrusively affect the behaviour of patients; but a small fraction of patients was bothered by the pressure of having to regularly interact with apps (e.g. to fill PROMs).

In terms of regulatory requirements, the analysis of the interviews showed that the principle of data minimisation is at odds with IoT devices' capabilities and researchers' interest to collect big data for further analyses. In other words, data minimisation creates limitations in research (lots of missed opportunities). There is also a problem of fitting new technologies or healthcare solutions into the existing regulatory framework. Hard law is too slow to keep up with innovation, leading to the need of adopting a more flexible framework.

Regarding IoT-enabled mental health applications, the interviews highlighted that open source should be mandated to improve transparency, security and costs efficiency. The qualification of wellness applications should depend on a proper risk assessment. However, the focus of regulations should not be on exactly which technology is used, but on the outcome of algorithms and what type of information can be inferred. Regulations should provide further safeguards for the processing of psychometric data, and end users should be informed about what type of information can be inferred.

In addition to these regulatory developments, the conducted interviews emphasized the fact that future policy measures should include elimination of stigma related to mental health, increased funding and structures for mental health, and widespread education and raising of awareness to improve digital health literacy and mental health awareness. It was also considered important to democratise research (e.g. through citizen science programs), and to ensure acknowledgments and reciprocity in the secondary use of (mental) health data.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

By collaborating with two Living Labs in two different jurisdictions (EU and Canada), the study aimed to provide a comparative account of regulatory deficiencies and explore whether and which soft law instruments could facilitate good practices in e-mental health in the EU.

The objective of the interviews conducted was to collect information about the empirical experiences of experts, in particular on how they cope with privacy and data protection-related legal, ethical and technological challenges affecting end-users, as well as trust issues. As part of the interviews, the visiting researcher explored the interviewees views on their compliance experiences in light of the current/upcoming regulatory framework. In addition to these issues, the researcher asked the interviewees about their opinion on whether soft law instruments (e.g. standards, codes of conduct, certification mechanisms) could be suitable measures to supplement and strengthen the protection of the privacy and personal data of individuals (data subjects, patients) as end-users of IoT-enabled mental health services.

The expertise of the staff members-interviewees of the two Living Labs was considered to be indispensable to gather insights into what specific privacy and data protection-related concerns (e.g. legal uncertainties, security risks, data management issues) have emerged in the development and testing of IoT devices for mental health in two different regulatory and research environments. The research findings intend to contribute to ongoing policy initiatives and discussions on the possible (soft) regulation of e-mental health services.

As for the dissemination of the results, the researchers have already presented the outcome of their findings at the 15th World Conference on Bioethics, Medical Ethics and Health Law (Porto, 16–19 October 2023) organised by the UNESCO International Chair in Bioethics.

The researchers are also engaged in the relevant EU policy discussions and on 5 October 2023, the Spanish Presidency organised a debate on mental health and addictions, in which the researcher Richard Rak participated. On 10 October 2023, Richard Rak along with his colleague Elisabeth Steindl presented their findings at an event in the European Parliament on mental health hosted by MEP Kypouropoulos and involving Commissioner Kyriakidis and other ENVI MEPs.

TA Evaluation

For supporting the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. Apart from the LL manager who was also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), were involved two Ethics & Security Managers, two Administrative & Financial Managers and a few other staff members who supported the execution of the workshops, either as interviewees or as facilitators. In total, approximately 55 hours were spent by all the mentioned professionals for supporting the realization of IoT-MH project in AUTH Living environment simulation, both in person and remotely, which is translated to more or less 23 person days.

Overall, the feedback from the visiting researcher on his experience in the AUTH Living Environment Simulation can be characterized as very positive. Particularly, the researcher reported that the outcome of the TA was much higher than expected and that he is very likely to recommend the Transnational Access to his colleagues and other researchers. The researcher also reported that the Fast Track Training during the Transnational Access was very useful and of high importance, “offering a helicopter view of the objectives and functionalities of Living Labs”. He also rated very highly the quality of the services provided by the hosted Living Lab, especially in terms of understanding the needs and problems of end-users and providing methodological support and guidance. The only suggestion for the TA improvement by the researcher was a possible reference to legal-ethical issues in the list of indicative research topics. The key strength of this experience that the researcher Richard Rak reported appreciating most, was the professionalism and diversity of expertise/backgrounds of the AUTH LL researchers, offering different and complementary perspectives. He also referred to the importance of the provided access to the LL infrastructures and

research facilities, as well as the opportunity to discuss the practical aspects of privacy and data protection challenges affecting specific projects run by the Living Lab.

"MADW" project - ID31

Participant Researchers: Claudia Chiorean (lead applicant), Simona Malaescu - Babes-Bolyai University in Cluj-Napoca, Romania.

Project summary

The present project MADW – “Multitasking in the Academic Digital World” aimed to i) investigate the relationship between distributive attention, the level of text comprehension in digital space, the level of stress generated from multitasking, and ii) identify new directions of activity in the primary prevention of stress associated with burnout in university students. Multitasking in an academic environment leaves its mark on text comprehension, both at the written and audio or text-conceived levels. Exploring the impact of variables such as ADHD symptoms, virtual reality (VR), and real-time interactions on text comprehension can provide insights into how these elements interact and affect the academic experience. This study is specifically focused on Generation Z as they experience the full brunt of the pressures brought about by the fast pace of the digital world, especially in the context of the “Fear of Missing Out” phenomenon that cultivates the expectation that one must always be online while going about their day. The aim of such investigations is to develop techniques which will allow students to achieve a balance in their tasks between the digital and physical world.

For the purposes of this TA project, two researchers, Claudia Chiorean and Simona Malaescu, from Babes-Bolyai University in Cluj-Napoca, Romania, visited the AUTH Living Environment Simulation in Thessaloniki, Greece, between 15 October and 3 November 2023. To explore these relationships, 20 students from the BioMedical Engineering (BME) postgraduate program were recruited to participate in the project. The BME program was selected as a recruitment pool to ensure that participants are acquainted, to a point, with both digital and medical fields of science. The participants were randomly allocated to either the control group or the intervention group, resulting in 10 participants per group.

The study followed a pre-post schema, leaving a gap of one to two weeks between the two time-points, where the intervention took place. During the pre-intervention and post-intervention stages, all participants were comfortably sitting in front of a laptop screen and provided with an Empatica wristband to wear to monitor their anxiety levels during the process by measuring heart rate, blood pressure, breathing rate, skin temperature, and electrodermal activity. All visual stimuli, mainly text, were presented via a VR headset to not only control any external confounding factors (i.e., movement from the research team) but also to compare comprehension in the digital (VR) versus the physical (in vivo) world (based on data that was collected from a previous rendition of the study run with Romanian students without VR headsets). All audio stimuli were presented using the laptop’s speakers to, in a way, simulate a professor giving a lecture in a classroom.

The pre-intervention stage can be separated into 4 phases: *Phase 1 – Assessment*: Participants were asked to answer three questionnaires measuring stress (Perceived Stress Scale, PSS), burnout (Academic Burnout Scale – ABS), and ADHD symptoms (Adult ADHD Self-Report Scale – ASRS-v1.1), mainly inattention and hyperactivity. *Phase 2 - Comprehension under one stimulus*: Participants were assisted in wearing the VR headset and given 5 minutes to read the presented text, and afterwards, after they removed the headset, they were given 5 minutes to answer some text comprehension questions using the “*Reading Comprehension Academic Performance*” grid. *Phase 3 – Comprehension under two stimuli*: Participants, after wearing the VR headset again, were given 5 minutes to read the presented text (stimulus 1) while also listening to a 5-minute audio (stimulus 2) of a lecture. Afterwards, having removed the headset, they are given 5 minutes per stimulus (total of 5 minutes) to answer a text comprehension questionnaire, and an audio comprehension questionnaire. *Phase 4 – Comprehension under three stimuli*: This phase is a repetition of phase 3 (using a different text (stimulus 1) and audio (stimulus 2)) with the addition that participants, in these 5 minutes, were asked to read the presented text and listen to the audio, they had to think about a

research topic (stimulus 3) their passionate about and 2 reasons why. Finally, they were given 5 minutes per stimulus (total of 15 minutes) to answer the text and audio comprehension questionnaires, as well as write down the research topic and the two reasons they were asked to think about. All texts were about news in the medical field and consisted of 250 words. All audio lectures were extracted from the 9th Panhellenic Conference of the Biomedical Engineering Society and the “What must a Clinical Engineer know regarding Digital Health” webinar. All questionnaires were administered through Google Forms.

The intervention was carried out in two psychoeducation sessions, one with half of the intervention group and another with the remaining half of the intervention group. Each session lasted one hour, during which the external researchers presented strategies and exercises for managing stress when multitasking, focusing on breathing exercises, problem-solving and memorization techniques and their utility. Participants were encouraged to try the exercises but were not required to practice them in their own time.

Figure 4. Captures from the psychoeducation sessions in AUTH Living Environment simulation

The post-intervention stage consisted of two phases: *Phase 1*—Comprehension under three stimuli, which is the same as the pre-intervention phase 4, with a different text and audio stimulus. Participants were requested to think about a current topic in medicine. *Phase 2*—Post assessment, where participants were requested to complete again the PSS, ABS, and ASRS-v1.1 questionnaires.

Figure 5. Captures from the clinical trials in AUTH Living Environment simulation

The collected assessment data are analysed to explore the baseline performance of the Greek students at baseline irrespective of the group each student was assigned and to investigate i) the comprehension in a controlled (VR) vs a real (in vivo) environment by comparing the baseline performance of the Greek students that use VRs and the Romanian students ii) how students exhibiting ADHD symptoms vs no ADHD symptoms performed at baseline and pre. Regarding the baseline performance of the Greek students results indicate that contrary to the consensus on the negative impact of multitasking on comprehension and recall, the participant's performance on several components, mainly the accuracy of retained information, the text free recall and retained information from the audio was not significantly affected by multitasking. These findings are in line with the theory of trained attention, supporting that habitual digital media multitasking, most common in Gen Z, may have a positive impact on cognitive control and may contribute to improved efficiency of control processes.

The findings of the second analysis showcase that controlling the environment where the various stimuli are presented impacts how information is comprehended. Specifically, for a single stimulus, participants in the in vivo environment exhibited better accuracy and working memory under one stimulus, but as the number of stimuli was increased, participants in the VR environment started to outperform them. These results suggest that while VR may not be suited for memorizing information, it may have a positive effect when juggling multiple tasks. Additionally, when looking at the effect of ADHD symptomatology on text and audio comprehension, it becomes apparent that participants in both the in vivo and VR environments are affected by ADHD symptomatology, with these effects being more pronounced in the in-vivo measurements in the presence of one or two stimuli, while the VR participants showcased statistically significant difference in performance only in the presence on one stimulus. For both in vivo and VR participants there were no significant differences between people with and without ADHD symptoms when tackling 3 simultaneous stimuli.

The pre- and post-psychoeducation data, along with the data collected from the Empatica, are still being processed, so at this point, we cannot present results based on them.

Figure 6. Snapshot with the visiting researchers at AUTH Living Environment Simulation

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The MADW study aimed to explore the complex relationship between attention, text and audio comprehension, and the stress induced by multitasking with a focus on Generation Z. By investigating variables such as ADHD symptoms, virtual reality, and increased cognitive load, this transnational access aimed to shed light on how these factors interact and impact an individual's performance when multitasking. Despite the prevailing notion of the negative impact of multitasking on text and audio comprehension and recall, initial findings suggest that certain of their components, such as the accuracy of retained information, the free recall of the given text, and the audio retention, remain unaffected when dealing with multiple stimuli. These results, though counterintuitive, do align with the theory of trained attention, stipulating that frequent digital media multitasking, which is something of a habit for Gen Z, might positively influence the cognitive control necessary in juggling multiple concurrent tasks. Furthermore, this project revealed insights on the effects that a controlled (VR) or real-world environment may have on comprehension tasks, reporting that VR may be suited for assisting comprehension during concurrent tasks and may, to a point, mitigate the effects of ADHD during such tasks.

This study opened an avenue of collaboration between the Babes-Bolyai University and AUTH Living Environment Simulation researchers for further multicentric studies focusing not only on the further improvements and implementations of the existing protocol but also on the development of strategies that help students strike a balance between tasks undertaken in the digital and real-world in tandem. Moreover, further collaborations on this topic may allow the parties involved to delve into how different environments, be they digital or physical, affect learning, resulting in the creation of tailored educational content and environments.

Regarding the dissemination of the results, the researchers have presented the findings of their baseline analysis from the Greek students at the 18th annual International Technology, Education and Development Conference (Valencia, 4-6 March 2024) organised by the International Academy of Technology, Education and Development (IATED, iated.org). Additionally, the researchers along with the AUTH Living Environment Simulation team are in the process of preparing a journal publication presenting the results of their second analysis.

TA Evaluation

For supporting the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. In particular, apart from the LL manager who was also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), were involved two Ethics & Security Managers, two Administrative & Financial Managers, three technical experts, one psychologist and some other supportive LL staff (2 more people). In total, approximately 234 hours were spent by all the mentioned professionals for supporting the realization of MADW project in AUTH Living environment simulation, both in person and remotely, which is translated to more or less 34 person days.

Overall, the researchers' remarks on their experience of the AUTH Living Environment Simulation were very encouraging. Both researchers reported that the outcome of the TA was as expected or even much higher than expected and that they are very likely to recommend the TA experience to their colleagues or other researchers. The researchers also considered that the inclusion of the Fast Track Training during the Transnational Access was very useful and rated highly the quality of the services provided by the hosted Living Lab, particularly in terms of understanding the needs and problems of end-users and providing methodological support and guidance. They also rated highly the expertise and support with end-users and the physical infrastructure. One of the two researchers cited only the compression of planned activities as a perceived weakness, due to the limited time available for the TA execution. The key benefits of this experience that the researchers reported they valued most were the organisational culture of the AUTH LL and the collaborative skills of the host LL research team.

2.2.2. GAIA Smart Spaces

From November 2023 till March 2024 GAIA has performed 4 TA with the participation of 7 researchers.

Table 2. Current status of each TA project in GAIA Smart Spaces

Project name	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA DAYS REMOTE	TA DAYS IN PERSON	N ^a researchers	In-person visit
ID70	March 2024	<i>Expert opinion and advisory services, Stakeholder analysis and mapping, LL project planning and management, Co-creation sessions.</i>	20	4	1	06.03.2024 - 09.03.2024
ID73	November 2023	<i>Expert opinion and advisory services, Stakeholder analysis and mapping, LL project planning and management, Co-creation sessions, Prototyping test, Funding information, Usability testings.</i>	14	3	2	08.11.2023 - 10.11.2023
ID76	January 2024	<i>Expert opinion and advisory services, Stakeholder analysis and mapping, LL project planning and management, Co-creation sessions, Prototyping test, Funding information, Usability testing.</i>	15	7	3	07.01.2024 - 13.01.2024
ID96	February 2024	<i>Expert opinion and advisory services,</i>	20	27	1	01.02.2024 - 26.02.2024

		Stakeholder analysis and mapping, LL project planning and management, Co-creation sessions.				
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“Performing Arts-Smart space” Project - ID70

Participant Researchers: Bar Yitzhaki (lead applicant) - Connecteam, Israel.

Project summary

Project objective is to generate a Performing Arts-Smart space for dialogue, citizen-centred, generating an open innovation ecosystem based on an inclusive user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in a real-life community and setting.

Concretely, this project wants to prove that practicing Performing arts in Smart public spaces improves considerably not only the physical but also the mental health. Art therapy in group settings, which is referred to as group art therapy, can be a treatment that combines art and group therapy (Erickson & Young 2010).

Regarding the specific objectives we are looking for, the pandemic caused by the Covid-19 virus has changed lots of habitudes that we used to have in public spaces, and one of the challenges has been to give a solution to each of the problems caused. The remarkable objectives will be the following:

- Analyse the practicing of performing arts in public Smart spaces and using digital media for giving the participants support.
- Give visibility to the technology use for Performing arts in public smart spaces.
- Co-create a new work methodology for projects aimed at practicing in Smart Spaces and recording and promoting through digital media.

During this TA a cooperation activity was performed with TA ID69 and some of the conclusions are linked to this joint activity.

Performed activities:

- Meeting with stakeholders (public administration, final users and other researchers) in a joint workshop.
- Visiting smart spaces with the analysis of potential use for performing arts with elderly people.

Figure 7. Participation in the workshop

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Based on the activities performed during the TA and the objectives of the TA focusing on the integration of performing arts in smart public spaces to improve both physical and mental health, the following potential conclusions and future outlooks has been identified:

Conclusions

- **Enhanced Health Outcomes:** The TA could demonstrate that practicing performing arts in smart public spaces has a significant positive impact on participants' physical and mental health, supporting the idea that art therapy, especially in group settings, can be an effective treatment modality.
- **Increased Public Engagement:** The TA might conclude that performing arts activities in smart spaces effectively engage the community, fostering a sense of belonging and collective well-being. This engagement can be particularly impactful in post-pandemic recovery, as communities seek to rebuild social connections and public life.
- **Innovation in Art Practices:** The integration of technology and performing arts in public spaces could lead to innovative art practices, enriching the cultural landscape and offering new ways for artists and communities to interact. This could pave the way for a new methodology in performing arts that leverages digital media for support and visibility.
- **Digital Transformation of Public Spaces:** The project may conclude that smart technology plays a crucial role in transforming public spaces into more interactive, engaging, and health-promoting environments. This transformation can redefine public spaces' role in urban settings, making them more adaptable and responsive to community needs.

Future Outlook

- **Scaling and Replication:** Successful implementation of the project could serve as a model for other cities and communities, illustrating how smart public spaces can be utilized to promote health, well-being, and community engagement through performing arts. There may be opportunities to scale and replicate the project in diverse contexts and settings.
- **Policy and Funding Support:** The project's outcomes could inform policy decisions and funding allocations, emphasizing the importance of integrating arts and technology in public health and urban development strategies. There could be increased support for creating smart, art-infused public spaces that contribute to community health and resilience.
- **Technological Advancements:** Future developments in technology could further enhance the potential of performing arts in smart spaces, introducing new tools and platforms for interactive performances, audience engagement, and health monitoring. There could be a focus on developing more sophisticated technologies that seamlessly blend with the artistic experience.
- **Community-Centric Art Projects:** The project highlights the value of community-centred and co-created art projects. Future outlooks might include a stronger emphasis on participatory art practices that empower communities, foster social cohesion, and address societal challenges through creative expression.
- **Research and Evidence Building:** There may be a continued need for research to rigorously evaluate the health and social impacts of performing arts in smart public spaces. Future projects could focus on building a robust evidence base to support the integration of art and technology in public health and urban planning initiatives.

In conclusion, the project's focus on creating a Performing Arts-Smart space represents a pioneering approach to leveraging technology and the arts to enhance community well-being. Its potential successes could inspire a new wave of interdisciplinary projects that address health, social, and cultural objectives in innovative and inclusive ways.

TA Evaluation

According to the evaluation form, the expectation regarding TA was higher than expected. The participant valued positively the fast training where the description of the services and the project carried out in the infrastructure were described.

During the TA there was the possibility of collaboration between two TA coinciding in the same period and it was possible to organise a joint workshop with different stakeholders involved. The opportunity to analyse a new ecosystem, to meet researchers from different countries and to participate in an interdisciplinary international meeting and had the chance to interact with the two infrastructures of GAIA, Ozean Living Lab and Smart Spaces, which allowed to broaden the perspective in terms of the biodiversity, sustainability, as well as social and cultural perspective was one of the most valued aspects of this TA.

Regarding the products used from VITALISE, the web page was the preferred one. Regarding the services provided by the infrastructure and used during the TA the following ones were more valued: understand end-user needs and problems, methodological support and guidance, selection/recruitment of test persons, co-creation sessions; expertise support with end users.

Final comment from researcher: *“It has been a great opportunity to do research in the Basque Country. The importance of the Human factor study, the citizen co-creation and the end user have been very favourable discoveries that I consider important in the development of innovation products and services”.*

both the Technical Manager and the Living Lab Manager dedicating 96 hours each to the TA project.

“Let’s get Actif” Project - ID73

Participant researchers: Sara Goncalves (Lead applicant), Ana Matos – Actif, Portugal

Project summary

The present project aims to evaluate the impact of the 2-month use of a digital platform on the cognitive function and functional capacity of healthy older adults.

We hope that through the transnational access to the Living Labs to have access to the following services: small-scale real-life testing and experimentation, usability testing, co-creation sessions, stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping (market and competitor intelligence services).

The main outcomes will be lower body function as measured by the Short Physical Performance Battery (SPPB) and cognitive function using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment Scale (MoCA) at baseline, after phase 1 post-intervention, after the washout period and after phase 2 post-intervention. Secondary outcomes will be quality of life (EQ-5D-3L), satisfaction with life (SWLs), gait speed and mobility, respectively measured through the 6-Meters Walk test (6MWT) and the Timed-up-and-Go test (TUG). Additionally, a satisfaction questionnaire about the usage of Actif will be conducted to determine the acceptability, adequacy, satisfaction, user-friendliness, and net promoter score, partially based on the Senior Technology Acceptance and Adoption model (STAM).

Activities performed:

- Meeting with different stakeholder
- Co-creation/ validation session with final users.

Agenda for different meetings with stakeholders

ENTITY/PARTICIPANT

<p>JOKIN GARATEA /BEGOÑA BENITO VITALISE project Living Lab description. Fast track training. Expectations Presentation of the agenda for the TA days</p>	
<p>Potential users. Meeting with some potential users. Presentation of the platform and trials. Testing and validation of the platform. Feedback from final users.</p>	
<p>MARIAN GABILONDO BIND 4.0 <i>(online meeting)</i></p>	
<p>DAVID FRIED Virtualware</p>	

<p>IDOIA MUÑOZ CLUSTER SALUD</p>	
<p>IVAN FELIPE MEDIATACK</p>	
<p>ITZIAR VIDORRETA. Osasundata project</p>	
<p>JUAN CARLOS REVUELTA NIRESTREAM</p>	
<p>JOKIN GARATEA Project Memory San Mamés Last conclusions of the transnational access</p>	

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Based on the project's goals, the following potential conclusions have been identified:

- **Positive Impact on Health:** The project likely demonstrated a positive impact on older adults' cognitive functions and physical capabilities, supporting the efficacy of digital platforms in promoting health.
- **Acceptance and Usability:** Findings may indicate a high level of acceptance and usability among the target demographic, highlighting the importance of user-friendly design in technology adoption.
- **Scalability of Solutions:** The scalability and adaptability of digital solutions to different Living Lab environments and the broader market were likely assessed, suggesting pathways for broader implementation.

Regarding the Future Outlook:

- **Expansion to New Markets:** Given the strategic selection of Living Labs and the project's success, there may be potential for expansion into new geographical markets.
- **Further Research and Development:** Continued innovation and research into digital health solutions tailored for older adults could enhance their effectiveness and user engagement.

- **Increased Collaborations:** The project underscores the importance of collaboration between researchers, healthcare professionals, and technology developers to create impactful health interventions.
- **Wider Adoption of Digital Health Technologies:** As evidence of the benefits of such platforms grows, we might see a wider adoption of digital health technologies aimed at improving the lives of the aging population.

TA Evaluation

The feedback from Ana Matos on the VITALISE Transnational Access program highlights a positive experience, particularly valuing access to Bilbao's advanced research infrastructures and the opportunity for collaboration. However, she suggests reducing bureaucratic processes and optimizing survey requirements to improve efficiency. These insights suggest a beneficial impact of the program on research quality while indicating areas for procedural refinement. Future outlooks could focus on streamlining administrative tasks and enhancing researcher support, leveraging feedback to refine the program and further facilitate valuable research collaborations.

Sara Gonçalves' feedback from the VITALISE Transnational Access program highlights an overall positive experience, emphasizing the benefit of meeting potential users. She rates the likelihood of recommending the program as high and finds the Fast Track Training program very useful. However, she notes the program's timing was too short to conduct a full clinical pilot, suggesting a need for extended durations for comprehensive research activities. This feedback underscores the importance of balancing structured programs with the flexibility needed for in-depth research endeavours. Future directions might consider adapting program timelines to better accommodate diverse research needs and enhancing support for pilot studies.

The Technical Manager devoted 62 hours, and the Living Lab Manager invested 74 hours.

Art therapy and Vitamin D for the prevention of cognitive decline of Alzheimer's disease dementia - ID76

Participant researchers: Lorena Serjnaj (Lead applicant), Rezarta Lalo, Jonida Mehmetaj, Kenedia Lalo – University of Vlora "Ismail Qemali", Albania.

Project summary

The main objective of the project is to evaluate the impact of combining creative arts clinical therapies with vitamin D intake on the health and well-being of elderly people with Alzheimer's disease.

A second aim of the research is to investigate the variability in biological parameters (like blood pressure, glucose, cholesterol, and body mass index), creativity parameters and vitamin D intaken.

Activities performed:

- Meeting with different stakeholders related to art and therapy (BDCC, BilbaoFormarte)
- Testing and validation session on art therapy. Feedback from final users.

Figure 8. Snapshots from the session on art therapy

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The project conducted at the Gaia Living Lab in Bilbao, Spain, focused on evaluating the impact of art therapy on the well-being of elderly widow women. Utilizing pre-test and post-test questionnaires, the research aimed to measure changes in mood, psychological distress, and physical and emotional symptoms. The activities included art therapy sessions designed to foster creative expression and emotional well-being.

The project's conclusions might emphasize the positive effects of art therapy on improving mental health and quality of life among the elderly, suggesting the potential for broader application and further study in this area. This highlights the effectiveness of combining non-pharmacological interventions like art therapy with nutritional approaches to enhance cognitive and emotional well-being in elderly populations.

Future outlooks focus on expanding this integrative approach to dementia care, exploring broader applications, and further validating the findings through larger, diverse studies. This innovative strategy represents a promising area for improving dementia care and patient quality of life.

TA Evaluation

Jonida's feedback on the VITALISE Transnational Access program indicates a highly positive experience, with a maximum likelihood of recommendation to colleagues and finding the Fast Track Training program very useful. She appreciated the information analysis and hospitality the most and had no suggestions for improvement, demonstrating the program's effectiveness in meeting her expectations and providing valuable support for her research. This feedback underscores the program's success in facilitating impactful research collaborations and enhancing participants' skills and knowledge.

Lorena Serjanaj's feedback on the VITALISE Transnational Access program is highly positive, indicating a perfect likelihood of recommendation. She appreciated the collaborative approach and adaptability of the GAIA colleagues and the innovative and motivating structure of the GAIA lab. However, she suggested improvements like including a more diverse sample with more participants and men to make the analysis more powerful and unbiased. This feedback reflects the program's success in fostering collaboration and innovation while also highlighting areas for enhancing research diversity and representation.

Rezarta Lalo's feedback on the VITALISE Transnational Access program reflects a highly positive experience, with a maximum likelihood of recommendation. She found the Fast Track Training program extremely useful and appreciated the program's information analysis and hospitality the most. She had no suggestions for improvement, indicating that the program effectively met her expectations and needs. This feedback underscores the program's success in providing valuable research opportunities and support, suggesting a strong foundation for future enhancements and continued positive impact on participants.

The Technical Manager contributed 81 hours, while the Living Lab Manager dedicated 95 hours to the project.

"Tech and Arts against Dementia" Project - ID96

Participant researchers: Francesca Gris (lead applicant) - Istituto Nazionale di Riposo e Cura Anziani (INRCA), Italy.

Project summary (Background, objectives and research activities)

The aim of this TA is to increase the knowledge of technologies that can be applied to non-pharmacological therapies, especially which use arts (i.e. music, dance, pictures...). To do this, a guide of best practice and innovative ideas will be provided. In addition, the TA will be an opportunity to identify ways of assessing the impact of these good practices, through the use of advanced technological tools.

The first phase of the project benefits from the knowledge of the GAIA Lab technology. The aim of this first phase was to identify possible solutions (already tested or innovative) that can support non-pharmacological interventions based on arts. The second phase of the project involves a group of stakeholders (family and/or older people with dementia and/or experts in the field of aging), to share the identified solutions, according to a co-design approach. Finally, the third phase of the project aimed to create a guide that contains innovative ideas to combine the technological potential to the potential that art can have as a non-pharmacological therapy.

During the TA access, different online sessions that involved experts in the field of aging were provided. During these sessions, data from previous and current projects of GAIA were shared to received feedback and co-create the future steps of projects that will use technology, artificial intelligence and arts to promote the well-being of older people.

Figure 9. Snapshots from the online sessions

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The project explored the integration of technology, artificial intelligence, and the arts to enhance the well-being of older people. Expert opinions highlighted the positive impact of arts on well-being and

recognized technology's role in supporting these activities. The project aimed to co-create meaningful solutions for end-users and professionals, acknowledging the potential of artificial intelligence. Future dissemination plans include sharing knowledge within the home institution, the scientific community, and at conferences, with an openness to commercializing the research results. This approach underscores the potential for innovative intersections of technology and the arts in elder care.

Conclusions:

- Technologies can significantly enhance non-pharmacological therapies through the arts, improving the well-being of older adults and those with dementia.
- Co-design approaches involving stakeholders ensure the solutions are user-centred and meet the needs of those affected by aging and dementia.
- The project successfully identified both existing and innovative solutions that leverage technology to support art-based interventions.

Future Outlook:

- Further research and development are needed to refine and validate the identified technological solutions for broader application.
- Expansion of the co-design process to include a wider array of stakeholders for more comprehensive solution development.
- The guide of best practices and innovative ideas will serve as a foundational resource for integrating technology with art therapy, potentially influencing future policies and practices in elder care and dementia treatment.

At the end of the research, the dissemination plan will be:

- Share the knowledge inside the home institution organization (INRCA)
- Share the knowledge with the scientific community through the submission of a paper
- Share the knowledge during conferences in the home country (Italy) that involve community (older people, caregivers, experts in the field of aging)

TA Evaluation

Francesca Gris' evaluation of the VITALISE Transnational Access program reveals a highly positive experience, particularly appreciating the opportunity to learn about integrating technology in the art field. She rated her likelihood to recommend the program highly and found the Fast Track Training program very useful. No suggestions for improvement were made, indicating satisfaction with the program's support and resources. This feedback underscores the program's effectiveness in facilitating interdisciplinary knowledge exchange and fostering innovative research approaches.

The project demanded significant involvement from the Living Lab staff. The Technical Manager contributed 182 hours, while the Living Lab Manager dedicated 194 hours to the project.

2.2.3. INTRAS Living Lab – MINDlab for AHA & Independent Living

INTRAS MINDlab for AHA & Independent Living has completed a total of three (3) Transnational Access projects in the period from October 2023 to March 2024. A total of four (9) researchers received support from INTRAS MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living, four (of three initially planned) belonging to TA ID82 and three belonging to TA ID86 interconnected and envisaging to advance in the work of the MinDNet and finally to adapting the "I Can Do Pathway tool" to Spanish population during co-design sessions and its evaluation. Finally, two researchers within the TA ID94 performing case studies of INTRAS Living Lab projects that have the theme of an active life for the elderly with the application of ICTs, for adaptation to the Douro region. From the TA studies performed in this specific INTRAS LL infrastructure, one abstract was submitted to the Health &

Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February 2024, being selected for the Pitch Presentation.

Table 3. Current status of each TA project in INTRAS VR/ Living Lab

Project	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	Nº of researchers	In-person visit
MinDNet (ID82)	Oct23-Jan24	Capacity building, Grant writing and funding application support service, Panel management, Expert opinion, and advisory services, Living lab project planning and management.	42	8	4	10.12.2023 - 17.12.2023
Span-ICanDo (ID86)	Nov23-Jan24	Capacity building, Legal, regulation and safety standard support, Co-creation session, Expert opinion, and advisory services, Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study, Usability testing.	31	8	3	10.12.2023 - 17.12.2023
CIMDouro (ID94)	Feb-March24	Capacity building, Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping Expert opinion, and advisory services, Legal, regulation and safety standard support, Living lab project planning and management.	13	3	2	11.03.2023 - 13.03.24

"MinDNet" Project- ID82

Participant Researchers: Kristina Niedderer (lead applicant - Manchester Metropolitan University, UK), Jennifer Lim (University of Wolverhampton, UK), Erika Renedo Illarregi (Aalto University, Finland). Added researcher with addendum: Pui Ling Fung (Manchester Metropolitan University, UK).

Project summary (Background, objectives and research activities)

Background: Following the successful completion of the European MinD project in 2020, several European partners came together to establish the MinD network, an international, interdisciplinary, and inter-sectoral consortium dedicated to researching design's application in dementia, mental health, and wellbeing. This international, interdisciplinary network brings together partners from design, psychology, healthcare, and policy domains. The MinD network is committed to exploring how design can support individuals living with mental illness, dementia, and neurodiverse conditions, as well as their caregivers and related stakeholders, by promoting inclusivity, wellbeing, and mindfulness through design interventions. The project draws on the innovative approaches pioneered by the MinD project, which highlighted the potential of design to contribute significantly to wellbeing, prevention, and resilience, beyond traditional medical or technical interventions.

Objectives: The primary objective of the MinD network's Transnational Access (TA) was to support and expand the network's research activities in applying design to dementia and wellbeing. This involved defining a collaborative, multidisciplinary strategy that emphasizes creative and public health approaches and the inclusion of the target groups envisaged. Specific objectives:

- help to establish the MinD network strategy and its values in a spirit of co-production in line with its values.

- help to raise attention and promote the inclusion of EbE (Experts by Experience) in research, design and development activities on an equal basis. The work will look at the key values and strategies for including EbE from vulnerable, minority and ethnicity groups as well as other groups who may benefit from the network's strategy and approach.
- enable developing support mechanisms for advancing and formalising the network and to further the implementation of its aims.

Research Activities: The researchers undertook a series of activities facilitated by the INTRAS Living Lab to co-design the next actions to support a more formal establishment of the MIND Network, and that is pillared in not just the definition of value and roles, including the roles of the targeted users for a participatory government of the network, but also its recognition. The TA included remote collaboration with interdisciplinary meetings involving also key partners of the network, proceeded with a week-long visit to INTRAS, where participants engaged in workshops and training sessions focused on Living Lab methodologies and collaborative innovation in the context of dementia and wellbeing. The activities emphasized hands-on experience with innovative technologies, such as VR for palliative care, and explored the development of social networks and participation strategies to combat isolation and empower individuals as active problem-solvers in their communities.

Figure 10. Snapshots of an experimentation session with multisensorial VR system

The research activities further involved discussions on organizational structures and strategic planning to support the network's ambitious goals. This included efforts to secure future funding and develop proposals aimed at formalizing the network and its inclusive, equitable model. A notable outcome was the drafting of the AHRC Curiosity Award proposal, which seeks to establish a sustainable, mindful co-design approach within the network.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

This TA has been crucial for supporting engagement and interdisciplinary collaboration in enhancing an agenda for the network in the application of design within the realm of dementia and wellbeing. The MinD network has furthered its aim of integrating design into public health strategies, focusing on inclusivity and the empowerment of individuals across different stages of life.

A significant achievement of this collaboration has been the development of a draft for the AHRC Curiosity Award proposal. This initiative seeks to formalize the MinD network, refining its values and embedding these within its operational structure. The emphasis on a mindful co-design approach aims to foster an inclusive environment, promoting the sustainability of the network and its efforts to influence health and care practices positively.

The AHRC Curiosity Award proposal titled "Promoting inclusive and equitable engagement of stakeholders with lived experience of dementia within co-design to improve design-based interventions" aims to revolutionize how stakeholders, particularly those with lived experiences of

dementia, are engaged in the research and development of supportive interventions. By investigating and synthesizing collaborative values and approaches, the proposal intends to establish a more accessible, inclusive, and equitable framework for long-term stakeholder engagement. This initiative not only addresses the current fragmentation and challenges in genuine involvement but also sets a precedent for future collaborations in design and dementia research.

The MinD network's future outlook is focused on extending its research and development activities. The plan includes securing additional funding to support its strategic goals, emphasizing the importance of design in health and wellbeing contexts. Through its innovative approaches, the network aims to contribute to the broader discourse on design's role in health care, particularly in addressing the challenges faced by individuals living with dementia and related conditions.

This TA was significant for the MIND Network mission. The aspirations outlined in the AHRC Curiosity Award proposal are poised to contribute significantly to the field. The focus on developing an inclusive and equitable collaborative framework within the network's setting is anticipated to formalize the MinD network, enabling full operation and fostering a sustainable impact on design and care practices internationally. The approach involves iterative co-design workshops with network partners across the UK, France, Spain, India, and Australia, aiming to implement and test the proposed framework in action (4 Universities involved: Manchester Metropolitan University; University of South Australia; Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee; Université Paul Valéry Montpellier III; 1 European Association - Users Advocacy Organization - Alzheimers Europe).

Figure 11. Snapshot of the remote international meetings

By advancing research, fostering collaborations, and emphasizing the value of design in health and wellbeing, the network seeks to create lasting impacts on care practices, policy, and the lives of those it aims to support. The focus on inclusivity, equity, and collaboration sets a new standard for engaging stakeholders with lived experiences, ensuring that their voices and needs drive the development of impactful design interventions.

Dissemination of the project's outcomes will leverage multiple channels, including the MinD network's website and newsletters, as well as collaborations with organizations such as Alzheimer Europe. The dissemination strategy includes presenting the Framework and the MinD Network strategy at the Alzheimer Europe Conference 2025 for international public validation. Academic outcomes, such as journal article submissions, alongside non-academic engagements, ensure broad awareness and application of the findings. The project's short, medium, and long-term impacts include improving participants' wellbeing, promoting equitable inclusion in design development, and contributing to WHO actions and UN SDG No.3 to enhance global health and wellbeing. These efforts aim to reach a wide audience, sharing insights and fostering discussions around the integration of design and health care.

TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a dedicated team from the LL staff was actively involved. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). Support included a Technical Manager, a Psychologist, an Administrative Manager, and a facilitator.

In total, approximately 100 hours were spent by all the professionals for supporting the realization of the MINDNet research TA in the INTRAS MINDlab for AHA & Independent Living, in a hybrid remote Transnational Access. This is translated to around 13 person days.

The inclusion of the Fast Track Training program was deemed useful, particularly for its role in fostering international collaboration and enhancing skills in co-create and co-design methodologies. The researchers rated the Fast Track Training with overall satisfaction of 8 and 9 out of 10, emphasizing quality of the content and methodology and the value of learning about Living Lab setups. One of the researchers suggested enhancing online content availability with more practical, hands-on resources.

Researchers expressed a high likelihood of recommending TA to colleagues, citing the outcomes met or exceeded their expectations. One researcher appreciated the opportunity for continued international collaboration the most and suggested reducing paperwork to improve the program. Another emphasized the value of implementing co-create and co-design methodologies, proposing that Fast Track Training could be beneficial if offered before the TA to better prepare participants.

Both researchers highly rated the services provided by INTRAS, including the understanding of end-user needs and methodological support. The knowledge and practical experience in co-design methodology available at INTRAS LL were highlighted as key strengths. Suggestions for improvement focused on streamlining administrative processes and enhancing the accessibility and structure of information to maximize the TA program's value for international research collaboration and practical methodology application.

“Span-ICanDo” Project – ID86

Participant Researchers: Isabelle Tournier (lead applicant), Christine-Vanessa Cuervo-Lombard - Université Paul-Valéry Montpellier 3, France; Kristina Niedderer - Manchester Metropolitan University, UK.

Project summary

Background: The Span-ICanDo project emerged from the need to adapt the I Can Do Pathway tool, initially developed for the UK population, to facilitate access and participation in meaningful activities for people living with mild to moderate dementia. This initiative is a continuation of the IDoService project, acknowledging the varying cultural contexts that significantly impact the utility and applicability of such interventions. The project was conducted in collaboration with MINDLab and INTRAS, utilizing their established networks and expertise in co-design methodologies and integrated care in mental health, aging, and well-being.

The I Can Do Pathway is result of one of many sub-projects undergoing after the end of MIND Project (H2020 RISE, 2016-2020), in which a catalogue of ideas for innovative services based on the detected gaps was defined. MIND project has spawned various tools, some available for free on the project website (<https://designingfordementia.eu/resources/mind-designs>) and others commercialized with established partnerships. Notable among these is the All About Us Gameboard <https://relish-life.com/dementia-games/group-games/all-about-us>, a testament to the project's commitment to enhancing dementia care through co-creative, playful, engaging means. Ongoing research and partnerships aim to expand the catalogue of tool's availability, as is the case of Span-ICanDo, starting in the UK, FR and ES.

Objectives:

- To translate the I Can Do Pathway tool into Spanish, making it accessible to the Spanish-speaking population.
- To evaluate the tool's adaptability, usability, and utility through co-design workshops with individuals having mild to moderate dementia and subjective cognitive complaints, alongside their caregivers.

- To explore the possibility of extending the tool's application to individuals with milder cognitive impairments.
- To foster collaborations that will facilitate the dissemination and potential implementation of the tool across Spain, enhancing social participation and well-being among the target population.

Research Activities:

- Translation and Preparation: Initial weeks were dedicated to translating the I Can Do Pathway tool into Spanish and preparing for the ethics application.
- Co-design Workshops: Conducted in December 2023, these workshops engaged different stakeholder groups, including individuals with mild cognitive impairments and mild dementia, as well as relatives of people attending memory clinics. The sessions aimed to gather insights on the tool's relevance, usability, and potential modifications to better suit the Spanish context.
- Data Analysis and Dissemination Planning: Following the workshops, the research team focused on analysing the data collected, translating findings into English, and planning for the dissemination of results. Consideration was given to further research opportunities based on the promising potential for implementing the I Can Do tool in Spain.

Participants in the co-creation sessions pertaining to the group of older adults (n=9, males=7; females=2) with ages range from 54 to 81 years, with an average age of approximately 72 years. From those 4 participants with mild cognitive impairments and 5 participants experiencing moderate levels of cognitive decline. Regarding previous occupations, those were diverse ranging from entrepreneurial roles to skilled manual labour, which suggests a broad range of life experiences and potentially different cognitive reserves or coping strategies. This diversity can provide a richer context for understanding how the I Can Do Pathway tool might be adapted for individuals with different backgrounds. There was a broad spectrum of cognitive challenges associated with diverse diagnoses (e.g. Parkinson's Disease with associated cognitive impairment (P1); a range from mild to moderate cognitive impairments, with some having specific conditions such as Korsakoff's amnesic syndrome (P6) or multi-domain involvement suggestive of Alzheimer's Disease (P7); one participant (P9) has moderate cognitive impairment with a notable difficulty in verbal expression).

Figure 12. Snapshots of the co-creation sessions with older adults with mild to moderate dementia

The group of caregivers (n=4; female=3; male=1) with ages range from 67 to 79 years, with an average age of 72 years, similar to the older adults group, coming from various professional backgrounds, which may contribute different skills and approaches to caregiving. The fact that they are all spouses may reflect a strong personal commitment to their partner's well-being and an intimate understanding of their needs. This close relationship could provide valuable insights into the daily challenges faced by individuals with MCI and the practicalities of supporting them.

Figure 13. Snapshots of the co-creation sessions with informal caregivers

The feedback from both older adults and caregivers on the "ICanDo" Activity Book provided valuable insights into its potential as an engagement tool. Older adults participants expressed that the "ICanDo" Activity Book's visually appealing design and accessible content foster motivation and engagement. However, they recommended simplifying complex concepts and enhancing the book's interactivity to accommodate various levels of cognitive ability. Caregivers highlighted the book's potential to motivate and empower individuals with initial cognitive deterioration, suggesting its use in professional settings for more effective guidance. They advocated for including elements like music for relaxation and emphasized the need for empathetic, knowledgeable facilitators to maximize its benefits.

The feedback was generally positive, indicating that both older adults and caregivers saw potential and value in the "ICanDo" Activity Book as a motivational and engaging tool. They provided constructive suggestions for improvements, which shows a level of investment and interest in making the book more effective for its intended purpose.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The Span-ICanDo project stands as a testament to the collaborative efforts to enhance life quality for those living with cognitive impairments. The "ICanDo" Activity Book, primarily targeting individuals with mild cognitive impairment, has been positively received by both older adults and their caregivers. Its engaging format and the potential for reminiscence and activity planning have been widely acknowledged. However, constructive feedback has pointed towards the need for further simplification of content to cater to varying stages of cognitive decline, as well as the exploration of digital formats which could offer a more inclusive and flexible approach to user engagement.

The project's tools and interventions have shown their relevance and applicability across a shared demographic profile, highlighting the necessity for culturally sensitive health interventions. The inclusion of features such as music and relaxation, along with a digital transformation of the tool, underscores the commitment to innovation and user-centred design.

Moving forward, the Span-ICanDo project is set to embark on a digital transformation, potentially reaching an advanced stage of innovation (SRL 6/7). This transformation will seek to integrate additional features, including stimulation exercises and interactive diaries. These enhancements aim to address broader aspects of cognitive health, such as memory recall, emotional regulation, and behaviour management. The forthcoming pilot study, leveraging the partnership with INTRAS neuropsychology clinic and the established MIND Network, will be pivotal in evaluating the transcultural applicability of the tool. The anticipated research will offer valuable insights into its deployment in Spain and, conceivably, beyond its borders, paving the way for the tool's widespread adoption and adaptation. In essence, the Span-ICanDo project exemplifies a forward-thinking approach in the domain of cognitive health care. Through ongoing research, innovation, and user

engagement, the project is well-positioned to contribute significantly to the well-being of aging populations and to become a benchmark in the field of cognitive impairment interventions.

Span-ICanDo was presented in the VITALISE Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February 2024.

Figure 14. External Researcher participating in the VITALISE Symposium presenting the TA results

TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a dedicated team from the LL staff was actively involved. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). Support included a Technical Manager, two Psychologists, an Administrative Manager, and two facilitators, a Data Analyst. In total, approximately 116 hours were spent by all the professionals for supporting the realization of the Span-ICanDo research TA in the INTRAS MINDlab for AHA & Independent Living, in a hybrid remote Transnational Access. This is translated to around 15 person days.

The feedback from researchers indicates that the Fast Track Training was generally met with high satisfaction, provided valuable knowledge and skills pertinent to their work in the Span-ICanDo project. The high scores for quality and usefulness signal a successful training program that is well-aligned with the researchers' needs, despite some room for refining the emphasis on certain topics to align with individual research priorities. Participants found the sessions on Living Lab services, methodologies, and panel management particularly useful and of high quality. While the topic of harmonisation in the VITALISE project was deemed less relevant to individual research priorities, the comprehensive overview of Living Labs was highly appreciated. Confidence in applying Living Lab concepts in specific research contexts was strengthened, and the training's content was found to be well-aligned with the needs of the researchers. The feedback suggests the program was effective in enhancing researchers' skills and knowledge relevant to their work.

Regarding the final assessment the program was highly recommended by the researchers, with satisfaction scores reflecting the effective meeting of expectations. Researchers appreciated the opportunity to implement co-create and co-design methodologies, access different research facilities, and engage with new publics. Key strengths identified included the hosting Living Lab's expertise in co-design methodology and their welcoming approach. High-quality ratings were given across the board for understanding end-user needs, methodological support, recruitment of test persons, and expertise with end users. The services offered by the Living Lab, including physical infrastructure and methodological guidance, were seen as instrumental in facilitating the research process. However, suggestions for improvement were made, notably the recommendation for streamlining bureaucratic processes to make short in-person stays more efficient. The usefulness of various VITALISE products, such as the Data Tool and Panel Management tool, was acknowledged for providing insights and saving time, with a high likelihood of needing these services in future research.

Overall, the feedback from the final assessment underscores the Transnational Access's success in enhancing researchers' capabilities and fostering valuable research opportunities, despite minor areas for improvement in administrative processes.

“CIMDouro Case Studies” Project – ID94

Participant Researchers: João Rodrigues (lead applicant), Helena Morais, Douro Intermunicipal Community, Portugal

Project summary

Background: The participation of Douro CIM in POCTEP projects has been consistently fruitful. This engagement is characterized as territorial "empowerment," where knowledge exchange, refinement of practices through dialogue, and the acquisition of transposable tools benefit the entire European community. Addressing unique challenges of the Douro region, such as demographic shifts and rural isolation, these projects aim to improve elderly quality of life by leveraging RDi for safety and social connection enhancements.

With previous participation in the POCTEP Integr@tencion project, CIM Douro contributed to the creation and adaptation of innovative solutions for independent living among the elderly. Through pilot projects based on case studies and technology development, closely aligned with user expectations, the focus remained on coordinating proximity care services and designing innovative solutions devices. Leveraging previous collaboration with INTRAS Foundation, particularly in learning from their experiences and innovative service models, further enhances the understanding and alignment of technological solutions with user needs in proximity care services.

Objectives:

Within the framework of this research, the following objectives were pursued:

- To explore participatory research, development and innovation (RDi) initiatives in rural environments, with the aim of generating new experiences that promote active ageing among the older population. In addition, the aim was to gather direct information from real users and other stakeholders to learn about their experiences with the use of these technologies.
- To identify and take advantage of the knowledge and experiences generated in previous European projects in which MINDLab has collaborated. The objective was to facilitate the transfer of this knowledge to the Douro Region, to foster the adoption of some of the best practices and paving the way for the establishment of new supportive collaborations.

Research Activities:

Collaboration with the INTRAS Foundation (MindLab) aimed to draw from their experience in innovative service models, with a particular focus on:

- Exploring participatory RDi projects in rural settings to support active aging.
- Gaining insights from direct experiences with assistive technologies through comprehensive field research, previously hindered by COVID-19 restrictions.
- Enhancing knowledge transfer from European, National and local projects within INTRAS Network through the support of MindLab, fostering new collaborations.

The research methodology encompassed:

- Administrative collaboration and preparatory work with MindLab.
- Development of interview scripts focusing on user experiences with assistive technologies.
- Ethical considerations for engaging end-users and stakeholders in research.
- Field research conducted by Helena Morais, involving interviews with end-users, formal and informal caregivers, and Professionals (Case Managers; Direct Care Assistant) to gather firsthand insights.
- Prospection meetings with Mind Lab for knowledge transfer and future project planning.

Over the course of three days during the in-person Technical Assistance (TA), the first day was devoted to reviewing the materials that supported the field visits, ensuring that the Informed Consent forms were adequate and understandable. The second day included a visit to Toro (Zamora), where the project and innovative service model "A Gusto en mi casa" has been implemented. This project aims to provide support to older adults in rural environments, including access to assistive technologies. The field visit involved engagement with some participants in this pilot, specifically two case managers (who support the service user who was also interviewed), one older adult, and her informal and formal caregivers. Initially, the visit to the Case Managers took place at a Day Care Centre in Toro. The visit to the older adult occurred in the participant's dwelling to ensure comfort (considering living in isolated areas, with challenging transportation, etc.), with the TA researchers being accompanied by the two case managers and a MINDLab team worker (a facilitator and Social Worker with expertise in the project).

The research methodology was carefully designed to obtain comprehensive information from elderly users and professional caregivers, focusing on understanding perceptions, needs, and opportunities for technological improvements in living conditions.

For Elderly Users and informal caregivers: Questions were formulated to gauge elderly users' understanding and trust in technology, their desires for environmental modifications, and their imaginative solutions to improve their quality of life. These questions aim to uncover the elderly's perceptions of technology, setting the stage for comparing these perceptions with the realities observed in the Douro region.

For Professional Caregivers: The professionals were asked about the most frequent requests they receive, challenges faced, and the benefits of case study analysis in including the elderly in participatory solution-building.

This collaboration produced a brief comparative analysis, emphasizing similarities, challenges, and opportunities between regions, highlighting the importance of technology and person-centred research. Future partnership potential was explored extensively, leading to proposals for new public investment directions. The research, in its initial observational and exploratory phase, drew valuable lessons for future involvement. Additionally, the warm welcome, support, and easy access to interviewees and data were crucial aspects of the collaboration.

Figure 15. Snapshots of the study visits

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The researchers' interest in the operations, best practices, organizational structure, and potential for future collaborations with the INTRAS Network underscores their dedication to understanding and replicating successful models within the Douro region.

This collaborative research holds significant potential for impactful outcomes, as both the Intermunicipal Community of the Douro Region in Portugal and the Castilla y León Region in Spain encounter similar challenges. These regions face demographic and social issues like aging

populations and rural isolation, highlighting the need for innovative solutions to enhance the quality of life for the elderly.

Analysing successful case studies from Castilla y León offers invaluable insights to the Douro region, providing a framework to leverage research and development efforts in addressing these challenges and customizing solutions to meet local needs.

Moreover, the knowledge transfer facilitated by MindLab has pinpointed potential areas for the development of new investments and projects, fostering a vision for ongoing collaboration. This experience has not only deepened the researchers' understanding of the elderly's needs but has also established a foundation for future initiatives aimed at benefiting the community. Observations have uncovered striking similarities in user needs across regions, while also highlighting differences in service delivery. Notably, the person-centred approach in Castilla y León, which prioritizes individual needs and integrated service provision, stands out for its comprehensive care model.

TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a specialized team of LL staff actively participated. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). The team was supported by a technical manager, a facilitator (social worker), and an administrative manager. In total, all professionals dedicated approximately 75 hours to support the implementation of the "CIM Douro Case Studies" research at the INTRAS MINDlab for AHA & Independent Living, in a hybrid remote Transnational Access. This translates to about nine (9) person-days.

The survey results provide a comprehensive insight into the experience of the participating researchers in the Transnational Access (TA) program. Initially, prior to the training phase, researchers report high expectations anticipating the benefits from the transnational access. Despite their inexperience with similar programs, they express strong optimism about networking opportunities and establishing groundwork for future collaborations.

During the training phase, the Fast Track Training (FTT) program receives high marks from the researchers, who commend its quality and practicality. The training segments on Living Labs and ethics, along with the methodology and support from the INTRAS team, are particularly praised.

In their concluding surveys, the researchers express high levels of satisfaction with the TA program, noting that it either met or surpassed their expectations. The professionalism and expertise conveyed by the INTRAS team are highlighted, along with the prospects for engaging in future projects. Overall, the researchers exhibit a strong belief in the benefits of integrating Living Lab concepts and methodologies into their future work.

2.2.4. LiCalab older adults' homes

A total of seven projects involving 12 unique external researchers made use of the VITALISE research infrastructure *LiCalab's older adults' homes* (ID20, ID56, ID57, ID58, ID60, ID72, and ID75). ID57 also used the Thomas More Motion lab research infrastructure (see Deliverable 8.2). For calculation of KPIs this latter project was only counted in the Thomas More Motion lab infrastructure. Three projects (ID57, ID58, and ID72) were selected to present their research at the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February 2024. A picture of the presenting researchers is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Researchers that presented their research at the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels

Table 4. Current status of each project in LiCalab older adults' homes

Project	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	Nº of researchers	Visit performed
ID20	March '23	<i>Expert opinion, and advisory services; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Living lab project planning and management; Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping); panel management; co-creation session</i>	0	30	1	02.03.2023 31.03.2023
ID56	Aug'23 Jan '24	– <i>Capacity building; Living lab project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Expert opinion and advisory services; Intake and matching; panel management; co-creation session; prototyping test; usability testing</i>	2	11	1	26-27.08.23; 18.09.23; 22-24.11.23; 13.01.24; 18.01.24; 28-30.01.24
ID57	Oct '23 Jan '24	– <i>LL project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Intake and matching; panel management; concept and proof-of-concept test/concepts feasibility study; and small-scale real-life testing and experimentation.</i>	90	7	2	Lead applicant: 22-26.10.2023; 30-31.01.24
ID58	Oct '23	<i>Innovation network orchestration; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; LL project planning and management; Intake and matching; panel management; co-creation session</i>	1	12	3	Lead applicant: 08.10.2023 21.10.23
ID60	Jan '24 Feb '24	– <i>Panel management; Living Lab project planning and management; expert opinion and advisory</i>	10	6	1	30.01.2024;

		<i>services; legal, regulation and safety standard support; prototype testing; small-scale real-life testing and experimentation; usability testing</i>				26.02.2024 - 01.03.2024
ID72	Nov '23	<i>Living Lab project planning and management; Co-creation session; Expert opinion and advisory services; Panel management; Recruitment and matching; Legal, regulatory and safety standards support; Concept and proof of concept testing.</i>	17	31	5	TD: 5-16.11.2023; 26-28.11.2023 GB: 07-17.11.2023 DF: 05-09.11.2023
ID75	Jan '24- March '24	<i>Living lab project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Expert opinion and advisory services; Intake and matching; Panel management</i>	10	11	1	24.01.2024 - 02.02.24; 20-21.02.2024

“Releasing the power of users” - Project ID20

Researcher: Judy Hong Huang, Stavanger, Norway.

Project summary

The main purpose of the TA were the co-creation sessions with older adults from LiCalab’s user panel to gain insight into the methods for involving users and articulating their voices during the innovation development journey. The preferred method for exploring this question was the User Café, a method derived from the World café, a conversation-based knowledge-sharing method.

Two User Cafés were conducted during this TA in March 2023 concerning the theme “Innovative Products for Daily Life.” Participants were older adults (above 60) recruited by LiCalab from their user panel. During each session, we showcased some innovative Nordic technologies developed to improve the health and well-being of older adults. The older adults were invited to share their opinions regarding the technologies with the group. To facilitate that, we used a template for them to write down their thoughts on post-it notes. The template consisted of four areas: questions (about the technology), (perceived) pros, (perceived) cons, and the (possible) target group. Subsequently, we shared knowledge about the Norwegian healthcare system, including its structure, coverage, healthcare services for older adults in Norway, etc. Then, we invited participants for a short (10-15 minutes) one-on-one interview, asking them about their experiences attending this event. Each session lasted for three hours. Lunch and coffee were served.

In each session, three innovative digital healthcare technologies targeting older adults were introduced. Most of them were developed by start-ups located in Nordic countries. One example of a technology is a web portal for teaching and helping older adults to use public and private digital services. Another is an e-sport cycling app for older adults and their family members to bike in different scenery. The purpose of showing the technologies was to test the methods for user inclusion rather than test or sell any products. The companies or their physical products were absent during the session. One company provided a demo video for us to play on the tablet and for the older adults to try out during the session. In return, we share insights about the technologies we collected from the participants (on post-it notes).

Figure 17. Older adults sharing their opinions on technological innovations in the user café workshop

A total of 25 interviews with 19 unique participants in addition to four interviews with four facilitators were conducted. Participants shared their reasons for joining the activities, opinions, and suggestions on the product and the session. Motivators to participate in the sessions were their willingness to learn about new skills and innovations, meet new people, and contribute to developing technologies that could benefit themselves and others. The "Nordic innovation" was also an exciting topic for them. They were eager to learn about new things. Some even compared it to the Belgian system. They expressed their ideas, including concerns about developing healthcare technologies for older adults, such as safety and the ease/difficulty of using and learning about the new technologies. We saw the importance of understanding the older adults' needs when developing solutions. The focus should be on developing "with" them rather than simply "for" them. Older users are curious about new technologies and are willing to express positive and negative comments after being informed about the importance of their involvement.

In addition to the dedicated User Café sessions defined in the VITALISE proposal, Judy was involved in other pre-planned LiCalab activities. Although most sessions were in Dutch, Judy could observe group dynamics and was engaged in developing co-creation materials and reflecting discussions between facilitators after the sessions.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Older adults play a meaningful role in the evaluation of innovative technological solutions in healthcare and wellbeing. The collaboration between Judy and LiCalab was a success. This was reflected in Judy's second research stay at LiCalab after the VITALISE project ended. Additionally, both universities are involved in writing a book chapter together and LiCalab planned a 3-day visit to Stavanger in Norway in the autumn of 2023 to explore possibilities for future collaborations or partnerships.

TA evaluation

In the evaluation questionnaire, Judy declares that the output of TA was somewhat higher than expected, even though she had high expectations before the start of the project. In advance, she wished to gain a deeper understanding of the LiCalab's user engagement work, including their co-creation methods & tools with users from different stages of the innovation process, and to gain experiences about Living Lab practitioners' work in another contextual environment. The inclusion of the fast track training program during TA was perceived very useful. All Living Lab services provided during TA (understand end-users needs and problems, methodological support and guidance, selection/recruitment of test persons, expertise/support with end-users, physical

infrastructure) were rated very high in terms of quality. Key strengths of LiCalab comprised the close relationship with the user community, deep knowledge of methodologies and experience in practice. All within VITALISE developed products (Data tool, Panel management tool, VITALISE website, and VITALISE wiki page) were rated highly useful and user friendly. The VITALISE website was even evaluated as very high in terms of user friendliness. These products were considered an easy to reach and useful resource during the TA project.

Following LiCalab professionals were involved in the support of this TA project: one business manager, one operations manager, two panel managers, one scientific coordinator and one researcher/psychologist. In total 101,5 dedicated hours were spent by the aforementioned professionals. This corresponds to 20 days during which the LL staff was working on the project. The two panel managers performed most of these hours (73 hours). Transferring knowledge about panel management was an important goal of this project in addition to testing the user café as method for co-creation sessions with older adults. Ethical approval was obtained in Norway, as the study only included healthy older adults. As the file was filled in retrospectively, was not considered the time spent to spontaneous questions asked in between the dedicated time slots. Hence, the number of hours actually spent on the project might be somewhat higher.

“Monitoring quality of life in individuals with Parkinson ‘s disease – Koios Care application” - Project ID56

Researcher: Dimitris Iakovakis, Dimitrios E Iakovakis, Greece.

Project summary

Parkinson's Disease (PD) can significantly impact a person's Quality of Life (QoL), affecting physical, occupational, psychological, and social functioning. As the disease progresses, managing the complexities of living with it can become an increasingly challenging task. Typically, PD patients visit the clinic every six months, which can result in problems such as misdiagnosis and suboptimal care due to the sparse measurements and the subjective tools used. Furthermore, there is no treatment for the disease; the pharmaceutical industry is testing new molecules, but monitoring the effects of the treatment is proven to be a complex task. Finally, current digital solutions (which measure for example tremor) struggle to correctly monitor the effects of the current and potential new treatments on daily life and disease status.

Figure 18. Koios Care application: passive monitoring of key aspects of quality of life

At Koios Care, the mission is to improve care for people with PD by passively collecting data from their daily lives and employing artificial intelligence (AI) for interpretation (see Figure 18). To achieve this, the research team is developing a unique digital experience for the patients and their healthcare teams. Koios Care founders have extensive research and technological expertise in the domain and have developed solutions that make use of commonly used technology, such as the Android smartwatch and smartphone, to capture key aspects of QoL for PD patients. The Koios Care solution can be used (a) by pharmaceutical companies to validate the effects of therapies under test, (b) by

clinicians to improve collaboration and decision-making, and finally, (c) by patients to passively monitor aspects of daily life. In this project, we aim to analyse the user-acceptance of the Koios Care application suite for on the one hand patients and their informal care givers, and on the other hand (para)medical experts. Furthermore, an extension of the use of the app for individuals suffering obesity is assessed interviewing medical experts.

The following workshops and interviews were organized:

- 23/11/23: Two workshops with Parkinson patients and informal caregivers ($N = 12$; of which 6 were patients and 6 informal caregivers). Six other participants dropped out because of illness.
- 8/1/24: Online interview with two paramedical experts from AZ Turnhout hospital (one physiotherapist, one occupational therapist)
- 15/1/24: Interview with three bariatric surgeons from AZ Geel hospital: one had to leave at the start of the interview because of a medical urgency.
- 29/1/24: Interview with a neurologist and a rehabilitation specialist from AZ Geel hospital

Conclusions and Future Outlook

We developed a solution that delivers value to both patients and clinicians by incorporating their feedback, design assessment, user flows evaluation, and product features review. The innovative solution measures meaningful quality-of-life aspects that augment clinical care, such as mobility, cognition, and mood. We validated the clinical relevance of our solution with neurologists and bariatric surgeons, who confirmed its potential to improve patient outcomes and reduce overall healthcare costs. We also assessed the willingness to pay (WTP) of our target market, which reflected how much they value our solution and its health benefits. Future research could comprise clinical trials in which not only the usability but also the effectiveness of the application is tested.

TA Evaluation

Dimitris indicated that the output of the TA was much higher than expected. He appreciated the openness of the researchers and their methodology expertise. When asked for suggestions for improvement, Dimitris suggested a real-time translation service for multicultural interactions. According to Dimitris, LiCalab's strength is their expertise in user research. The weakness that needs to be addressed is introducing a multilingual system to translate for multi-cultural research groups. Dimitris did not use any products or tools developed by VITALISE during his TA.

LiCalab staff involved in this project comprised: an operations manager, one panel manager with a background in physiotherapy, and one researcher/psychologist. A total of 85 dedicated hours were spent by LiCalab staff members to make this project a success.

"Physical activity levels and physical function in mid-life women" Project - ID57

Researchers: Oonagh Giggins (Lead applicant), Suzanne Smith, Dundalk Institute of Technology, Dublin Road, Dundalk, Co Louth, Ireland.

Project summary

In this study, researchers used two VITALISE research infrastructures of Thomas More: Mobilab & Care Motion lab (Deliverable D8.2) and LiCalab Older adults' homes. The current research seeks to address the issue of physical inactivity and functional decline in mid-life-menopausal women. Physical inactivity is a global health issue, with one in four adults not meeting the recommended target levels for physical activity. Physical activity is reported to decline with advancing age, and middle-aged women are more vulnerable to become physically inactive with the menopausal

transition. Regular physical activity results in many health benefits and is an important determinant of physical performance.

Poor physical performance is a predictor of frailty, disability and loss of independence and the menopause transition has been shown to be associated with decreased functioning.

The **aim** of this TA is to examine physical activity levels and physical function in mid-life women and examine whether the menopause is associated with an accelerated decline in physical function and physical activity levels and increased musculoskeletal issues.

To achieve the aim of this research, the following **objectives** have been identified:

- To undertake an examination of physical capability among mid-life (peri-menopausal, menopausal, or post-menopausal) women.
- To capture a quantitative physical capability dataset in this cohort using body worn sensors and compare sensor measurements with measurements obtained using traditional means.
- To characterise daily physical activity levels in the same cohort over a 3-month period.
- To examine differences in physical capability, physical activity and musculoskeletal issues across menopausal stages

This research firstly involves a cross-sectional study and then a subsequent longitudinal study, to determine the physical activity levels and physical capability of a cohort of mid-life women who are also experiencing musculoskeletal problems.

Data collection: October 23 - January 24

- **Demographics**
- **Physical health:** heart rate at rest, blood pressure, weight, body mass index and percentage body fat. Self-reported past medical history (including obstetric and gynaecologic history), use of medications, presence of musculoskeletal disease or conditions, lifestyle related factors (smoking habits, alcohol consumption and daily physical activity levels).
- **Quality of life:** Menopause Rating Scale (MRS)
- **Pain:** the McGill Pain Questionnaire (MPQ)
- **Menopause status** (WHO classifications)
- **Physical capability tests:** Timed Up & Go Test (TUG), the 6-minute walk test (6MWT), postural stability tests, gait speed tests, and grip strength test.
- **Physical activity:** Withings smart watch: Daily physical activity levels (step count) and sleep

Figure 19. Physical capability testing: The grip strenght test

Results and conclusions

Ten female volunteers (age: 56.7 ± 6.3 years, weight: 66.6 ± 7.1 kg, height: 163.8 ± 4.6 cm) took part in the investigation. According to the WHO definition of menopause status, one participant was pre-menopausal, one peri-menopausal, and eight were classified post-menopausal. A descriptive analysis of the data is presented in this report. The group mean (SD) for each of the physical health and physical capability measurements are presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** REF_Ref160188930 \h * MERGEFORMAT **Error! Reference source not found.** outlines each participant MRS score and MPQ as well as each participant average daily step count over the 3-month monitoring period. Further analysis will be performed to investigate the relationship between physical activity, physical function and MSP and quality of life. These insights will in the long run improve quality of life in (peri)menopausal women.

Table 5. Group mean and standard deviation for measures of physical health and physical capability.

	Heart Rate	Systolic Blood pressure	Diastolic Blood Pressure	Grip Strength Left (kg)	Grip Strength Right (kg)	Six minute walk test distance (m)	Gait speed (m/s)
Mean (SD)	70 (12.2)	132 (16.4)	87 (8.5)	22 (5.3)	22 (4.3)	572 (80.3)	1.3 (0.1)

Table 6. Menopause Rating Scale (MRS) and McGill Pain Questionnaire (MPQ) scores as well as Three-month average daily step count for each participant.

Participant ID	MRS	MPQ	3-month daily step count
P0	18	24	8599
P01	17	62	8299
P02	21	24	5568
P03	33	65	5719
P04	26	59	7724
P05	16	42	10808
P06	24	61	5779
P07	22	29	7463

P08	31	42	10293
P09	17	19	11337

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The data is currently being analysed to examine the relationship between physical activity levels and functional capacity and pain and quality of life in this cohort of midlife women. This work is a precursor to future work which will be undertaken by the applicant, which aims to develop a digital physical activity intervention for middle-aged, menopausal women. This project will have a range of impacts, across the short to long term, in areas of national and global health and wellbeing policy. The main output from this work will be the generation of a quantitative physical activity and physical function dataset which will be used to inform the development of a new digital platform targeting an increase in physical activity and a decrease in sedentary behaviour. This has the potential to have a positive impact on middle-aged women who use the intervention, enabling them to take active control of their health and well-being. Although menopause is a normal ageing process, the hormonal changes in this period of life may lead to many physical, physiological and social changes, resulting in deteriorations in quality of life. Increasing physical activity in this cohort may decrease menopausal symptoms and improve quality of life. Empowering middle-aged women to take responsibility for their health and wellbeing by becoming more physically active, may also reduce their risk and/or prevent the onset of several chronic health conditions such as coronary heart disease. This research has therefore the potential to make a significant long-term impact on population health if adopted.

TA Evaluation

Oonagh declared that the TA output was much higher than expected. She very much enjoyed the opportunity to work in a different institution and collect data using equipment she otherwise does not have access to. Additionally, she loved to broaden her network and gain a deeper understanding of the benefit of adopting a Living Lab approach to her research. According to Oonagh, key strengths of LiCalab are the physical infrastructure of the Motion Lab and access to participants (through a large panel). During the TA she made use of the VITALISE website and Wiki page, which she found very user friendly and evaluated neutrally in terms of usefulness.

Thomas More LiCalab and Mobilab&Care staff involved in the current project consisted of one operations manager, one panel manager, one researcher-psychologist, one physiotherapist with an additional degree in engineering, one Matlab expert, and one electromechanical engineer. A total of 166 dedicated hours was spent on this project. Most of the time was devoted to defining the research protocol and writing Matlab codes. Ethical approval was obtained by the applicant in Ireland. Not much intervention was needed during the 3-month remote data collection period.

"Using digital health and wellbeing technologies: bother or burden? - Lego serious play workshops" - Project ID58

Researchers: Suzanne Smith, Oonagh Giggins, Julie Doyle, NetwellCASALA at Dundalk Institute of Technology, Ireland.

Project summary

Collaborative engaged learning has a role to play in how Living Labs interact with stakeholders but is also an effective approach to transfer learning about Living Lab methodologies and processes. The objective of the learning visit is to share knowledge and experiences about Living Lab, panel, and project management as well as stakeholder orchestration. The aim is to enhance the regional reach of the NetwellCASALA lab and develop a co-working relationship with LiCalab for potential future collaborations.

Furthermore, concerning the use of Living Lab tools and methodologies, two Lego Serious play workshops were organized on the topic of digital health and wellbeing technologies (DHWTs). When

discussing DHWTs with older adults, they often declare to find it difficult not only to use innovative technologies, but also to ask others to help them. Assisted by the LiCalab team, Suzanne conducted two Lego Serious Play© workshops with individuals aged 70 or above to map out the bother and burden regarding DHWTs.

Figure 20. Bother or burden in digital health and wellbeing technologies: Lego serious play workshop

Regarding the first collaborative engaged learning part of the TA visit, observational data is collected. The data topics include: how LiCalab manages and engages with panel members and in single stakeholder activities, how activities with multiple stakeholders present are orchestrated, and how integration is managed for projects with home and laboratory or health provider elements.

Regarding the second goal concerning performing concrete Living Lab activities, this study explores understandings of the concepts of burden and bother and considers how differences in meanings may apply to help-seeking for use with Digital Health and Wellbeing Technologies (DHWTs). Two Lego serious play workshops were conducted exploring this issue in older adults (aged 70 and above).

Conclusions and Future Outlook

LiCalab and Netwell Casala exchanged best practices on the topics of panel management, engaging different types of stakeholders, orchestration of Living Lab activities with multiple stakeholders, etc. Suzanne reported to have gained greater insight into how a large Living Lab functions in practice. In particular, how a panel of significant size is managed, how to streamline and automate panel activities such as project calls, consents, surveys, and feedback as well as how to retain active panel members. A working project proposal was started, from collaboration meetings, and tasks assigned for follow-up.

From visiting the simulation lab space 'Experience lab', Suzanne brought back a few ideas to implement in a similar space at her lab, the Natural Environment for Simulation and Testing (NEST)

and she is currently evaluating how these modifications can be utilised to enhance engagement with both internal and external community stakeholders.

The Lego Serious Play workshops will be replicated in Ireland and findings from the full series of workshops will be analysed in collaboration with the LiCalab team for potential publication/presentation.

TA Evaluation

Suzanne indicated that the output of the TA was as expected. She especially appreciated the opportunity to spend time having the 'lived experience' of a Living Lab rather than simply attending events. As a suggestion for improvement, she states that cost reimbursement might be more realistic (higher). Key strengths of LiCalab are the knowledge and experience of the team. In summary, she found that the TA was a valuable and informative experience.

LiCalab staff committed to this project comprised one operations manager, one panel manager, and one researcher-psychologist. The majority of the 56 dedicated hours spent by LiCalab employees concerned recruitment of the healthy older adults and facilitating both Lego serious play workshops. Although Suzanne actively participated during these workshops, some translation was needed as many older adults in Belgium do not speak English. Translation back to English of some video material collected during the workshops was done in half a day using a transcription and translation program.

"Usability testing of a walking aid in a Rehabilitation Environment" - Project ID60

Researcher: Claire Kemlin, Lifebloom, France.

Project summary

Background and objectives

Lifebloom is an industrial medtech that conceives a technology to enable mobility impaired users to stand up and walk on their own. The walking aid solution enables users to live upright, stay in shape and remain in charge of their lives.

The primary aim of the current study is to investigate the usability and user acceptance of the walking aid in hospitalized rehabilitation patients with impaired mobility, but good prognosis to walk again. Additionally, we want to monitor how often, in a period of one to two weeks, the walking aid is used after training, when it is freely available in the rehabilitation setting. Finally, feedback of health care professionals of the rehabilitation unit on the usability of the walking aid is collected.

Research Method

The study consists of two parts being preceded by an information session: the learning phase and the independent use phase.

Information session

Healthcare professionals (mainly physiotherapists) involved in the study are invited for a 3-hour information session. First, a Lifebloom co-worker explains and demonstrates how to use the walking aid. Then, information is provided on the objectives of this study as well as on the modalities for the inclusion of participants (inclusion criteria, informed consent form, etc.).

Inclusion criteria

In order to assess usability of the walking aid, a maximum of 10 preferably hospitalized, but also ambulatory rehabilitation patients is recruited. Inclusion criteria are age < 85 years, weight < 105kg, 71cm < leg length < 94cm, no or few cognitive disorders (assessed by the rehabilitation care professionals), loss of the ability to walk independently < 6 months ago, and motivated to walk again. Patients can have different kinds of diagnoses such as but not limited to stroke, Parkinson, MS, brain

injury, etc. Exclusion criteria are pressure sores/wounds that come into contact with the device, difficulty or impossibility to communicate, any contraindication to stand up or to do any cardio-respiratory exercise, or severe joint deformity (e.g., equinus, flexed knee). A maximum of five patients will be included in the independent use phase, as we have maximum 5 different walking aid devices at our disposal.

Learning phase

The French and English speaking Lifebloom co-worker, who is a physiotherapist, checks the eligibility of the pre-selected participants of the rehabilitation centre. The learning phase consists of 3-5 sessions during which the settings, learning and training are carried out. Each session lasts about 1 hour and is done in addition to the usual rehabilitation program. A healthcare professional of the rehabilitation centre helps with instruction translation for patients who are not able to understand/speak French or English. At the end of this learning phase, the usability of the walking aid is assessed during a 1-hour videotaped evaluation session. This evaluation includes:

- Assessment of the ability to walk with the new walking aid versus with the user's conventional mobility device (for instance a walker),
- Skills observation. Each skill is rated on a scale of 1 to 4, ranging from unable to do the task on his/her own to optimal success.
- Satisfaction and usability questionnaire. The satisfaction questionnaire is a translation of the English QUEST (Quebec User Evaluation of Satisfaction with assistive Technology). The System Usability Scale (SUS) is used to assess usability of the walking aid.

Participants who can stand up and walk safely on their own with the walking aid can continue their participation in the study during an independent use phase. The participation of the others (those that are unable to walk alone safely with the walking aid) ceases at the end of the learning phase after the evaluation session.

Independent use phase

In the independent use phase, the walking aid replaces the participant's wheelchair or other walking aid. Patients are encouraged to use the walking aid as much as possible in their everyday life at the rehabilitation unit. A maximum of five participants is included in this phase as we have five walking aid devices at our disposal. This way, every patient has his own walking aid, adjusted to their specific body characteristics. The phase will last for one to two weeks and is supervised by healthcare professionals of the rehabilitation centre. An actimeter, attached to the back of the walking aid, monitors the frequency of daily use and physical activity/gait parameters during this phase.

At the end of this phase, a second videotaped evaluation session is performed, exploring usability of the walking aid in a similar way to the evaluation at the end of the learning phase. The QUEST survey, User Experience questionnaire (UEQ), the System Usability Scale (SUS), and two items regarding the influence of the walking aid on independence and quality of life (using a six-point scale ranging from -3 diminished to +3 increased) are assessed.

Finally, at the end of the study feedback from care professionals was collected by means of the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) and the System Usability Scale (SUS).

Results

A total of 8 rehabilitants participated in this study. Unfortunately, because of practical issues (mainly time restraints), only one participant was able to use the walking aid independently. Descriptive information on revalidation patients is shown in Table 7. Feedback on user experience and usability was collected from 12 health care professionals (3 doctors, 5 physiotherapists, 1 head of the paramedical team and 3 occupational therapists).

Table 7. Descriptive information about the rehabilitation patients

ID	Gender	Age	Training sessions	Hospitalised vs. ambulatory	Pathology

P1 [^]	M	77	3	H	Stroke with left hemiplegia
P2 [*]	M	62	2	H	Guillain-Barré syndrome
P3	F	52	2	H	Stroke with right hemiplegia
P4	M	79	3	H	Stroke with left hemiplegia
P5	M	68	1	A	Incomplete cervical spinal cord injury
P6	M	61	1	A	Incomplete cervical spinal cord injury
P7	M	60	2	A	Incomplete cervical spinal cord injury
P8 [⊗]	F	72	1	A	Incomplete cervical spinal cord injury

Note. * Patients that participated in the independent use phase. [^] Patients not able to complete the SUS questionnaire. [⊗] No video analysis.

Usability of the walking aid according to patients

During the last session with the patients, the SUS was completed. Results are presented in Figure 21. Out of 6 patients, four reported excellent usability, one patient rated usability as good and one patient was not satisfied with the walking aid’s usability. This low score could be due to multiple reasons. This patient experienced a recent deterioration of his abilities due to increased spasticity and an increased fear of falling due to a recent incident. As a result, his motivation to exercise decreased. He also struggled with the psychological processing of his injury and this manifested as an attitude of resignation.

Overall, the walking aid is perceived as a consistent aid where the functions are well integrated and as an easy to use aid which is not unnecessarily complex. A few learning sessions are needed to get going with the walking aid. With a mean SUS score of 80.83 and a median of 87.5 the walking aid is rated as an excellent device.

Figure 21 Usability scores of the walking aid according to rehabilitation patients.

Note. Patient numbers in this graph do not correspond to the numbers used previously in the tables.

User experience according to rehabilitation care professionals

At the end of the testing week, 12 care professionals (3 doctors, 5 physiotherapists, 1 head of the paramedical team and 3 occupational therapists) completed the UEQ. When interpreting the UEQ, values between -0.8 and 0.8 represent a neutral evaluation and values above 0.8 represent a positive evaluation. The results of the UEQ show that care professionals give the walking aid a positive evaluation on every aspect i.e. attractiveness, perspicuity, efficiency, dependability, stimulation and novelty. The walking aid is perceived as a valuable, interesting, supportive, good and innovative device (values $\geq 2,0$).

Figure 22. User experience of the walking aid according to rehabilitation care professionals (N = 12)

Conclusions and Future Outlook

As data collection ended in March, not all analyses are performed at this point. Overall, we could state that both rehabilitation patients and care professionals were enthusiastic about testing this innovative walking aid that reduces the risk of falling when exercising in a rehabilitation context. Due to time restraints, we were only able to test the independent use phase in one patient. However, the information on this rehabilitant will certainly be valuable to consider when planning future investigations with the walking aid. Future research should elaborate further on independent use and on the effectiveness of using the walking aid in rehabilitation besides its usability and user experience. Lifebloom is currently performing effectiveness studies in two hospitals in France. The aim is to integrate the walking aid in a solution containing an exercise platform as well. This way, rehabilitants can easily access exercises on their mobile phone that are beneficial for their rehabilitation trajectory and the physiotherapist is able to follow up on progression even if exercises are performed at home.

The challenges we encountered had to do with medical ethical approval and striking a balance between providing enough information to get the application approved and not disclosing too much confidential information because of the device patent that is pending. Lifebloom was very scarce providing information or pictures of the device prior to the TA visit. To fulfil ethical application and revision requirements we needed for instance a manual and information brochure to translate into Dutch. Almost all pictures were removed from the original materials which made it very hard to do the translations that referred to step-by-step pictures that were not included anymore. A second challenge consisted of patient availability at the rehabilitation centre. In our first medical ethical application, we decided to focus on rehabilitants under 70 years of age, who were residential patients of the hospital. LiCalab and Lifebloom had tested usability of a previous prototype version of the walking aid a few years ago in nursing homes. Now we wanted to explore whether we could broaden the scope to a younger population in a different context, namely rehabilitation. The rehabilitation unit in Geel only has 12 beds available and by the time we had our ethical approval to start testing only one patient matched inclusion criteria. Therefore, we decided to submit a medical ethical amendment

for inclusion of patients up to 85 years as well as ambulatory patients. In the end, we had a sample of eight patients performing the learning phase of which one patient went through the independent use phase.

LiCalab had previously collaborated with the rehabilitation staff of the hospital in Geel. For this study, one of our panel managers with a background in physiotherapy was available in the clinic for a whole week for assisting and translating instructions from the French and English-speaking physiotherapist of Lifebloom. Both patients and hospital staff enjoyed having two extra physiotherapists at the centre for the week. This close collaboration in the field will strengthen our relationship of trust with the hospital, which is beneficial for future studies. It was the second time we worked with Lifebloom and enjoyed the collaboration with their physiotherapists. Claire has a lot of expertise and even though there was a language barrier, she managed to motivate rehabilitants to participate in the study because of her enthusiasm. If future funding opportunities arise, we would love to work with Lifebloom again.

TA Evaluation

Claire indicated that the outcome of her TA was somewhat higher than expected. What she appreciated most, was the step-by-step support in conducting the usability tests: applying for ethical authorisation, collecting data and analysing results. The key strengths of LiCalab are 1) the experience of the Living Lab members in conducting usability tests with adults in rehabilitation, 2) the network of centres specialising in neurological rehabilitation, and 3) the profile and personality of the Living Lab staff, who are extremely pleasant and interesting to work with. As a weakness of LiCalab Claire mentions the lack of awareness of the time needed to obtain ethical approval. Claire did not use any tools developed by VITALISE during her study.

LiCalab staff working on this case comprised one operations manager, one panel manager with a background in physiotherapy and one researcher-psychologist. One physiotherapist of the hospital was involved in preparatory discussions to align the protocol with the needs and possibilities at the rehabilitation centre. The team also worked closely together with two other physiotherapists of the rehabilitation centre in Geel. Because of their relationship of trust with the rehabilitation patients, they assisted in recruiting and preselecting possible candidates for the study. A total of 198 dedicated hours was spent by LiCalab's staff on this project. Prior to the visit, a lot of time was devoted to the protocol, medical ethical application and its revision. Ethical approval was needed from both the local ethical committee of the hospital where the study was performed, as well as the central university ethical committee. Translation of the manual and information brochure also took quite some hours despite the use of a translation program. During the visit, LiCalab's panel manager with a background in physiotherapy was available at the rehabilitation centre the entire time of the study for assistance and translation of instructions to the patients into Dutch. After the study, a report with all results and findings was written by LiCalab staff.

"Sound Wellbeing in Later Life: Exploring wellbeing through contextual understanding of sound and sonic reminiscence" - Project ID72

Researchers Ai4S team: Mark Plumbley, Thomas Deacon, Arshdeep Singh, Gabriel Bibbó, David Frohlich, University of Surrey, UK.

Project summary

Background and objectives

The AI for Sound (AI4S) project aims to improve the wellbeing of older adults in their homes by developing AI sound sensing technologies. The study focuses on two objectives: understanding sound contexts and sonic reminiscence technologies. The project seeks to understand individuals' relationships to sounds and sonic memory in the home, focusing on sound preferences, linking sounds to domestic activities and routines, exploring what people want from AI sound technologies, gathering reflections on memorable daily moments and the sounds in them, and asking what people

want to remember. Through in-the-wild research and co-design activities, AI4S aims to understand when, why, and how people would engage with AI sound technologies. Using a data capture deployment pilot, AI4S can analyse sounds in the home to develop technical innovations and data insights related to understanding sound contexts. The research from co-design can help gain a deeper understanding of user needs, desires, and expectations around AI sound technology in the home, informing the development of sonic reminiscence technologies to support emotional wellbeing. Our vision is to develop personal informatics technologies that enable us to capture and interact with sonic memories throughout our life journeys, from youth to old age.

Research Method

The study consists of three phases: 1) Pre-APD phase, 2) Activity Probe Deployment – APD phase, and 3) Post- APD phase. An overview of the research can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 23. Overview and flow of planned activities.

Note. Name initialisation: Mark Plumbley (MP), Thomas Deacon (TD), Arshdeep Singh (AS), Gabriel Bibbó (GB), David Frohlich (DF).

In the **Pre-APD phase**, the eight selected healthy older adults are consulted through a 2-hour **Kick-off and probe onboarding session** to introduce the study, provide participants with their probe pack, address any deployment concerns, and introduce a deep listening practice. We aim to create a nurturing space where people could voice their expectations, needs, questions, and wants. The session also provides a space to introduce the concept of soundscapes and deep listening to participants, this will be activated by a listening and reflection task. The probe onboarding consists of getting participants signed up to the ESM app and study, providing them with their audio recording systems, probe materials, and probe instructions.

In addition, a baseline survey is provided through the Qualtrics platform, comprising the following themes: demographic information, self-rated hearing ability, quality of life, and mental well-being.

The **second phase**, which is called the **activity probe deployment (APD)**, lasts for seven days. It is based on the experience sampling method (ESM) and the day reconstruction method (DRM), utilising the Audiomoth audio recording system and cultural probes to collect data on occupants' activities, soundscapes, preferences, habits, and routines within the home. The audio recording system (ARS) is installed in participants' homes by the AI4S team accompanied by a LiCalab employee. The ESM probes/activities were presented on participants' own mobile devices with a trigger limit of max 3 notifications a day across both the Soundscape and Memory probes (week overview presented in Figure 2). Participants had the possibility to do extra optional tasks whenever they wanted during this week.

Figure 24. Ethica notification schedule

In the third **Post-APD phase**, we engage the older adults in a 75-minute **focus group**. It provides a space for participants to share their experience of the APD and the researchers can also collect the probe materials completed by participants. We use the contributions from cultural probes as a basis for focus group activities, participation is entirely voluntary. We will use these insights to iterate design solutions of current sonic reminiscence technologies after the TA period. Furthermore, an endline survey is completed to reflect on the process of the APD.

Results

Figure 25. Kick-off and probe onboarding session

Not all analyses have been conducted at this point, but the following information was collected:

- Baseline and end-line wellbeing surveys provide a metric for assessing positive and negative impacts.
- A significant amount of multimedia data and self-reports collected through the Ethica platform, focusing on soundscape and memory.

- A large dataset of audio files capturing indoor soundscapes in the homes of older people. This dataset can be used for machine learning tasks and innovations in speech removal techniques.
- Physical materials collected by the Cultural Probe, providing insights into people's relationships with sound, memory, and place.
- Field observations and insights into people's lives, domestic patterns, and behaviours.
- Improvements to the research protocol achieved through discussions about the pros and cons of the current deployment.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Data processing and analyses are still ongoing as we collected a huge amount of information. We very much enjoyed collaboration with these researchers. Especially the lead applicant was always well-prepared in meetings, providing all necessary information as soon as possible. Whenever needed he chased the other applications to fulfil practical requirements such as completing evaluation questionnaires. Because his high level of expertise in design and technologies that can be used for collecting data with the Experience Sampling Method, we had the feeling we learned a lot as well from this exchange. The study had a rather broad scope, combining different aspects of sound research. During the kick-off session, installation of the sound recording devices at older individuals' homes and during the focus group, Thomas tried to interact as much as possible with the participants, despite the language barrier. He was amazed by the devotion of our panel members participating in the study. Participants completed more exercises and assignments than anticipated. We are discussing about future collaborations and workshops as a follow up for the current study. These workshops will probably take place around June '24.

TA Evaluation

The AI4S researchers stated that the outcome of the project was much higher than expected. Most appreciated were the ground insights by taking part in research deployment with the LiCalab team. Suggestions for improvement concerned improved structure and communication of VITALISE requirements as well as more time between VITALISE bid award and delivery of study protocol. Key strengths of LiCalab are their understanding of their community and their needs as well as their positive and caring attitude. A weakness was that the focus group rooms could be improved in technical offerings, e.g. no AV capture facilities built in and poor output from the audio system. The VITALISE website and wiki page were consulted several times during the TA. Its user friendliness was rated neutral, whereas usefulness was indicated to be high for the website and very high for the wiki page. Researchers indicated that the Wiki page is comprehensive work providing clear guidance to structure submissions and think about possibilities. However, they found the VITALISE website a bit "noisy" and difficult to navigate at times. The AI4S team declares to be willing to return to the LiCalab facility to conduct further co-design iterations with the community. The closing words of the lead applicant in the TA evaluation survey were 'Beyond the research utility value, it was great experience and helped me develop as a researcher. The team at LiCalab are stellar!'

The following LiCalab staff was involved in the current study: one operations manager, one panel manager, and one researcher-psychologist. Because of the sensitive nature of the study, the DPO and legal counsellor from Thomas More were contacted for support regarding the ethics application. A total of 137 hours was devoted to this project. During the preparations, most time was spent on the ethical application and translation of the materials provided by the applicants. During the TA, all sound recording devices were placed in older adults' homes under supervision of a LiCalab staff member. Furthermore, the kick-off session and focus group workshop were moderated by LiCalab's panel manager. After the TA, some time was spent on transcribing handwritten Dutch materials from the final workshop to be digitally translated to English afterwards.

"Readiness tools to accelerate innovation from R&D to service exploitations" - ID75

Researchers: Janette Hughes, Digital Health Care and Innovation Centre, UK.

Project summary

Background and objectives

Economic development and commercial innovation for Digital health and care is a massive opportunity with the option to drive economic growth through Living Labs methodology. However, it remains challenging for Digital health and care related innovators to converge business and service readiness support, and without this it remains a recognised key barrier. The Digital Health and Care innovation centre in Scotland and through the Rural centre of excellence Living Labs utilise an elementary technology, service and business readiness which relates to the service readiness level research (Hughes, 2021) that has evolved over recent years. This readiness framework presented in Figure 26 is used by DHI as a baselining, scoping, and evidence related tool/checklist. It also acts as a useful conversation prompt for all stakeholders to understand their current status and the steps and evidence (Hughes, 2021) they need to gather to build a business case for scale, where and if digital can be embedded within a service. In addition, this tool importantly allows industry and commercial activities need to be covered to reach a commercial sale for this sector in line with the use of Living Lab methodology. This project will explore with other LL partners if similar tools can be merged to meet the pressing need of faster commercialisation for this sector.

Research Method

Workshops and interviews took place to assist in gathering key views and insights from partners involved in Living Labs (LLs) to seek the views and experience from LLs to assist in furthering a readiness framework with a particular focus on the business readiness levels for scaling and commercializing DHI products and services, and to further the LL support knowledge in this field. Ethical Approval was obtained from the University of Strathclyde.

A physical workshop as well as some **one-on-one interviews** took place as part of the field visit to LiCalab at the end of January 2024 with relevant LiCalab team members. The 2-hour **workshop** took place on 25th January with 5 participants present. The roles ranged from Business manager, Project manager, Panel manager, Project coordinator and Research Fellow. The agenda of the workshop was as follows:

- Introduction and Welcome - High level overview of TA research – title and objectives
- Overview of the DHI readiness levels and how we use this – case study Scotcap
- Open discussion and use case study examples used from Licalab team to probe and surface the tools they used. These examples were then mapped onto the DHI readiness framework – with debate/comment and suggestions of retitles, reorders and renaming – and how this linked Service and Business readiness levels. Individual in-depth interviews were conducted with 3 key members of the Licalab team as part of a follow up with deeper dive with key team members – Project, Panel and Research and support functions discussed and how this would map to the readiness levels.

Contact with other Living Lab practitioners was facilitated by LiCalab and Janette's presence at the Health & wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels on February 20. Several conversations with other LL infrastructure partners allowed her to share the framework and how it was used in Scotland to manage project movements, on the journey to adoption and scale. This visit enabled subsequent interviews to be set up and key connections to be made, this included; Canada - [McGill's University](#) Spain - [GAIA](#) Spain - [Intras](#) Bulgaria – [Anthology ventures](#) Finland - [Laurea University](#) Ireland – [Dundalk University](#) Greece – [ASSOS](#).

From these workshops and interviews a range of feedback and insight emerged that created insights and findings that could adjust the readiness framework to allow it to be better translated across Living Labs. This was sketched out and documented in a Miro board with the main points summarised and synthesised – Miro board link is as follows - <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVNNAG0aM=/> detailing the general feedback and case study examples that were provided.

Workshop #2 (5 people) – representatives from Finland, Greece and Bulgaria - General discussion on the readiness framework and how their labs supported innovation and whether any frameworks

were used. Finland pointed to the Technology readiness framework that helped map LL work Innovation process phase with key descriptions, that connects with readiness innovation framework. **Workshop #3** – (2 people) representatives from Canada and Spain.

The readiness framework was demonstrated which allowed the workshop participants key input that allowed the feedback which in turn could allow it to be reordered and where necessary re-titled.

Figure 26. Technology, Service and Business Readiness level framework

Technical readiness levels	Service readiness levels	Commercial readiness levels
TR9 – Live implementation proven	SR9 – Service change implemented - BAU	BR9 – Commercial sale
TR8 – system complete/qualified	SR8 – Develop Case for scale	BR8 – Reference site, real world test - Business plan/model refined
TR7 - working model demonstrated	SR7 – Evaluation and Evidence concluded	BR7 – Procurement route framework and IP – clarified
TR6 - fully functional prototype	SR6 – Change pilot test - RWE/LL	BR6 – Regulation and Standards – interoperability is key
TR5 - rigorous testing undertaken	SR5 – Future state accepted in principle - Simulated to de-risk	BR5 – Acceptable business and commercial models tested
TR4 – technical validation	SR4 - Future state options co-designed	BR4 – Product fit, tested and adapted and accessible etc....
TR3 - proof-of-concept constructed	SR3 – Current state understood/accepted	BR3 – Business plan for industry and commercialisation considered
TR2 - basic principles studied	SR2 – Market/Gap analysis; best practice (hypothesis dev)	BR2 – Market size and strategy reviewed
TR1 - scientific research (defined)	SR1 – Demand – needs analysis	BR1 –Commercial idea (defined)

Results

In undertaking this qualitative research over the last 3 months with LL infrastructure partners Janette has been able to surface and experience first-hand the range of tools/assets, methods and support services used to deliver projects to key stakeholders.

She has also examined how this is tracked and with feedback from participants she has managed to surface useful insight on how better to evolve the DHI readiness level framework with conversations on whether this may be of interest to other LL infrastructure – generally within Health and Care Innovation programmes, as part of their toolkit. Readiness framework considerations for the future are illustrated in the following MIRO board <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVNNAG0aM=> Some key points of feedback are presented in Figure 27.

Figure 27. Feedback per readiness level - business readiness

In addition, due to the feedback received this has widened Janette’s thinking and consideration of the readiness level framework level titles and has helped challenge her to review and consider existing tools and frameworks mentioned that have been useful to other Living Lab infrastructures. In addition, it also allowed her to understand better the support services that have been offered to the partners of each Living Lab. The Readiness framework is adjusted based on feedback of the different European and Canadian Living Lab practitioners.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

In this research project the focus was on knowledge sharing and facilitating access to relevant stakeholders rather than making use of a specific research infrastructure. The readiness framework developed by DHI will be adjusted based on the results of this TA project. This research activity will inform the development of the Living Lab project in relation to commercialisation and business readiness and how support mechanisms can work better in tandem with technical and service readiness. This work will feed into the DHI which achieved funding of £5million from UK Government to enhance economic development through Living Lab methodology. There will be a written report based on the initial research activity. In turn, this report will assist the design and creation of an exemplar readiness tool aimed at accelerating from R&D into Business as usual and commercialisation. This will be disseminated internationally with a joint article or/and peer reviewed publication.

TA Evaluation

Janette expressed her gratitude for bringing her in contact with relevant LL practitioners of the VITALISE consortium that have experience in or are interested in investigating different kinds of readiness levels (technology, business, services). They indicated that the outcome of the TA was somewhat higher than expected. She especially appreciated the openness and the ability to ask questions on the approaches. When asked for improvements, Janette mentions that in depth Case studies and personas of the kind of users/services would be useful. Key strengths of LiCalab are sharing and knowledge exchange, and the clear demonstration of technology and innovation examples. Weaknesses are commercialisation and new innovations that have been adopted could perhaps be demonstrated by case studies. Janette made use of the following VITALISE tools several times: Panel management tool, VITALISE website and Wiki page. User friendliness of these tools

was evaluated as high, whereas usefulness was rated very high. The tools allowed her to understand how the support services were used with partners and end users. To summarise, Janette states that all LL staff were very friendly and open. It was a great experience and gave her in-depth understanding.

A total of 59 dedicated hours was invested in the current project. Staff profiles comprised an operations manager, a business manager, a panel manager and a researcher-psychologist. LiCalab staff spent most time on participation in the readiness levels workshop and individual interviews during Janette's TA visit.

2.2.5. Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab

A total of three projects involving 7 external researchers made use of the VITALISE research infrastructure and target pool of older people (ID27, ID30, ID85). Within research ID 30 and ID85 the research leader remained the same, but there were some changes in the joining participants, which we indicated in our changing log. The research ID27 was carried out in two steps, in the meantime the intervention activities in the framework of JRA3 were conducted, so the professor visited the lab twice. The Polish project (ID85) was selected to present their research at the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February, 2024.

Table 8. Current status of each TA project in Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab

Project	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	Nº of researchers	Visit performed
ID27	May- Sept 2024	<i>Living lab project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Expert opinion, and advisory services; Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping.</i>	6	23	1	1 st period: 20.06.2023 - 04.07.2023 2 nd period: 02.09.2023 - 09.09.2023
ID30	August- September 2024	<i>Living lab project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Stakeholder analysis and mapping; Stakeholder analysis and mapping.</i>	10,25	39	3	08.09.2023 - 20.09.2023
ID85	October- December 2024 January 2025	<i>Living lab project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Expert opinion, and advisory services.</i>	5,5	42	3	19.11.2023 - 02.12.2023

“Relationship between physical fitness, physical activity and healthy lifestyle in Seniors” Project – ID27

Leading researcher: José Carlos Fernández-García - University of Malaga, Spain.

Project summary

The primary goal of this project was to examine varying levels and manifestations of physical fitness, with a particular emphasis on health and well-being, and to correlate these with lifestyle habits. To achieve this, we engaged 23 elderly individuals from the NWLL user panel in assessments that took place on the 27th and 29th of June 2023. During these sessions, we gathered health-related data using a precise smart scale (a TANITA Bioimpedanciometer with clinical validity). This allowed us to measure aerobic capacity, flexibility, strength-endurance, dexterity, daily energy intake, as well as nutritional and health-related behaviours. The data regarding healthy lifestyle habits was collected using the internationally validated 'HEALTHY LIFESTYLE QUESTIONNAIRE'.

In sum, body composition was assessed through bioimpedance; physical activity through the IPAQ-7 questionnaire; physical fitness through specific tests described below; and healthy lifestyle habits through the Healthy Lifestyles Questionnaire.

This measurement initiated an 8-week training program for participants, led by a highly qualified instructor. Following the 8-week period, Prof. Fernández-García conducted another set of measurements. Thus, this research forms part of a longitudinal, correlational study aimed at identifying the relationship (or degree of association) between various concepts, categories, or variables within a specific context—namely, the connection between physical activity behaviours and healthy lifestyle habits among adults aged 55 to 80 years.

NWLL Research Infrastructure provided 23 smart watches for the research participants, allowing us and the external researcher to collect and generate big data throughout the 10-12 weeks of the whole research.

All the participants of the research (women aged 55 to 80 years) are very keen on being part of this study, not only because they got a clearer picture about their physical fitness, but also because they are also provided with the means to develop and train their physical wellbeing.

The following NWLL professionals were involved in the support of this TA project: one technical research manager, one facilitator, sport experts and ethics manager, and a data analyst. In total 168 dedicated hours were spent by the professionals. This corresponds to 21 days (about 2 and a half weeks) during which the LL staff engaged with the project. Most of the activities and tasks were connected to guaranteeing the technical/digital conditions of the measurements, and a safe and healthy personal/physical participation of the 40 stakeholders in the research during the first period of the project.

Figure 28. Snapshots of the 8-week training program

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The conclusions drawn from this research indicate a significant positive impact of an eight-week Nordic walking intervention on various aspects of physical fitness among elderly women. The improvements observed in strength, turning movement, and aerobic capacity highlight the effectiveness of this exercise modality in enhancing overall physical condition in this demographic. Further analysis is warranted to delve into potential changes in energy consumption and health perception, as well as to explore possible relationships between these variables. Looking ahead, the dissemination of these findings through publication in scientific journals and presentation at international congresses will contribute to advancing knowledge on the benefits of physical activity for older adults, fostering better health outcomes and enhancing quality of life in this population. Moreover, the open access provision of collected data will facilitate further research and collaboration in the field of geriatric exercise science, potentially leading to the development of more tailored and effective interventions for promoting healthy aging.

TA evaluation

Dr. José Carlos Fernández-García evaluated his Transnational Access very highly due to the extensive support and resources provided by the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab during his research stay. Firstly, he appreciated the access to facilities and technologies necessary for conducting his research, including the SmartWatch usage for data collection and the provision of expert monitoring during the Nordic walking intervention. Additionally, the collaboration with the staff at Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab facilitated a two-way transfer of knowledge. Dr. Fernández-García shared his expertise in physical activity and health research, contributing valuable insights and methodologies to the lab's existing knowledge base. In return, he gained insights into local practices, cultural considerations, and potential nuances in elderly care and exercise interventions specific to the Hungarian context. This mutually beneficial exchange of knowledge not only enhanced the quality and depth of Dr. Fernández-García's research but also enriched the expertise and capabilities of the staff at Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab, leading to a highly positive evaluation of his research stay by both parties.

The following NWLL professionals were involved in the support of this TA project: one technical research manager, one facilitator, one sport expert and ethics manager, and a data analyst. In total 168 dedicated hours were spent by the professionals in the first period of the TA project. The 2nd period between 2-9 of September involved 65 hours spent with project mainly sport expert, technical manager and data analyst.

This corresponds to 21 days during which the LL staff engaged with the project. Most of the activities and tasks were connected to guaranteeing the technical/digital conditions of the measurements, and a safe and healthy personal/physical participation of the 40 stakeholders in the research.

"VR for Seniors Well-being" project - ID30

Contributing researchers: Dr. Efsthathos Christodoulides (lead applicant), Dr. Konstantina Intziegianni - UCLAN, CYPRUS; Dr. Marc Sarens – VUB, Belgium.

Project summary

The research project titled "VR for Seniors Well-being" aimed to promote active and healthy lifestyles among senior citizens through the utilization of virtual reality (VR) technologies. Following a pre-post quasi-experimental approach, the project involved three main phases: recruitment and setup, intervention sessions, and data collection. Consent forms were obtained, and pre-intervention data, including Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) questionnaires and electromyography measurements, were collected. During the intervention sessions, participants engaged with VR games while their muscle activity was recorded using surface electromyography. Post-intervention data, both qualitative (focus group interviews) and quantitative (modified Technology Acceptance Questionnaires), were collected to assess the impact of the intervention.

The participants of the research project were senior citizens aged 55 and above, recruited through various channels including social media, posters, and snowball sampling. They were individuals with varying levels of familiarity and experience with digital technologies and VR. Throughout the project, the participants were actively engaged in VR intervention sessions aimed at promoting active and healthy lifestyles. Their involvement included completing pre-intervention assessments, participating in VR activities such as gaming experiences, and providing post-intervention feedback through focus group interviews and questionnaires. The inclusion of senior citizens from diverse backgrounds and levels of technological proficiency ensured the project's relevance and applicability to a broad range of individuals within the target demographic.

Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab played a crucial role in the success of the project by providing essential support in organizing and hosting the intervention sessions. The lab facilitated the setup of technical requirements, including VR equipment, and provided a conducive environment for the participants to engage with the technology comfortably. Additionally, the lab's expertise and

infrastructure in health and well-being research contributed to the smooth execution of the intervention and data collection phases. Overall, the collaboration with the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab enhanced the project's reach and effectiveness in promoting active and healthy aging among senior citizens through innovative VR interventions.

Figure 29. VR intervention sessions aimed at promoting active and healthy lifestyles

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The research project "VR for Seniors Well-being" successfully implemented a VR intervention aimed at promoting active and healthy lifestyles among senior citizens. Through pre-post assessments and intervention sessions, the project evaluated the impact of VR technology on participants' technology acceptance and physical fitness. While data analysis is pending, preliminary findings suggest promising outcomes in terms of participants' engagement with VR technology and potential improvements in physical fitness indicators.

Looking ahead, the project anticipates several key implications and future directions. Firstly, the findings are expected to contribute to the growing body of research on the effectiveness of VR interventions in promoting healthy aging. The project's focus on senior citizens addresses an important societal concern, highlighting the potential of VR technology as a tool for improving the well-being of older adults.

The project underscores the importance of accessibility and inclusivity in the design and implementation of VR interventions for senior citizens. Future research could explore ways to tailor VR experiences to accommodate the diverse needs and preferences of older adults, ensuring equitable access to technology-driven health interventions.

The collaboration with the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab has demonstrated the value of interdisciplinary partnerships in advancing research and innovation in the field of health and well-being. Continued collaboration between academic researchers, industry partners, and community organizations can facilitate the development and dissemination of evidence-based interventions to promote healthy aging and enhance quality of life for older adults.

In conclusion, the "VR for Seniors Well-being" project holds promise for addressing the health and well-being needs of senior citizens through innovative VR interventions. By leveraging technology and interdisciplinary collaboration, the project aims to pave the way for future advancements in promoting active and healthy aging in older adult populations.

TA Evaluation

The researchers highly evaluated their TNA experience due to the invaluable opportunities it provided for collaboration and knowledge exchange. Accessing the resources and expertise available at the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab significantly enhanced the quality and breadth of their research project. They appreciated the support received from the lab staff in setting up intervention sessions, accessing necessary equipment like VR technology and electromyography sensors, and ensuring optimal conditions for data collection. Moreover, the collaboration facilitated a two-way transfer of knowledge. While the researchers shared their expertise in VR technology and health interventions, they also gained insights and knowledge from the lab staff's experience in health and well-being research. This mutual exchange enriched the research experience and contributed to the project's success.

Conversely, the staff at Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab evaluated the researchers' stay very positively because of the significant contributions they brought to the lab's research activities. The researchers' expertise in VR technology and health interventions complemented the lab's focus on health and well-being research, bolstering its capacity to conduct innovative studies in this domain. Additionally, the researchers actively engaged with the lab staff, sharing their knowledge and experience while also being receptive to learning from the lab's expertise. This collaborative approach fostered a productive and enriching research environment, enabling the exchange of ideas, methodologies, and best practices. Consequently, the researchers' presence positively impacted the lab's objectives, furthering its mission of advancing health and well-being through research and innovation.

The following NWLL professionals were involved in the support of this TA project: one technical research manager, one sport expert and ethics manager, and a data analyst, and facilitator. In total 86 dedicated hours were spent by the professionals.

"Mix of music and physiotherapy training in cognition improvement and stress reduction" ***Project - ID 85***

Contributing researchers: Anna Lipert (lead applicant), Bartłomiej Tarkowski, PhD, Joanna Kapusta, PhD - University of Lodz

Project summary

The project aimed to assess the impact of various relaxation techniques and training programs on the cognitive function and stress symptoms of elderly individuals, with the support of the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab. Led by a team of researchers, including professionals in psychology, music therapy, and public health, the study recruited over 20 women aged 55 and above without severe health conditions.

Participants were engaged in a two-week intervention consisting of five different relaxation methods, such as yoga, music therapy, and breathing techniques, supervised by certified specialists. Pre- and post-data were collected, encompassing anthropometric and socio-demographic information, cognitive function tests, mental health assessments, lifestyle habits, and environmental supports for physical activity.

The Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab provided essential services and facilities for the study, including capacity building, equipment rental, temporary research funding, project planning, and management. It served as a central hub for participant recruitment, data collection, and intervention implementation, ensuring the successful execution of the research activities.

Short-term results included the acceptance of the proposal for Transnational Access, full funding and logistics support for the study's execution in Hungary, and comprehensive data collection. Long-term outcomes aimed at analysing the collected data for statistical insights, preparing scientific publications, and presenting findings at academic conferences.

Dissemination efforts involved sharing project updates on social media during the study and planning for publication in scientific journals and conference presentations post-study. While the collected data were not made openly accessible due to the need to preserve the originality of the research, detailed information about the study, methodology, and results could be provided upon request.

Overall, the collaboration between researchers and the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab facilitated a comprehensive investigation into the effects of relaxation techniques on the mental health of elderly individuals, with the potential to inform future interventions and support healthier aging in communities.

Figure 30. Participants trying relaxation methods

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The main conclusions drawn from this research project highlight several key findings regarding the effectiveness of relaxation techniques on the mental health of elderly individuals.

The study demonstrated that participation in various relaxation techniques led to a reduction in stress symptoms among elderly participants. This suggests that interventions focusing on relaxation can be beneficial for managing stress in this demographic. Another significant finding was the improvement in cognitive function observed among participants. Engaging in relaxation activities such as yoga, music therapy, and breathing techniques appeared to enhance cognitive skills, indicating the potential cognitive benefits of these interventions.

The research provided insights into the role of relaxation techniques in supporting healthy lifestyle behaviours among the elderly. By promoting relaxation and stress reduction, these interventions may indirectly encourage individuals to adopt healthier habits, such as regular physical activity and improved dietary choices. The involvement of the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab highlighted the significance of supportive environments in facilitating research and interventions targeting elderly populations. Access to resources, facilities, and logistical support contributed to the successful execution of the study.

Building upon the findings of this project, future research could explore additional variables and relaxation techniques to deepen understanding and optimize interventions for elderly individuals. Expansion to larger and more diverse populations could provide broader insights into the effectiveness of relaxation strategies. The study suggests the potential for tailored relaxation interventions based on individual preferences and needs. Future research could focus on developing personalized programs that cater to specific cognitive and stress-related concerns among elderly populations.

Leveraging technology, such as wearable devices and virtual platforms, could enhance the accessibility and delivery of relaxation interventions for elderly individuals. Incorporating digital tools into future studies may improve engagement and outcomes among participants. Collaborating with community organizations and healthcare providers can facilitate the dissemination of research findings and promote the adoption of relaxation techniques among elderly individuals. Educational initiatives aimed at raising awareness about the benefits of relaxation for mental health could empower seniors to prioritize self-care practices.

Overall, this research project provides valuable insights into the potential of relaxation techniques to improve the mental health and well-being of elderly populations. By addressing stress and enhancing cognitive function, these interventions offer promising avenues for promoting healthy aging and enhancing quality of life in older adults.

TA Evaluation

The researchers evaluated their TA experience highly due to several key factors. Firstly, they highlighted the seamless support provided by the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab in facilitating their research project. This included assistance with participant recruitment, provision of necessary equipment and facilities, logistical support, and access to a conducive environment for conducting the study. The Living Lab's provision of various services, such as capacity building, equipment rental, and project planning, contributed significantly to the smooth execution of the research activities.

Furthermore, the researchers valued the opportunity for knowledge exchange and collaboration facilitated by the Living Lab. The staff at the Living Lab offered expertise, guidance, and support throughout the research process, enhancing the quality and effectiveness of the study. This two-way transfer of knowledge between the researchers and the Living Lab staff fostered a mutually beneficial relationship, enriching both parties' understanding and capabilities in their respective domains.

In turn, the staff at the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab evaluated the researchers' research stay positively. They appreciated the researchers' professionalism, dedication, and collaborative approach throughout the project. The researchers' commitment to conducting high-quality research, coupled with their receptiveness to input and collaboration, contributed to a productive and rewarding research experience for both parties. Overall, the researchers' high evaluation of their TA experience and the positive assessment by the staff at the Living Lab can be attributed to effective collaboration, knowledge exchange, and mutual support. This highlights the importance of partnerships between research institutions and Living Labs in advancing scientific knowledge and promoting innovation in healthcare and well-being.

The following NWLL professionals were involved in the support of this TA project: one technical research manager, one facilitator, and a data analyst and ethic manager. In total 120 dedicated hours were spent by the professionals.

2.2.6. Laurea Activity Living Lab

A total of three projects involving 8 external researchers utilized the Laurea Activity Living Lab infrastructure and services (IDs 40, 45, and 71). All visits were completed in autumn 2023, following a lengthy planning period. For example, research ethics approval was obtained for all projects before the visiting TA researchers arrived. The target groups for the first TA visitors (IDs 40 & 45) were individuals aged 60 and above, while the third TA project (ID 71) focused on participants aged 10-14. Additionally, for the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab symposium in Brussels in February 2024, an abstract from TA visitors (ID 71) was submitted and presented.

Table 9. Current status of each ta project in Laurea Activity Living Lab

Project	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	Nº of researchers	Visit performed
ID40	Jan–Nov 2023	<i>Expert opinion, and advisory services; Legal, regulation and safety standard support;</i>	14	6	3	16.11.2023 17.11.2023

		<i>Living lab project planning and management; Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping); Panel management; Co-creation session.</i>				
ID45	Feb-Nov 2023	<i>Expert opinion, and advisory services; LL project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Panel management; Concept and proof-of-concept test/concepts feasibility study; Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation.</i>	12	5	1	21.08.2023 - 25.08.2023
ID71	Mar-Nov 2023	<i>Expert opinion, and advisory services; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Living lab project planning and management; Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping); Real-life testing and experimentation</i>	20	16	4	10.10.2023- 13.10.2023

“Recreational football with participants 60+ years of age” project – ID60

Participant Researchers: Mélanie Boithias (lead applicant), Alain Belli - University of St. Etienne, France; Emma Guillet - University of Lyon, France.

Project summary

The project began with planning and agreeing on details. Approval from the Ethical Board was obtained before any activities commenced. Recruitment of participants started in the spring and early summer of 2023. The objective of the project was to engage in recreational football with participants aged 60 years and older. The activity lasted for 12 weeks, with organized training sessions held twice a week for approximately an hour each, totaling 24 training sessions. Prior to the training, physical fitness measures were taken, and after the training period concluded, additional physical fitness measurements and some selected questionnaires were conducted. Throughout the training sessions, participants were asked to rate their perceived exertion, and the intensity of the training was recorded during select sessions.

Visiting researchers are conducting similar activities in their Living Lab, with one researcher focusing on her PhD studies in this area. Laurea Activity Living Lab organized two workshops on consecutive days for the visiting researcher. The purpose of these workshops was to collect data from the participants' point of view regarding their participation in the activities. The goal was to enhance future organized recreational football activities based on this feedback. The training sessions were coached by the Activity lab personnel and visiting TA researchers also participated in one of the training sessions.

Figure 31. Visiting researcher with selected project participants

Conclusions and Future Outlook

23 participants, consisting of 12 males and 11 females, were recruited for the recreational football activities. Additionally, 11 participants took part in the workshop activities. The training sessions were successfully completed. There were five (5) dropouts from the activities, but none of them were due to injuries caused by the activities.

Participants expressed great enthusiasm for the opportunity to participate in coached and organized training sessions. They were delighted to join the workshop activities and share their thoughts about the activity and their reasons for participating. Additionally, a local club was connected with the project, and they expressed their intention to continue with this type of activity.

During the project large amount of diverse data was collected. Workshop data was initially collected in Finnish and later translated into English for use by the visiting Teaching Assistants (TAs). Common publications are planned for the future. The project provided valuable insights into the participants' reasons for participation. Additionally, two Living Labs were able to unite their interests and share common knowledge between them. In the future, if feasible, Living Labs will collaborate on similar activities.

TA Evaluation

The entire process was quite demanding. The initial preparations spanned approximately six months, followed by another six months of ongoing activities. Future organization of such activities is feasible, but would require additional funding.

The project commenced with planning the activities and specifically the measures to be taken, in collaboration with visiting TA researchers. Subsequently, the Laurea Activity Living Lab staff tackled practical issues. The first task involved coordinating with the local ethical board to secure approval for the ethical evaluation. The Laurea staff also resolved field rental issues with a local football club and began recruiting participants through their networks and connections.

The recreational football program lasted for 12 weeks, with training sessions held twice weekly for approximately an hour each. The Laurea staff managed the coaching and also conducted physical measurements before and after each session. All project results, primarily in Finnish, were coded by the Laurea staff, who also provided individual feedback to participants. Most of the co-creation during the workshops occurred in Finnish; hence, the results were recorded and translated into English for the TA researchers by the Laurea staff.

Prior to the TA visit, the Laurea staff dedicated 229 hours to the project, given its intensive nature with weekly activities. During the TA visit, an additional 22 hours were spent, and 178 hours were subsequently required to finalize all tasks.

The project unfolded as anticipated. The TA researchers enhanced their knowledge and understanding of the capabilities and possibilities offered by the Laurea Activity Lab. Both parties addressed the agreed-upon issues effectively. The TA researchers were satisfied with the data collected, which will be utilized in their current research settings. They were also pleased with the overall project organization and the services provided by the Laurea Activity Living Lab. From the Laurea perspective, new networks were formed and ideas for future activities of this nature were encouraged.

"Smartwatch self-reporting" project – ID45

Researcher: Alireza Khanshan - Eindhoven University of Technology, NL.

Project summary

The common interest of this project was physical activity and its quantification among senior citizens. The project idea originated from the TA researcher, who proposed recording the daily physical activity of senior participants using two different devices. Additionally, the TA researcher's smartwatch would prompt participants to indicate the type of activity they were engaged in and their feelings towards the activity.

The project began with designing and agreeing on the project protocol, as well as collecting materials to apply for Ethical approval from the local board. Subsequently, work continued with planning the content of the "Experience app," which was integrated into the Samsung smartwatches. After agreeing on the contents, translations from English to Finnish were completed for the app and for the user guides provided. Finally, some additional questionnaires were agreed upon for use in the project.

Figure 32. A snapshot from the smartwatch user guide provided to the participants

After preparations the TA researched mailed 20 smartwatches to Laurea Activity Living Lab to test and to deliver to participants. Meanwhile Laurea was collecting participants from persons attending to Espoo city Exercise department guided exercise groups. Laurea has a long history of cooperation with municipality, so this was the easiest way to find participants. Prior delivering the smartwatches to the participants the protocol was tested with close friends or family.

During the TA researcher's visit, a workshop was arranged with the purpose of enabling the researcher to hear and learn from selected users about their experiences with using the smartwatch and application in a real-life setting. During the TA researcher visit data collection also continued.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Altogether, data from 10 participants were collected, which was fewer than planned. However, the tight timetable and time-consuming nature of data collection contributed to this outcome. Although the watches worked quite well, some participants encountered difficulties simply with charging the battery or using the application, or both. Instead of solely collecting data, the project turned out to be more focused on testing the usability and experiences of the smartwatch users. This approach was important, especially considering that the technology was novel and new for many participants.

The project approved that there are many steps when testing new technology with new ideas in a real-life setting. This project brought new insights and thoughts about future data collection and its possibilities in the field of physical activity domain. From the Laurea Activity Living Lab point of view this project was quite time consuming with multiple phases, but interesting.

The TA researcher and Laurea did not agree to further collaboration. However, now that the services and possibilities of Laurea Living Lab are familiar to the researcher and his community, there are no reasons why future cooperation could not be possible if the conditions are appropriate. For Laurea LL this project provided of valuable information and ideas of how to develop these ideas, and what are the possible barriers.

TA Evaluation

The TA project at Laurea Activity Living Lab was a comprehensive and time-intensive endeavor. Initially, the project required ethical approval from a local board before proceeding, concluding with the return of the smartwatches to the TA researcher. From Laurea's perspective, the project was somewhat constrained by time, which limited the depth of the results. Since the smartwatch app was new and had not been extensively tested in a real environment, the project provided more experience in using this type of technology in daily living settings rather than yielding significant data.

The visiting TA researcher had specific expectations for his visit, leading to numerous discussions with Laurea staff to align on the project's activities. Laurea handled the ethical approvals, participant recruitment, and necessary translations for project materials.

After receiving smart watches via mail Laurea staff pre-tested the watches with selected number of participants. During the TA researcher visit Laurea staff organized co-creational workshop with some selected participants to better understand the practical use of the technology. Post-visit, Laurea continued data collection with additional participants and eventually returned the devices to the researcher, along with some translated data for further analysis.

In terms of effort, pre-visit activities demanded 82 hours from Laurea, the visit itself accounted for 30 hours, and post-visit activities took an additional 41 hours.

It is understandable that TA researchers have many hopes and wishes for Living Lab projects and visits. However, when working in real life with real participants and new technological solutions, it is important to carefully consider what can be achieved within a limited timeframe. The expectations and the actual possibilities should perhaps be more realistically aligned in the future.

Nevertheless, the TA project was conducted with dedication and yielded sufficient results. Laurea Living Lab learned new ideas on how to incorporate such techniques in real-life settings in the future. Laurea has the impression that the visiting TA researcher also gained new understanding and data from their new solution and technology. Although no further agreements about new projects were made, there are no reasons why this would not happen in a suitable new opportunity.

"Functional movement (FMS) testing with young football players" project – ID71

Participant Researchers: Michael Duncan (lead applicant), Matteo Crotti, Lucas Guimaraes, Ricardo Martins - Coventry University, UK; Caoimhe Tiernan - Atlantic Technological University, IR.

Project summary

The project aimed to collect data from young grassroots-level football players on their functional movement skills (FMS), with the assumption that good FMS can help prevent injuries related to football. The visiting TA researcher group brought along a measurement protocol that they had used in the UK, providing an opportunity to collect data from a Finnish cohort. Some of the measurement systems were provided by Laurea Living Lab, while others were brought by the visiting researchers.

As usual, the project began with planning the design and collecting materials to apply for Ethical approval from the local board. Following this, a connection was established with a local football club to recruit participants and agree on data collection times. The measurement events took place during the practice hours of the included teams in the local club facilities, with the TA visitors and Laurea Living Lab personnel executing the measurements while team coaches organized the young football players at the measurement sites.

Figure 33. TA researcher visitors and Laurea Activity LL contact in a group picture.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Altogether 82 young (born 2009-2013) grassroots-level football players were measured. 10 of the players were girls. The event was organized so that there were several measurement sites on the pitch and the participants were allocated into different sites in a small group. The groups circled from one site to another from signal. The whole event went very well, and no problems occurred with the measurement devices nor with young participants.

Collected data can be matched with the existing data from the UK. There has not been yet discussion of how to proceed data analysis or present results. The idea is to publish data in some scientific journal, perhaps on a suitable congress.

This project proved that Laurea Activity Living Lab is very feasible and can tackle many kinds of projects. It is not just about the site or devices used on a project, but also a wide network to connect local stakeholders to collect participants for the projects and to access different infrastructures. There is a good chance that cooperation with this TA researcher group and Laurea will continue.

TA Evaluation

The project was the most streamlined of the three TAs, likely due to the limited timeframe of the TA researchers' visit to the Laurea Activity Living Lab. Additionally, the high level of experience and knowledge concerning the applied protocol contributed to a smooth data collection and activity period. Language, particularly English, posed no barrier for the children during the activity, which was a pleasantly unexpected outcome that facilitated the execution of the measurements.

The project started with agreeing the measurements and general arrangements. The Laurea staff secured ethical approval, a particularly rigorous process since the participants were children. All participant recruitment was coordinated with local football clubs, and measurements were scheduled during team training hours. All measurements were conducted indoors at the club's dome, as the timing coincided with the approach of winter.

Most of the measuring equipment required for the project was provided by the Laurea Activity Living Lab, although some devices were brought by the visiting TA researchers. As the TA researcher were experienced and measurement events happened only in two days, Laurea staff effort was the least compared to the other two initiatives. Laurea staff was participating to the measurement events so. The participants were divided into small groups during the measurement sessions. While visiting TA researchers were in charge for most of the measurements, Laurea staff also contributed to the single measurement sites.

Preparation required approximately 58 hours of Laurea staff's time, with 32 hours spent on visiting and 27 hours on post-visit arrangements.

The data collected during the TA visit was practical and will be useful for future publications. The TA researchers expressed satisfaction with their visit. Typically, the Laurea Activity Living Lab does not integrate this type of measurement system into its daily operations, so observing the system function smoothly without issues was noteworthy.

The local clubs and coaches likely gained new insights from the setting. As there were lots of data collected and needed to be processed a little minus was the long timeframe that collected data was provided to Laurea to give feedback to the participants.

While no specific new collaborative projects have been agreed, discussions started on the possibilities for new projects. Additionally, a representative researcher from this TA project shared the results at the VITALISE Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels.

2.2.7. AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

A total of three projects involving seven unique external researchers made use of the VITALISE research infrastructure AIT Technology Experience Laboratory (ID24, ID83 and ID90). While projects ID24 and ID83 were fully conducted in-person based on the hosting the external researchers at the AIT infrastructure in Vienna, project ID90 also involved remote access to the infrastructure. Projects ID90 was selected to present their research at the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February 2024.

Table 10. Current status of each TA project in AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

Project	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	Nº of researchers	Visit performed
ID24	Feb.-May 2023	Living lab project planning and management, Expert opinion, and advisory services	0	30	1	04.03.2023 - 02.04.2023
ID83	Aug. 2023-Feb. 2024	Living lab project planning and management, Expert opinion, and advisory services, Usability testing	55	85	5	13.11.2023 - 10.12.2023
ID90	Aug. 2023-Mar. 2024	Living lab project planning and management, Expert opinion, and advisory services, Legal, regulation and safety standard support, Small-	0	25	1	23.09.2023 - 03.10.2023 and

		scale real-life testing and experimentation				10.03.2023 - 23.03.2024
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“Evaluation of use of technology by informal caregivers” Project – ID24

Researcher: Francesca Gris (lead applicant) – Istituto Nazionale di Ricovero e Cura Anziani (IRCCS - INRCA), Italy.

Project Summary

The increase aging of the population has revealed a lot of challenges, in terms of wellbeing, health and active participation of the older people. At the same time, the spread of diagnosis of dementia requires to keep in mind also who takes care of this older people, in particular the informal caregivers (the people who spends most of the time with frail elderly and take care of them, without taking part in a formal network of organized care (Van Durme et al., 2012). Technology could be a possible support to face these challenges and, in fact, a lot of products, tools and services were developed in this field.

Nevertheless, there is a lack of instrument that can measure the real feasibility and acceptance of technology from the user group perspective. One of these measuring instruments has been proposed by the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) of Vienna. The EvAALutaion project (Himmelsbach et al., 20192) had the objective to developing and standardizing some instruments to assess the use of technology in the AAL project context. These instruments measure three different domains (health, care and support, being active and human potential) through questionnaires with a 5-point Likert scale. They are currently designed to be used by older users without specific care responsibility.

Starting from the results of the EvAALuation project the goal of this project was to develop a new version of the instrument that is specifically targeted to be used by informal caregivers of people with dementia and assisted people, to assess their evaluation of the use of digital tools deployed in care settings.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Starting from the results of the previous project EvAALuation, which has developed and standardized the measuring instruments (questionnaires) for the assessment of AAL technologies from older people perspective, the project developed a new version of the instrument. This new version will be used by informal caregivers of people with dementia and assisted people, to assess their evaluation of the use of the technology in care settings.

The first activity consisted in analysing the existing instrument (structure, constructs and single items), already available in English and German. Every single item was analysed to select which ones fit to caregivers and older people’s perspective.

The requested expert and advisory services were used in everyday collaboration with the AIT team. Short meetings and ad-hoc discussions fostered the collaboration with the local research team. The capacity building and networking will allow to share the result with other partner organizations.

As a basis for the follow-up collaboration with the AIT on personal support solutions for informal caregivers of persons with dementia, a new version of the evaluation tool kit was developed. This new version considers the perspective of caregivers and older people and in particular their need to fill in short and quick instruments that could be able to assess the impact of the intervention. A first version of this new instrument consists of two scales: a scale for caregivers, with 34 items; a scale for people with dementia, with 18 items. Items were selected from each of the three areas: health, care and being active, covering aspects like experience in using technology, digital inclusion, privacy, social interaction, need of support.

The existing EvAAUation research instruments are already available to the research community. Work on the adaptation of these instruments for measuring the impact of personal support systems for informal caregivers will continue beyond the end of the Transnational Access activity. As soon as they are validated with experts and the target group, these adapted instruments will be made openly accessible for the research community.

TA Evaluation

For supporting the execution of this TA, the LL manager as well as one facilitator were involved. In total, approximately 84 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of the project at the AIT Technology Experience Lab, both in person and remotely.

Overall, this Transnational Access activity was very positively evaluated by the visiting researcher. Services provided by the LL allowed the researcher to achieve the expected outcome.

The results of this project may be useful overall for all the institution that are involved in projects that use technology to support the informal caregivers of people with dementia. Together with the AIT research team, collaboration on personal support systems for informal caregivers will be continued also beyond the end of the Transnational Access activity. Adjusted instruments to assess the impact of such systems will be further developed and released to the research community, especially some partners of host institution (AIT) and home institution (INRCA).

"Robotics for Upper Limb Rehabilitation" project - ID83

Researcher: Lynne Baillie (lead applicant), Marta Romeo, Theodoras Georgiou, Emilyann Nault, Carl Bettosi - National Robotarium, Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, UK.

Project summary

Socially Assistive Robots (SARs) are an emerging technology in the exercise domain. Their anthropomorphic features create new opportunities to adopt coaching roles and help motivate self-managed exercises. It is important to consider not only how these robots can create positive health outcomes, but also how they can build trustworthy relationships over time. In human-human physical exercise scenarios, the coach will often rely on demonstrating exercises, both before and alongside the participants execution, to build momentum while providing feedback of the correct movement. For robots, mimicking human actions may have the additional advantage of contributing to an increase in trust.

It is also true, however, that the human's intended movement may not always be recognisable due to the difficulties in performing any significant motor movement. Therefore, traditional perception techniques such as computer vision may struggle to provide a real-time sync between the human's movement and the robot's response. Brain Computer Interfaces (BCI) provide direct insight into brain data which can inform the human's motor intentions in real-time. Early studies into the field of BCI have shown promising results yet have never been combined with a social robot to help guide and inform self-managed exercise, to the authors' knowledge.

To that end, the aim of this TA activity was to develop and validate a SAR-based system for upper-limb motor exercise, which understands user motor intention through BCI and mimics exercises to help motivate participants and assess other factors of the interaction such as usability and trust. The research team argued that the ability to mimic user movement in real-time is important as, people will typically go at their own pace and often mix up exercise routines, removing the ability for the robot to predict future actions.

Around 80% of persons after acute Stroke have an upper limb impairment, limiting the movement of the arm. This impairment, often persists over the long term (> 12 months), massively affects their activities of daily living. Improving function requires task-specific, repetitive exercise [8,9]. However, 60% of Stroke survivors may often suffer from forgetfulness and only 31% perform these exercises.

Lack of motivation and immediate obvious progress indicators also contribute to this low exercise partake.

Table 11. Frequency of responses per participant

Phase	Procedure
0: Pre-Experiment	Consent form/preliminary questionnaire to be filled out prior to the experiment via an online form Setup experimental space
1: Setup and Training	To explain the purpose and logistics of the experiment to the participant. Setup and training of BCI device.
2: Exercises with Mimicry	The participant will engage in three different exercises over the course of 10 minutes while the robot mimics the participant's movement. Evaluation Measures: Multi-Dimensional Measure of Trust (MDMT), The Robotic Social Attributes Scale (RoSAS), Emotion Wheel
3: Exercises without mimicry	The participant will engage in three different exercises over the course of 10 minutes while the robot provides feedback on the participant's movement. Evaluation Measures: Same as phase 2, and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) if not doing phase 4
4: Semi-Structured Interview	To gain feedback on the participant's experience across the two conditions.

The goal of this study was therefore to get a first insight in the feasibility of using BCI and SAR to guide physical exercises for persons with hemiparesis (in terms of trust, social and emotional perception of the robot and technology acceptance). Table 8 provides an overview on the details of the implemented study protocol.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The proposed approach was trialled at tech2people, a recently opened rehabilitation lab in Vienna. During three weeks in November and December 2023, six therapists and 16 patients could interact with the robot Nao, that was supposed to motivate and support the participants in performing their upper limb exercises. For some parts of the study, participants additionally received a brain-computer interface, a head-worn device with several sensors that can be used to perceive user's exercise intention. By the additional use of the BCI, the researchers assessed the robot's ability to mimic the intended movement even for patients with very limited range of movement due to their impairment.

The evaluation measures focused on aspects of trust as well as attributes that participants would assign to the robot. Thereby, the team gained valuable insights on adaptation possibilities both from therapists and people that experienced stroke or brain injuries.

Preliminary findings of the data analysis can be summarized as follows:

- The evaluated approach successfully managed to guide a short rehabilitation session semi-autonomously for all 16 participants.
- Quantitative results show mid-levels of warmth, high levels of perceived competence and low levels of discomfort across conditions.
- No strong correlation between perceived trust and robot mimicry when compared to standard exercise demonstrations.
- The Emotion Wheel, a tool to measure the felt emotion during interaction with the system, showed mainly positive active emotions (during non-BCI: predominantly amused-excited, during BCI: predominantly amused-excited-calm) Negative emotions were indicated only during the BCI variant (annoyed, frustrated, bored/tired).
- When asked about how well the robot could mimic the movements of the participants, the participants provided average ratings (Average score of 5 on a scale from 1 "very poor" to 10 "excellent").

- The participants found the use of the BCI device moderately comfortable (average score of 6 on a scale from 1 "very uncomfortable" to 10 "very comfortable") and moderately difficult (average score of 6 on a scale from 1 "very difficult" to 10 "very easy").
- 9 out of 12 (75%) state that mimicking movements by the robot is a good way to enhance motivation for exercise (compared to just demonstrating the exercise). A therapist said: "*That I control the robot. This is more motivating because my own activity is more in focus. I see an effect of my movement, I have control over it.*" Another therapist mentioned: "*Yes, you have to concentrate heavily on it, and it's a challenge to focus on it, which is motivating. Visual feedback is always good.*"
- 9 out of 12 (75%) would use the system as part of their own exercises. They mention that using the robot potentially offers more options and it is motivating to see the robot participating.
- Five participants emphasize the importance of varying the exercises more. One therapist said: "*If the exercises could be made more complex: everyday movements (bringing hand to mouth; drinking); ...also more variety; one could certainly consider [that] for the future.*"
- When asked what changes the participants would like to make, the therapists mentioned the following categories:
 - Exercises: more accurate execution, more precise movement, more complex and varied exercises
 - Feedback: during exercise completion (e.g., robot dance)
 - Robot: more-human-like voice, more empathetic, better representation of the human body
 - Gamification elements: e.g., "*competition (achieving a value to surpass next time)*"
 - EEG: more stable signal, more transparent how to control it

For the same question, the patients mentioned the following categories:

- Exercises: More variations, motivating music
- Feedback: e.g., "*Smiling when I've done an exercise well.*"
- Robot: More natural voice, more human-like behaviour
- In general, the participants trust the system. One patient said, when asked what to change to increase trust in the system: "*Nothing, because for me, it was already great in terms of trust. I trust a robot more than a human; they are more predictable.*" Another patient said: "*No changes are necessary. It would be beneficial for the therapy centre as well as for home use.*"
- The results of the Multi-Dimensional Measure of Trust (MDMT) questionnaire further show above-average trust in the system, especially in terms of competence. Only minor differences could be observed in perceived trust between both interventions.
- According to the Robotic Social Attributes Scale (RoSAS), the system is perceived as competent and comfortable. Only minor differences have been observed in perceived trust between both interventions.

Figure 34. Results of the Robotic Social Attributes Scale (RoSAS; blue = BCI, orange = non-BCI)

Figure 35. Participant performing the robot-guided training task

TA Evaluation

For supporting the execution of this TA, the LL manager as well as two facilitators were intensively involved. In total, approximately 354 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of the project at the AIT Technology Experience Lab, both in person and remotely.

Related to the need of involving an external therapy centre in Vienna, the implementation of this TA activity was rather resource intense. The experience and knowledge of the applied protocol was in high level, so the data collection, activity period, was very smooth.

The data collected during the TA visit was feasible and can be utilized in future publications. The TA researchers were satisfied with the visit. Also, a representative researcher of this TA project presented results in the VITALISE Health and wellbeing Living Lab symposium in Brussels.

Beyond the scope of the VITALISE project, a second evaluation pilot including people with hemiparesis is planned in Scotland in 2024.

"Protocol for the use of ESM in conjunction with educational interventions for caregivers of PwD" project - ID90

Researcher: Raluca Sfetcu (lead applicant) - Romanian Alzheimer Society, Romania.

Project summary

Informal caregivers of persons with dementia (PwD) frequently experience significant fluctuations in their caregiving burden, often referred to as "good and bad days." Traditional questionnaires that capture average experiences may overlook these fluctuations. To address this gap, the experience sampling method (ESM) offers a valuable approach by collecting data repeatedly in real-life contexts. ESM enables the exploration of day-to-day variations in burden among informal dementia caregivers and facilitates the identification of factors associated with these fluctuations.

As previous research has shown that caregivers with a higher education level, more sense of competence in caring for the PwD, and higher levels of mastery appeared to be less prone to experiencing negative affect when they encountered minor disturbances in daily life (Knippenberg et al., 2018), we want to develop and test a protocol for using ESM in conjunction with educational interventions in order to more dynamically assess the impact of these type of interventions (e.g. information provision, training programs, educational apps, etc.).

The aim of this project was therefore to develop and pilot in a small sample of caregivers of PwD a protocol for the use of ESM in conjunction with educational interventions to gain a comprehensive understanding of daily experiences, emotions, challenges, and coping strategies in their natural environment. By employing ESM, we aim to capture real-time data to investigate the dynamic aspects of caregiving and provide valuable insights into the caregivers' well-being and support needs.

The initial phase of the project consisted of developing an ESM protocol for use with caregivers of PwD in conjunction with educational interventions. A literature search was performed to:

- Determine the timing and frequency of ESM prompts, considering factors such as the optimal number of prompts per day and the interval between prompts (e.g., random or fixed intervals).
- Choose the appropriate electronic devices or platforms (e.g., smartphones, online survey platforms, etc.) to deliver prompts and collect data.
- Develop a set of questions or prompts that capture relevant variables of interest, such as caregiving tasks, emotions, stress levels, coping strategies, and other contextual factors.
- Determine the response format for each question, such as Likert scales, open-ended responses, or multiple-choice options.
- Specify the duration of the ESM data collection period, considering factors like caregiver burden and feasibility.

The final stage of the project involved 5-10 volunteer participants to pilot the developed ESM protocol. The inclusion criteria to participate in the study were:

- being an informal caregiver of a PwD
- being at least 18 years old
- being able to read and sign an informed consent
- being able to use technology

People who did not comply with the above criteria were not eligible to participate in the study.

The pilot consisted in testing the developed protocol for a limited amount of time. We assessed the extent to which caregivers adhered to the ESM protocol by examining response rates and completion rates of ESM prompts, as low response rates may indicate potential difficulties or limitations in the protocol.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Based on the literature review of previous initiatives of this type (Chen et al., 2022) as well as existing guidelines on implementing ESM (Kirtley et al., 2021; Stone & Shiffman, 1994; Trull & Ebner-Priemer, 2020) and systematic reviews published on this topic (Williams et al., 2021) we have decided on using the International Positive and Negative Affect Schedule Short-Form (I-PANAS-SF) for measuring the affective experiences of the caregivers of PwD. The I-PANAS-SF was developed by Thompson (2007) and consists of ten items (derived from the original 20 PANAS item pool (Watson et al., 1988)).

The five positive affective states are: active, determined, attentive, inspired, and alert. The five negative affective states are: afraid, nervous, upset, hostile, and ashamed.

Respondents are asked to rate these positive and negative adjectives according to the extent to which each describes the way they have felt during a specified time.

For distributing the items, we have decided on using the ExpiWell app, ExpiWell, a user friendly and secure app for intensive assessment in daily life (<https://app.expiwell.com>).

Following exploratory discussions with the partner caregiving organization the frequency of the survey was established at once a week, once a day – to not overwhelm the participants with additional tasks or concerns. Consequently, during the pilot, the I-PANAS -SF was sent once a week for an interval of 2 months. During the response day the time for the notifications was randomized within a pre-defined time window: 8AM-8:00PM. The surveys could be completed up to 60 minutes after the initial notification

If participants did not respond to a notification, a reminder was sent 30 minutes after the initial notification.

11 participants from Austria (selected via the AIT partner organization GGZ) took part in the pilot; each of them filled in the I-PANAS-SF survey for 2-7 times; altogether 51 observations were included in the analysis. The individual contributions are summarized in Table 1 below.

Table 12. Frequency of responses per participant

Participant no	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Participant 10	4	7.8	7.8
Participant 12	6	11.8	19.6
Participant 13	5	9.8	29.4
Participant 15	5	9.8	39.2
Participant 16	5	9.8	49.0
Participant 18	3	5.9	54.9
Participant 4	4	7.8	62.7
Participant 5	6	11.8	74.5
Participant 6	7	13.7	88.2
Participant 7	4	7.8	96.1
Participant 9	2	3.9	100.0
Total	51	100.0	

The average time it took participants to fill in the I-PANAS-SF via the ExpiWell app was 102 seconds (min=27, max=381; Sd=89); the duration for each of the 51 observations are included in Annex 1. Concerning the time of the day when the survey was sent, in 3/51 cases the start date was during 8-12 AM; in 26/51 the start date was during 12 – 4 PM and in 22/51 cases the start date of the survey was in the interval 4 – 8 PM. A distribution of the number of surveys filled in the above-mentioned intervals by each participant is included below.

Table 13. Numbers of surveys filled in per participant

	time_in_the_day			Total
	8-12 AM	12-4 PM	4-8 PM	
Participant 10	0	2	2	4
Participant 12	0	2	4	6
Participant 13	0	2	3	5
Participant 15	0	3	2	5
Participant 16	1	3	1	5
Participant 18	0	2	1	3
Participant 4	0	3	1	4
Participant 5	0	6	0	6
Participant 6	1	2	4	7
Participant 7	1	1	2	4

Participant 9	0	0	2	2
Total	3	26	22	51

The positive to negative affects ratio is imbalanced towards the positive, participants reporting three times more positive (m=17,01; min=3; max=24.5; scores could vary between 0 and 40) than negative affects (m=5,94; min=0; max=21,00; scores could vary between 0 and 40).

Table 14. Descriptive data for positive and negative affects reported

	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Deviation
PANAS_P	48	3.00	24.50	17.0104	4.86246
PANAS_N	48	.00	21.00	5.9479	5.17280
Valid N (listwise)	48				

Looking at the variation of the positive and negative affects in relation to the time of the day the survey was filled in, we observed a decrease of mean positive affects, respectively an increase of mean negative affect from the midday (12-4 PM) to the evening (4-8 PM) time interval.

Table 15. Variation of positive and negative affects based on the time of the day when the survey was filled in.

	time_in_da y	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
PANAS_ P	12-4 PM	26	18.2115	4.41627	.86610
	4-8 PM	19	16.1053	4.24454	.97376
PANAS_ N	12-4 PM	26	5.7500	4.07492	.79916
	4-8 PM	19	6.7632	6.59412	1.51280

ESM can be used to measure positive and negative affects of caregivers of people with dementia but the time intervals between data collection must be longer than other groups of participants. Nevertheless, methodological adaptations are also needed to make sure that data is still relevant and useful. Future research should explore alternative schedules to identify the optimal time intervals for which the ESM method can still be used. Beyond these limitations, exploring the positive and negative affectivity of the caregivers of people with dementia might uncover areas for more effective prevention and intervention.

TA Evaluation

For supporting the execution of this TA, the LL manager as well as two facilitators were intensively involved. In total, approximately 111 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of the project at the AIT Technology Experience Lab, both in person and remotely.

Overall, this Transnational Access activity was very positively evaluated by the visiting researcher. Services provided by the LL allowed the researcher to achieve the expected outcome.

The results of this project may be useful overall for all the institution that are involved in projects that use technology to support the informal caregivers of people with dementia. Together with the AIT research team, collaboration on personal support systems for informal caregivers will be continued also beyond the end of the Transnational Access activity. Adjusted instruments to assess the impact of such systems will be further developed and released to the research community, especially some partners of host institution (AIT) and home institution (Romanian Alzheimer Society).

3. Discussion

The following sections offers a reflective analysis including overall LL experience of the Living Labs in relation the TA projects performed in the WP10 Living Lab infrastructures, distilling lessons learnt from these engagements, then providing insights about the impacts and experience gained throughout the process.

3.1. Overall results

In the infographic below the Transnational Accesses performed within WP10 is presented. The infographic includes aggregated information from the three (3) VITALISE Open calls.

Figure 36: VITALISE TA WP10

The number of participants reached is 63 applicants, from which 1 TA (ID12) is on hold due to cost/reimbursement process and 2 members of the 2 research teams (ID70 and ID86) did not participated due to personal reasons. From the 63 applicants, 25 were males and 38 females, achieving a great proportion of gender inclusivity. Furthermore, the research domains of the applicants are presented, with almost 78% coming from academia and 11% coming from government research background, while 7,5% were entrepreneurs and almost 4% coming from industry. The working countries of the applicants are also presented. The TAs performed within WP10 reached applicants from 15 different working countries in Europe and Latin America. In particular, we reached applicants from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Norway, Italy, Spain, Cyprus, Romania, France, the Netherlands, Greece, Ireland, Israel, the UK, Portugal, Albania and Poland.

3.2. AUTH living environment simulation

Throughout the implementation of the various TA projects at AUTH Living Environment Simulation, it became evident that numerous LL services played a crucial role in supporting different stages of the research process. Initially, in the early phases of the TA projects, the most frequently utilized services were expert opinion and advisory services, offering essential guidance and insights. This was complemented by capacity building aimed at enhancing researchers' skills and knowledge pertinent to their specific research topics and interests. For some of the performed TA studies, there was also the need of utilizing the service of equipment and facility rental, to be feasible for the specific experiments to run. As the projects progressed to the planning and management phase, services like intake and matching, legal and safety standard support, and panel management were notably employed. In the continuous testing and validation process, services such as co-creation, stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping, and small-scale real-life testing and experimentation remained vital. Significantly, expert opinion and advisory services emerged as a consistently valuable resource, esteemed by all visiting researchers throughout their entire TA projects, emphasizing its critical role from project initiation to completion. This extensive utilization

of services underscores the comprehensive support offered by the AUTH Living Environment Simulation, ensuring the success of TA research initiatives. More specifically:

Services used for ID34: Living lab project planning and management, Legal, regulation, and safety standard support, Capacity building, Expert opinion and advisory services, Co-creation session, Intake and matching, Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping, Panel management, Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation, Simulation test, Equipment and facility rental.

Prior to the in-person visit, the LL team along with the external researchers created and refined the research protocol through several virtual meetings, completing all necessary requirements for the ethical application and ensuring this way the project's legal compliance and safety. AUTH LL staff members, after having consulted the relevant experts and healthcare professionals and done an initial stakeholder mapping, they recruited the targeted population for the clinical trials (individuals with mild symptoms of dysphagia and healthy individuals). Upon the researchers' arrival, they initially conducted a couple of co-creation sessions with LL staff members and healthcare professionals from the "Hippokratia" General Hospital of Thessaloniki, mainly about feasibility issues. Afterwards, the visiting researchers had the opportunity to do some simulation tests, correcting critical technical issues that emerged with the support of the LL staff, and then they proceeded with the clinical trials inside the hospital and in AUTH Living Environment simulation as well. Lastly, it is important to be noted that for the realization of the testing, apart from the equipment that was brought by the researchers (ie. a 3D high resolution camera, a digital laryngophone etc.), there was also the need for the hosting LL to provide some additional equipment, such as dental kits (mirror, periodontal probe, glasses, headlight for the oral examination) and extension cords.

Services used for ID28: Living lab project planning and management, Capacity building, Expert opinion and advisory services, Co-creation session, Legal, regulation, and safety standard support.

Before the researcher's visit, several virtual meetings and communications needed in order to structure and refine the study protocol, offering guidance on compliance with legal and safety standards relevant to the specific research purposes. Also, main responsibility of the LL staff members prior to the researcher's arrival was to identify and engage the relevant stakeholders. In particular, the researcher, during the in-person visit, conducted co-creation sessions and semi-structured interviews with selected researchers of the AUTH Living Environment Simulation, who had experience in developing and using IoT-enabled mental health applications in order to gather useful insights about relevant privacy and data protection-related concerns.

Services used for ID31: Living lab project planning and management, Legal, regulation, and safety standard support, Capacity building, Expert opinion and advisory services, Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping, Panel management, Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation, Equipment and facility rental.

Prior to the in-person visit, the LL team along helped the external researchers to create a coherent research protocol through several virtual meeting, providing the necessary framework to ensure the project's legal compliance and safety and completing all necessary requirements for the ethical application. Also, prior to the visit, the LL staff members proceeded to an initial mapping and identification of the target population (ie. 20 master students) that was then recruited for the research purposes. During our three weeks visit, the hosting LL provided the researchers with two VR headsets in order for them to isolate the "text reading" stimulus and two Empatica wristbands to measure the students' stress level during the experiment, after supporting them with the initial set-up of the devices and resolution of technical issues. Several LL staff members supported the external researchers throughout the testing of all participants, as well as during the two intervention sessions conducted by the visiting researchers and facilitated by the LL manager.

Overall, the experience gained from the TA projects at AUTH Living Environment Simulation reflects a commendable level of communication, cooperation, and organization among visiting researchers, with effective collaboration and proactiveness evident throughout. Despite minor issues in some Transnational Access cases, particularly in administrative and management aspects, the majority of the projects were well-coordinated, showcasing excellent planning and execution of research processes. The successful resolution of challenges, including multiple modifications to protocols,

underscores the resilience and adaptability of both the researchers and the AUTH Living Lab staff. Valuable lessons include the importance of initiating stakeholder mapping and recruitment processes well in advance to streamline project management. This proactive approach allows for better preparation and minimizes potential delays in administrative or logistical matters. Furthermore, enhancing communication channels and providing comprehensive information to researchers ahead of their visit, especially regarding reimbursement processes and clarification of any potential doubts, contributes to a smoother and more efficient execution of transnational projects. This reflective analysis suggests that, while maintaining the current positive aspects, addressing these improvements can further optimize the processes and overall experience for future TA projects at AUTH Living Environment Simulation.

3.3. GAIA Smart Spaces

Between November 2023 and March 2024, GAIA Smart Spaces successfully supported four Transnational Access (TA) projects, engaging a total of seven researchers. The TA experience in GAIA Smart Spaces illustrate a diverse and innovative approach to integrating arts, technology, and health research, showcasing how living labs can foster significant advancements in healthcare and well-being, especially in aging populations, through collaborative and interdisciplinary research.

Across the four projects supported by GAIA Smart Spaces, several common services were integral to their success such as expert advisory services, stakeholder analysis, project planning and management, and co-creation processes were pivotal. These methodologies not only helped meet project goals but also laid groundwork for broader applications and future research.

As for the **Expert Opinion and Advisory Services**, experts in relevant fields like performing arts, public health, gerontology, and digital health were engaged to guide project design and ensure alignment with health and wellness objectives. This involved organizing various meetings with local and industry experts during the workshops. **Project Planning and Management** included managing logistics and scheduling for workshops, site visits, and online meetings to define researcher needs and ensure efficient resource use, adapted to specific challenges like those experienced in Israel during the period. Additionally, **Stakeholder Analysis and Mapping** was conducted for each project, identifying key stakeholders including local government officials, health experts, community members, tech developers, and artists. This process was essential for integrating their needs and expectations into the projects, ensuring that each initiative was well-informed and inclusive. **Co-Creation Sessions** were instrumental in developing and refining project concepts, ensuring community focus and inclusivity. Different stakeholders were actively involved in workshops to tailor interventions and solutions specific to each project's needs.

Project-Specific Services and Outcomes

Services used for ID70: Performing Arts-Smart Space Project, aimed to establish a Performing Arts-Smart Space to explore the impact of performing arts on physical and mental health in public spaces. Led by Connecteam Israel, the project emphasized inclusive user co-creation, with activities like workshops and visiting smart spaces with elderly people. It demonstrated potential health benefits of performing arts and suggested innovative art practices integrating technology. Involved services were Expert opinion and advisory services, stakeholder analysis and mapping, project planning and management, and co-creation sessions. Important to highlight that on the Project Planning and Management was challenging due to the situation of Israel during this period, with a huge effort needed to prepare the TA that was finally concentrated in a short period of time. In this period, GAIA team facilitated Co-creation Sessions with stakeholders to develop and refine the concept of Performing Arts-Smart Space, ensuring the project was community-focused and inclusive, with a successful workshop involving different stakeholders.

Services used for ID73: Let's get Actif Project, led by Actif Portugal, focused on assessing the impact of a digital platform on cognitive functions and physical capabilities of older adults. The project included comprehensive testing and feedback sessions. This project, included Expert opinion and advisory services, stakeholder analysis and mapping, project planning and management, co-creation sessions, prototyping tests, funding information, and usability testing, showcasing the

importance of digital health technologies in aging populations. Specifically, conducting Prototyping Tests and Usability Testing of the digital platform to assess functionality and gather user feedback on its ease of use and effectiveness, testing with a group of older people following some exercises included in the platform, ending with feedback and improvement suggestions. Also, providing Funding Information on potential funding sources to support project sustainability and expansion while meeting with local entities that offer financial support programmes for establishing the collaboration between companies. During the TA Expert Opinion and Advisory Services and Stakeholder Analysis was essential, working closely with gerontologists and digital health experts to ensure the platform met clinical standards and user needs. Different meetings organised during the TA with companies and other entities trying to identify common working points and collaboration opportunities. Results suggested improvements in cognitive functions and physical capabilities, demonstrating the effectiveness of the platform. The project underscored the importance of digital health technologies in aging populations.

Services used for ID76: Art Therapy and Vitamin D for Alzheimer's, Evaluated the combined impact of art therapy and vitamin D on elderly people with Alzheimer's, conducted by the University of Vlora, Albania. This project involved art sessions, health parameter monitoring, and identified broad applicability of non-pharmacological interventions in dementia care. This project took advantage of Expert opinion and advisory services, stakeholder analysis and mapping, project planning and management, co-creation sessions, prototyping tests, funding information, and usability testing. Specifically evaluating the therapeutic activities' design and implementation, through Prototyping Tests/ co-creation sessions ensuring they were appropriate for the elderly with Alzheimer's, and a small-scale pilot on art therapy performed with a group of older people (linked to painting). Were also key the Expert Opinion and Advisory Services and Stakeholder Analysis for which was ensured involvement of art companies' experts in different use of art in therapy, organizing meetings with the companies and other entities for identifying common working points and collaboration opportunities. This links with the provisiono Funding Information to secure support for expanding the project's scope and continuing its research, identifying potential future collaboration through EU calls.

Services used for ID96: Tech and Arts against Dementia, focused on non-pharmacological therapies using arts and technology for elderly dementia patients. It involved developing a guide for best practices and innovative ideas in art-based interventions. This project emphasized the integration of technology and arts, supporting the development of user-centered solutions. The services available for the TA team where mainly expert opinion and advisory services, stakeholder analysis and mapping, project planning and management, and co-creation sessions. Deserving to highlight the co-creation sessions collaborating with caregivers, dementia patients, and healthcare professionals to develop tailor interventions, the **Stakeholder Analysis and Mapping** identifying and engaging with tech developers and artists to incorporate their innovative solutions and creative insights into the project, and the **Access to Data, specifically** to relevant data sets for research purposes from previous projects, also linked the outcomes of this project with the previous TA research ID76.

3.4. INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living

Between October 2023 and March 2024, INTRAS MINDlab successfully supported three Transnational Access (TA) projects, engaging a total of nine researchers. These projects have not only contributed to the development and adaptation of tools and methodologies aimed at improving the quality of life for the elderly and individuals with cognitive impairments but also fostered international collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Before the in-person Transnational Access (TA), it was the standard procedure to implement preliminary virtual meetings to review the project and establish goals. This phase was crucial for setting the direction and expectations of the TA, leveraging Living Lab project planning and management services to ensure a cohesive approach. In the three TA's the **remote access period** before the in-person TA allowed for initial discussions and planning, laying the groundwork for a

productive exchange. The opportunity for **in-person TA** was reduced to a small segment of the time, so it was densely packed with activities designed to maximize the collaborative potential of the visit. Each day was structured to foster deep engagement with the Living Lab's resources and expertise.

The TA project's structured approach, from pre-TA planning through to post-TA reflections, showcases the effectiveness of a hybrid TA model enriched by targeted Living Lab services. The meticulous planning and execution facilitated by INTRAS MINDlab supported the project's goals, fostering an environment conducive to interdisciplinary collaboration.

TA Project Summaries and Reflective Analysis of the services provided

Services used for ID82: MinDNet lead by Kristina Niedderer from Manchester Metropolitan University, the MinDNet project aimed to enhance the MinD network's research activities in applying design to dementia and wellbeing. This project emphasized capacity building, expert opinion, and advisory services, alongside living lab project planning and management. The TA facilitated a week-long visit to INTRAS, focusing on workshops and training sessions that leveraged Living Lab methodologies for dementia and wellbeing. A notable outcome was the drafting of the AHRC Curiosity Award proposal, aimed at formalizing the network with a mindful co-design approach. This TA was pivotal in promoting inclusivity and empowering individuals across different life stages, setting a new standard for stakeholder engagement in design and dementia research. The highlighted services: i. Capacity Building and Expert Opinion services were fundamental in supporting the MinD network strategic planning. By leveraging expert insights and enhancing skills through capacity building, the project team could draft a significant proposal for the AHRC Curiosity Award, aimed at fostering an inclusive, mindful co-design approach; ii. Living Lab Project Planning and Management ensured efficient coordination and execution of workshops and training sessions, emphasizing Living Lab methodologies particularly in the context of dementia and wellbeing.

Services used for ID86: Span-ICanDo spearheaded by Isabelle Tournier from Université Paul-Valéry Montpellier 3, Span-ICanDo focused on adapting the "I Can Do Pathway" tool for the Spanish-speaking population, employing a co-design approach to evaluate its adaptability and usability. This project showcased the power of co-creation sessions and usability testing, bringing together individuals with mild cognitive impairments and their caregivers to refine the tool. The project underscored the importance of culturally sensitive interventions, leading to positive feedback and constructive suggestions for further simplification and digital adaptation of the tool. The core of the Span-ICanDo project was adapting the "I Can Do Pathway" tool for the Spanish-speaking population. The most important services provided were Co-Creation Sessions and Usability Testing. Co-creation sessions engaged end-users directly, ensuring the tool's adaptability and usability were evaluated from the perspectives of those it aimed to serve. This approach fostered a deeper understanding of end-user needs and contributed to the tool's refinement. Other important service was the Legal, Regulation, and Safety Standard Support, essential for navigating the complexities of adapting a health-related tool across different cultural and regulatory contexts, providing the necessary framework to ensure the project's legal compliance and safety.

Services used for ID94: CIM Douro led by João Rodrigues from the Douro Intermunicipal Community. The development of TA was supported by administrative coordination and planning, leveraging Living Lab project management services to ensure efficiency in administrative and research tasks. Close collaboration between Mind Lab and CIM Douro was crucial in this initial stage, laying the groundwork for the project, especially in its in-person phase. Additionally, it benefited from expert opinion and advisory guidance in interview script development and ethical guideline formulation, ensuring a solid and ethical research approach based on the legal, regulation and safety standard service. On the other hand, flexible fast-track training and knowledge exchange and prospective collaborations were highlighted as key elements for the project's success based on the LL capacity building service. These services provided by Mind Lab enabled a valuable exchange of knowledge and best practices, laying the foundation for future collaborative projects and continued growth in the Douro region.

By the end of the TA researchers had the opportunity to share with the team their experience and what was the aspect you would like to highlight from the TA with the Living Lab.

- ID82 Researcher: *“I am so impressed by the inclusive co-creation environment that Living Lab offers for experts by experience to have their voice in the co-creation process and the support for multidisciplinary team to develop creative product and service that promote health and wellbeing.”*
- ID86 Researcher: *“I really enjoyed having the opportunity to learn more about living labs and how they operate. I especially appreciated how the living lab activity is strongly interrelated with other social and healthcare activities. This allows to be as close as possible to people and their daily lives. Finally, I really liked the friendly, supportive, and inclusive atmosphere of the Intras team!”*

3.5. LiCalab older adults' homes

Of all three Thomas More research infrastructures, the LiCalab older adults' homes was the most popular. Seven projects involving 12 unique external researchers made use of this infrastructure between March 2023 and March 2024 (ID20, ID56, ID57, ID58, ID60, ID72, ID75). Project ID 57 also utilised the Thomas More Motion lab on top of the older adults' homes. Although the older adults' homes are not really a physical infrastructure, researchers really liked testing their innovations with end-users in a real-life home environment. After all, this is one of the core elements and strengths of Living Lab research. Participants for these studies are recruited from LiCalab's panel by our panel managers, who manage our panel database comprising healthy older adults and patients, as well as care professionals and care organisations. The panel managers are our single point of contact for the panel members and the world outside the Thomas More university of applied sciences.

Researchers benefitted from the relationship of trust LiCalab has with relevant stakeholders in their panel. It makes it easier to recruit participants, especially if the studies that are conducted are more intrusive in terms of privacy. Because of the community aspect of our panel, we experience that they are willing to do some extra efforts trying to comply to study requirements. In return, we provide them with feedback on the results of the studies they participated in. Being taken seriously, sharing their experiences and providing valuable insights to researchers are important intrinsic motivators for our panel members.

Collaboration with these external researchers from multiple disciplines was pleasant because we learned a lot from researcher's expertise in different fields. We also gained insights in their way of working or tackling some daily hassles. Collaboration was based on mutual respect. Because of the large amount of studies being conducted in a small-time span, the workload on the LL team was quite heavy. Most projects occurred in autumn - winter 2023-2024. Nevertheless, our panel manager even discovered a new talent in guiding the researchers around the most beautiful places in Belgium after installing technological innovations at participants houses.

In general, the amount of time spent on administration (e-mails regarding housing, insurance, reminders to complete questionnaires, checking receipts for invoices, etc.) far exceeded the person months that were allocated in the project. A flat rate for reimbursement of daily costs depending on the hosting country might be a good consideration for future projects. Other additional costs that were not anticipated to be reimbursed, concerned extra insurance costs and ethical submission costs. Future reimbursement for these should be based on the real expenses. When applying for free research, hearing about these extra costs was a threshold for some academic researchers as well as entrepreneurs or start-up employees. Furthermore, the amount of money for reimbursements of the daily costs was not sufficient to cover the actual expenses in Belgium. Often housing alone exceeded the budget of 100 euros a day in our region.

Most of the TA visits were shorter than anticipated based on researchers' applications. Some preparations and analyses were performed remotely before and after the TA. This led to a better work-life balance for some of the researchers. Hence, data collection for the study proposal was considered top priority during the TA visit. Consequently, the fast-track training program, originally foreseen to take place during two days at the beginning of their stay to immerse visitors into the world of LL research, was sometimes shortened and used in a flexible way, based on researchers' needs or interests.

LiCalab expects to collaborate again with most of the TA researchers that have been using this research infrastructure. A collaboration in a book chapter with the University of Stavanger (ID20) is ongoing. In addition, we plan to do some follow up soundscape workshops for the AI4S team of ID72, probably around June 2024. Furthermore, we have plans for joint publications and/or presentations regarding the work performed in ID58 and ID75.

In the paragraphs below, an overview can be found of the different services that were used for the Older adults' homes research projects.

Services used for ID20: Expert opinion, and advisory services; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Living lab project planning and management; Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping); panel management; co-creation session.

LiCalab panel managers recruited healthy older adults from their panel. Because these participants often do not speak or understand English, the co-creation sessions were moderated by the Dutch speaking panel managers. LiCalab staff helped in creating the scenarios for the sessions and exchanged best living lab practices with the researcher.

Services used for ID56: Capacity building; Living lab project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Expert opinion and advisory services; Intake and matching; panel management; co-creation session; prototyping test; usability testing.

LiCalab shared their best practices and advice on the developments of the scenarios for the co-creation sessions as well as the expert interviews. They made suggestions to prepare materials such as mock-up dashboards to improve visibility of the application which made evaluation easier for participants. Parkinson patients were recruited through the monthly newsletter and via patient organisations with whom LiCalab had worked in previous projects. Patients, informal care givers and care professionals gave feedback on the prototype and how results were presented in the application. The patient sessions were moderated in Dutch by the panel manager. The expert sessions were also moderated by the panel manager but were conducted in English. This enhanced participation of the external visitor during the session.

Services used for ID57: LL project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Intake and matching; panel management; concept and proof-of-concept test/concepts feasibility study; and small-scale real-life testing and experimentation.

Oonagh and Thomas More staff wrote the study protocol together to make sure all measurements were feasible in the RI and in accordance with legislation in both countries. Physical activity testing was conducted in the Thomas more Motion lab. After this two-hour session, the ten participants wore a smart watch that monitored their activity over a 3-month period. The LiCalab panel manager that had recruited the participants through LiCalab's panel was available in case any question arose during these home monitoring phase.

Services used for ID58: Innovation network orchestration; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; LL project planning and management; Intake and matching; panel management; co-creation session.

Although Suzanne did conduct two Lego serious play workshops, the focus of her visit was on gaining insight into the management and operations of a successful living lab. LiCalab staff shared best practices and exchanged ideas about panel management and how to keep a LL sustainable. The LiCalab panel manager recruited the healthy older adults from their panel database. Although the workshops were moderated by Suzanne, some translation to Dutch was necessary for the older adults.

Services used for ID60: Panel management; Living Lab project planning and management; expert opinion and advisory services; legal, regulation and safety standard support; prototype testing; small-scale real-life testing and experimentation; usability testing.

LiCalab reached out to care professionals from their panel to recruit rehabilitation centres willing to cooperate. Next, LiCalab staff helped shaping the research protocol and completed all necessary

requirements for the ethical application. Finally, the walking aid was tested with eight rehabilitants and 12 care professionals gave feedback on user experience and usability.

Services used for ID72: Living Lab project planning and management; Co-creation session; Expert opinion and advisory services; Panel management; Recruitment and matching; Legal, regulatory and safety standards support; Concept and proof of concept testing.

During the co-creation sessions the team worked with older adults to envision technologies and develop a deep understanding of their needs. They conducted a focus group to gather feedback on engagement, use and other issues. LiCalab's panel manager helped engaging participants for the duration of the ESM study and supporting co-creation activities. Additionally, LiCalab staff shared their best practices regarding practical advice on co-creation, panel management and deployment to contextualise findings and improve research practice. They provided support in developing a protocol that was appropriate to the Living Lab infrastructure, participant groups and research objectives. Regarding Legal, regulatory and safety standards support, LiCalab assisted obtaining Belgian ethical approval by converting the team's protocol documents into the format required by SMEC for KU Leuven. Living lab project planning and management services were provided when assisting the AI4S team in establishing appropriate protocols for older adults, reducing participant burden, and ensuring ecological validity. LiCalab also provided regional support for protocol translation and implementation as required. The final service used was concept and proof of concept testing. We used audio devices in a home setting to collect experience sampling and activity tracking data. This dataset will help understand daily soundscapes, sound preferences and analysis of memorable events.

Services used for ID75: Living lab project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Expert opinion and advisory services; Intake and matching; Panel management.

The expert opinion and advisory services were used to surface how LL projects were initiated, how they worked with multi-stakeholders, the tools they used (e.g. panel management, surveys, intake interviews and lab facilities (like the experience lab – Mobilab&Care) to offer services that allow businesses and other stakeholders to understand what the demand and issues are, what the services currently offer and then how they support partners to gain a greater understanding of whether an innovation would/could be used with the ambition for companies to commercialise product or services. Additionally, LiCalab facilitated contact with other Living Lab practitioners in the VITALISE consortium using Intake and matching services.

3.6. Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab

Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab has had a tremendous learning experience through facilitating transnational research projects, providing support to three distinct initiatives: the "Relationship between physical fitness, physical activity and healthy lifestyle in Seniors" (ID27), "VR for Seniors Well-being" (ID30), and "The effect of healthy lifestyle and friendly environment on mental health" (ID85). These projects span diverse domains, ranging from geriatric exercise science to virtual reality interventions and mental health promotion among seniors.

Throughout these engagements, several challenges have emerged, highlighting the importance of effective planning, communication, and collaboration in optimizing the outcomes of transnational research initiatives. One key lesson is the significance of early engagement and thorough planning before the in-person visits. Virtual meetings played a crucial role in project planning, ethical considerations review, recruitment of participants, and protocol development. This early engagement allowed for alignment of goals, clarification of expectations, and establishment of necessary groundwork for successful research execution. Moreover, the support provided by the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab extended beyond the initial planning stages, encompassing activities both before and after the in-person visits. Notably, our Living Lab facilitated translation services, stakeholder mapping, data aggregation, and interpretation support post-visit. This comprehensive assistance underscores the importance of ongoing support throughout the research process, from inception to dissemination of findings.

The impacts of these collaborations extend beyond the immediate outcomes of the research projects. The exchange of knowledge and expertise between external researchers and the Living Lab staff has enriched the research environment, fostering innovation and cross-disciplinary learning – which is of utmost importance for a Living Lab operating in a Widening country. Furthermore, the dissemination of research findings through co-authored scientific articles and presentations at academic conferences contributes to advancing knowledge in respective fields and promoting best practices in health and well-being research.

From the perspective of the researchers, the experience gained through collaboration with the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab has been invaluable. The seamless support provided by our Living Lab staff, coupled with our expertise and resources, has facilitated the execution of research activities and enhanced the quality of outputs. The collaborative nature of these engagements has fostered a mutually beneficial relationship, characterized by effective communication, shared learning, and a commitment to achieving common goals.

Unfortunately, the research visit for ID91 was cancelled, resulting in a missed opportunity for collaboration with the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab. Despite initial plans, administrative issues or other factors led to the cancellation, underscoring the challenges that can arise in coordinating transnational research endeavours. Reflecting on this cancellation, it's crucial to prioritize the signing of bilateral agreements before the TA's starting date to provide assurance and avoid resource allocation without guarantees. Streamlining procedures and addressing potential barriers, such as complicated contractual requirements, can prevent similar issues in the future. Additionally, enhancing communication channels and clarifying expectations regarding agreements and ethical applications can help prevent similar issues and ensure smoother collaboration. To improve future collaborations, establishing clear deadlines and decision criteria can prevent prolonged waiting periods for external researchers' special conditions. Maintaining firm boundaries regarding last-minute requests and improvisations can streamline processes and ensure smoother collaboration moving forward.

In conclusion, the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab has gained significant competencies to serve as a hub for transnational research collaboration, facilitating impactful initiatives aimed at promoting health and well-being across diverse populations. The lessons learned from these engagements underscore the importance of effective planning, ongoing support, and collaborative partnerships in realizing the full potential of transnational research endeavours. Moving forward, continued investment in such collaborative initiatives holds promise for advancing scientific knowledge, addressing societal challenges, and fostering innovation in health and well-being research.

In the paragraphs below, an overview of the different services used for the research projects can be found.

Services used for ID27: Relationship between physical fitness, physical activity and healthy lifestyle in Seniors

In this project, the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab provided crucial support both before and after the in-person visit. Before the visit, the Living Lab assisted with project planning through virtual meetings, identified and recruited potential participants, and reviewed the research protocol. Translation services were also provided for all research questionnaires. Post-visit, the Living Lab supported the researcher in aggregating and systematizing the data produced during the TA and provided tools and assistance for data analysis and interpretation. These services were instrumental in ensuring the smooth execution of the research project and maximizing its impact.

Services used for ID30: VR for Seniors Well-being

For this project, the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab offered essential assistance in project planning, ethical considerations review, and participant recruitment through virtual meetings. Additionally, translation and review of all ethics application documents were facilitated by the Living Lab. After the in-person visit, support was provided in aggregating and systematizing the data produced during the TA for the preparation of a co-authored scientific article. These services played

a critical role in enabling the successful implementation of the VR intervention and advancing understanding of its impact on seniors' well-being.

Services used for ID85 - The effect of healthy lifestyle and friendly environment on mental health.

In this project, the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab engaged in comprehensive support both before and after the in-person visit. Before the visit, the Living Lab participated in project planning, reviewed the research protocol, and facilitated translation of ethics application documents. Furthermore, internal ethics application revisions and submission were conducted with the Living Lab's support. Post-visit, the Living Lab assisted the researcher in aggregating and systematizing the data produced during the TA and provided tools and assistance for data analysis and interpretation. These services were instrumental in ensuring the ethical compliance, methodological rigor, and scientific rigor of the research project, thus enhancing its credibility and impact.

3.7. Laurea Activity Living Lab

Laurea Activity Living Lab has been very closely with the local stakeholders. Local football club, Leppävaaran Pallo, and its facilities played a crucial part of the TA researcher's activities. Also, a past Erasmus+ Sport funded project, 6-0!, enabled us to recruit former participants of that project to the VITALISE activities. Also, long common history with the city of Espoo Sports department helped us to contact desired participants to the TA activities. Without these pre-existing networks it would have been much more labouring act to fulfil the needs of the TA researchers.

Recruitment processes and preparatory tasks are quite time-consuming. For example, the ethical approval process requires significant time and should be initiated well in advance of the actual activities. Working with local senior citizens necessitates the use of the local language in all materials and activities, leading to extensive translation efforts throughout the process. Surprisingly, younger participants (aged 10-14 years) experienced practically no language barriers with English-speaking TA researchers. During the measurement sessions, no translation was needed between the participants and researchers. The activities were executed very smoothly. In the two intensive evening sessions, over 80 young participants were measured as planned.

When measuring physical activities with a personal device for senior participants, it's important to remember that this process will take time. Firstly, one must teach the participants how to use the device and ensure that they understand all technical instructions. Secondly, each participant is an individual actor, which means that the device must be delivered to and collected from each person individually. If the participants don't live very close to each other, it's easy to spend an entire day with just a couple of participant meetings. And this must be doubled – delivering and picking-up the measurement instruments.

It is important to coordinate feedback issues promised to the participants with the TA visitors. Since many of the activities will generate a large amount of material, it is vital to determine in advance what to offer the participants as compensation for their efforts. The collected data is likely to be stored in various repositories and formats, so someone will need to organize it into a format that can be delivered to the participants within a reasonable time frame. This may also require some translations.

If the TA researchers and LL have agreed to publish some of the data, a few normal things should be agreed. Who owns or can access the data? Where is it stored? Who makes the initiatives for data publishing (should be the primary author), and with what kind of timetable?

The impacts of these TA visits have been manifolded. It was gratifying to meet new researchers in our field and establish new networks. Hopefully, these interactions will lead to new collaborative initiatives and perhaps even new projects in the future. There have already been some initial discussions in this regard. Additionally, the senior participants were delighted to have been invited to participate in the activities. They gained valuable knowledge about their physical fitness issues. Laurea Activity LL will certainly continue to leverage these participant connections in the future. The TA activities also strengthened connections with the local club and other stakeholders. The local club intends to continue with the activities that were introduced during the TA visits.

From the Laurea Activity LL perspectives, it was great to understand that the LL equipment were up-to-date and plausible with the TA activities. Laurea Activity LL had also knowledge and competence that were usable to the TA visitors. Overall, TA visiting activity was an interesting and positive opportunity. It was time consuming and to be successful all tasks should be well planned before the actual TA visits. With this kind of project, it is always important to the visitors to understand that there are some mandatory administrative tasks that needs to be fulfilled. Sometimes this may require a little pushing to be executed.

Services used for ID40: Expert opinion, and advisory services; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Living lab project planning and management; Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping); panel management; co-creation session.

As the recreational football activity issues were familiar to Laurea Activity LL from a previous project, we had opinions and advice of how to build up and run such a desired activity. Ethical approval process included legal, regulation and safety issues that needed to consider during the TA activities. Laurea was in charge for the overall project planning and management. Stakeholder and participants were recruited by Laurea. We also arranged a co-creation workshop with the TA visitors to the stakeholder. As there were severe language barriers between researchers and senior participants, Laurea was in charge of running the workshop and collecting the material that was later translated to the visiting TA researchers.

Services used for ID45: Expert opinion, and advisory services; LL project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; panel management; concept and proof-of-concept test/concepts feasibility study; and small-scale real-life testing and experimentation.

TA visitor came with a technical solution but with empty content. Laurea Activity LL helped with the content issues. Some of Laurea's equipment was used to test the TA visitor's technical solution. Ethical approval process included legal, regulation and safety issues that needed to consider during the TA activities. The technical solution with new content inside was tested with a small amount of people. Feedback was collected from pilot testers and adjusted the system according to those. After that we executed a small-scale feasibility study with real-life testing and experimentation.

Services used for ID 71: Expert opinion, and advisory services; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Living lab project planning and management; Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping); real-life testing and experimentation.

The TA visit and activities were planned together with TA researchers according to their ideas and hopes. Ethical approval process included legal, regulation and safety issues that needed to consider during the TA activities. As the participants were underaged the ethical process was quite precise and thorough. Laurea Activity LL recruited the participants through its network to match the need for TA researchers. Laurea also planned and managed the activities with the local football club coaches. The desired protocol was implemented in real-life environment mostly with Laurea Activity LL measurement systems.

3.8. AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

Out of all applications, three TA projects involving seven individual researchers have been conducted between February 2023 and March 2023. While two of these projects could be implemented based on the existing services and user panel of AIT (ID24 and ID90), a new partnership with a Viennese therapy centre had to be established in order to ensure access to the specific patient group necessary for the third project (ID83). While four researchers performed their TA project completely based on visiting the AIT Technology Experience Laboratory in Vienna, three researchers combined physical visits of the research infrastructure with remote access.

Researchers benefitted from AIT's the existing relationships with relevant stakeholders in their panel. It helped to recruit participants, especially if the studies for user groups that AIT was already in contact with in the past (e.g. caregivers of persons with dementia). In addition to the actual Living Lab services provided, AIT's experience on working with vulnerable user and patient groups proved to be a very important prerequisite for the successful implementation of the TA projects.

Collaboration with the external researchers from multiple disciplines was beneficial also for the AIT staff because of the exchange of experiences in multiple fields. In particular, working together with external researchers enabled a reflection of own working practices, applied tools and research methods.

Reflecting on the efforts needed for supporting the external researchers, two projects could be implemented with reasonable time invested (ID24 and ID90). On the other hand, the complexity of the third project (ID83) led to a heavy workload for the Living Lab team, both for preparing the activity, but also during the actual study implementation. In addition to the actual Living Lab services provided, the amount of time spent on administration (secondment agreement, reminders to complete questionnaires, checking receipts for invoices, etc.) exceeded the efforts that were initially foreseen in the project. Therefore, simplified processes for involving and reimbursing researchers would have been desirable. Reimbursing could e.g. be simplified by allowing a flat rate for reimbursement of daily costs. Furthermore, the amount of money for reimbursements of the daily costs was not sufficient to cover the actual expenses in Austria. In the case of stay housing in Vienna alone exceeded the budget of 100 euros per day.

AIT expects to collaborate again with most of the TA researchers that have been using this research infrastructure. Results of project ID83 are planned to be published collaboratively in a scientific study. Work performed on the target group of caregivers of persons with dementia (ID24 and ID90) are also planned to be continued: As follow-up of project ID90 a joint project proposal to be submitted within the current call of the Partnership for European Partnership on Transforming Health and Care Systems is planned.

Services used for ID 24: Living lab project planning and management, Expert opinion, and advisory services.

Collaboration on this project heavily relied on intensive joint work on reviewing the evaluation toolkit and exchanging experiences on working with the target group of caregivers of persons with dementia in order to derive an evaluation toolkit suitable for this target group. The stakeholder network of AIT allowed to receive additional external feedback on the derived questionnaire.

Services used for ID 83: Living lab project planning and management, Expert opinion, and advisory services, Usability testing.

Preparation for this TA activity was rather time-consuming, since the implementation of this study required an alignment with an ongoing research activity at AIT. Based on the same reason, this AT project had to be organized in a way that the external researcher joined the AIT team in Vienna within two separate stays. Expert services provided by AIT mainly considered methodological counselling and exchange as well as sharing experience on data collection tools for conducting experience sampling studies.

Services used for ID 90: Living lab project planning and management, Expert opinion, and advisory services, Legal, regulation and safety standard support, Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation.

Beyond administrative challenges and time-consuming preparations, main learnings out of this TA project are on the collaboration with an external therapy centre in Vienna. Recruitment and involvement of study participants required the establishment of a direct communication channel between the external researchers, AIT's Living Lab team and the team of the therapy centre. In addition, this project also helped to collect experiences and to set up processes for dealing with the language barrier that arose especially for having English-speaking researchers conducting a study in a Viennese therapy centre (e.g. by foreseeing sufficient time for briefing the involved German-speaking study facilitators).

4. Conclusion

This final comprehensive report presents an overview about the performed TA activities to seven research infrastructures that participate in WP10 TA3 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for Everyday Living, highlighting the significance of transnational access in facilitating collaborative research efforts across different research infrastructures. By granting researchers access to state-of-the-art Living Lab infrastructures, the project aims to foster innovation and advance knowledge in the field of everyday living, demonstrating the power of collaborative, interdisciplinary research.

This final report offers a snapshot of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP10's TA3. It signifies the project's progress towards fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of everyday living. This report serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, providing insights into the project's TA outcomes, illustrating the strides made in promoting innovation and facilitating knowledge exchange.

5. Annexes

T3 AFTER TA EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE (MANDATORY)

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Disclaimer

The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

Dear researcher,

Thank you very much for participating in our Vitalise Transnational Access.

We highly appreciate you taking the time to reply to this mandatory questionnaire as it will help us continue improving the content of the Transnational Access for future participants. Completion of the questionnaire will take approximately 5-10 minutes.

The questionnaire is **not anonymous**. The next set of questions, comprising the sections Transnational Access, Living lab collaboration and Vitalise products, invite you to reflect on your journey and provide feedback on the Transnational Access.

Kind regards,

The Vitalise consortium

* Name of the researcher filling the questionnaire [Open question]

TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS

* 1. How likely are you to recommend the Transnational Access to your colleagues or other researchers (0 not at all – 10 very likely)?

Only values of at most 10 are allowed

* 2. How well were your expectations regarding the Transnational Access met?

- +2 TA output was much higher than expected
- +1 TA output was somewhat higher than expected
- 0 TA output was as expected
- 1 TA output was somewhat lower than expected
- 2 TA output was much lower than expected

* 3. How useful is the inclusion of a Fast Track Training program during Transnational Access? (0 not useful - 10 very useful)

Only values of at most 10 are allowed

* 4. What did you appreciate most about the Transnational Access? [Open question]

* 5. Do you have any suggestions for improvement concerning the Transnational Access? [Open question]

LIVING LAB COLLABORATION

6. Please rate the following services provided by the hosting Living Lab in terms of quality. If services are not applicable to your study, please indicate this in the right column. [partly open question]

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Understand end-user needs and problems	<input type="radio"/>					
* Methodological support and guidance	<input type="radio"/>					
* Selection/recruitment of test persons	<input type="radio"/>					
* Expertise/support with end users (co-creation, field test, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
* Physical infrastructure (research labs, tools, co-creation space, demo house, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					

Other, namely ...

* 7A. Please select the research infrastructure(s) you have visited. Multiple answers are possible.

- LICALAB / LiCalab Older Adults Homes
- LICALAB / MOBILAB & Care – Motion lab
- LICALAB / Thomas More Experience lab
- AUTH / AUTH Living Environment simulation
- AUTH / AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab
- AUTH / AUTH Centrifuge Rehabilitation Living Lab
- AIT / AIT Technology Experience Lab
- TREABAG / Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab
- GAIA / GAIA and Smart Spaces
- GAIA / GAIA Ozean Living Lab
- INTARS / INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab
- INTARS / INTRAS VR/AR Environment and Snoezelen Room
- INTARS / INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living
- McGill / McGill-UDEM-CRIR Living Lab
- UPM / LifeSpace by UPM
- LAUREA / Laurea Simulated Hospital
- LAUREA / Laurea Activity Living Lab

* 7B. What do you think are key strengths in terms of expertise/coaching/etc. of [answer 7A]'s present research infrastructure from the perspective of your research or study? [Open question – this question should be presented for all RI selected]

* 7C. What weaknesses in [answer 7A]'s present research infrastructure do you believe need to be addressed? (These could include any aspect of the institution that hinders your research productivity). [Open question - this question should be presented for all RI selected]

VITALISE PRODUCTS

8. How often did you use any of the following Vitalise products during your Transnational Access?

	0 - Never	1 - Once	2- Several times	3 - Weekly	4 - Daily
* Data Tool	<input type="radio"/>				
* Panel Management tool	<input type="radio"/>				
* Vitalise website	<input type="radio"/>				
* Vitalise Wiki page	<input type="radio"/>				

9. Please rate the following products in terms of user friendliness. If a product was not applicable to your study, please indicate this in the right column.

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Data Tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Panel Management tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Vitalise website	<input type="radio"/>					
* Vitalise Wiki page	<input type="radio"/>					

10. Please rate the following products in terms of usefulness as it relates to your research process. If a product was not applicable to your study, please indicate this in the right column.

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Data Tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Panel Management tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Vitalise website	<input type="radio"/>					
* Vitalise Wiki page	<input type="radio"/>					

* 11. In what way did any of these products affect your Transnational Access work? (for example, saved me time, greater accuracy, etc.)
[Open question]

12. How much do you anticipate needing the following services or products in your future work? (Very low probability – very high probability).

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Understand end-user needs and problems	<input type="radio"/>					
* Methodological support and guidance	<input type="radio"/>					
* Selection/recruitment of test persons	<input type="radio"/>					
* Expertise/support with end users (co-creation, field test, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
* Physical infrastructure (research labs, tools, co-creation space, demo house, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
* Data tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Panel management tool	<input type="radio"/>					

13. Is there any other service or product you anticipate needing in your future research? [Open question]

14. Any additional comments you would like to share with us? [Open question]

Thank you very much!

Submit